

**Estimating Deceiving Signatures
and their Role in the Observation of the
VBF Production Mode in the
Higgs-Boson Decay into two *W* Bosons**

by

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Abstract

The Higgs boson is the most recently discovered fundamental particle and its precise characterization is an important test of the Standard Model. For these measurements, the decay into two W bosons is crucial because of the large branching ratio, the sensitivity to vector-boson couplings and the theoretical implications on WW scattering. The proton-proton collisions at the LHC with a centre-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV provide an excellent environment to study the Higgs boson. The data recorded by the ATLAS experiment between 2015 and 2018 is analyzed. With an integrated luminosity of 139/fb, it allows to measure precisely the two dominant production modes, gluon fusion (ggF) and vector-boson fusion (VBF).

Only collisions with one electron and one muon in the final state are considered and cuts are applied to select signal-like events. For the VBF process, the selection is further refined with the help of a deep neural network. Then, the purified dataset is analyzed with a statistical model constructed from MC simulation and a data-driven background estimate of misidentified leptons. The cross sections times branching ratio are measured to be 12.4 ± 1.5 pb for the ggF and $0.79^{+0.19}_{-0.16}$ pb for the VBF processes. For the first time, the VBF process is observed in this decay channel with a significance of 6.6 standard deviations. Also measurements of eleven Simplified Template Cross Sections are performed and found to be consistent with the Standard Model.

This precise measurement could only be achieved because the treatment of events with misidentified leptons was improved significantly. These deceiving signatures are estimated with the data-driven Fake Factor Method. An auxiliary measurement is performed to extract fake factors in a phase space with a Z boson recoiling against a jet that is misidentified as lepton. This measurement is presented together with the relevant experimental improvements. As a result of this work, the uncertainties could be reduced to an extent that they do not significantly affect the measurement of the Higgs-boson cross section.

Even though the Fake Factor Method is experimentally well-established, a consistent derivation for a phase space with many leptons does not exist. In this thesis, it is shown for the first time that the Fake Factor Method can be derived exactly from the Matrix Method for an arbitrary number of misidentified leptons. In addition, the uncertainty estimate is considered and cases are derived in which the fake estimate does not exhibit Gaussian uncertainties.

Keywords: ATLAS experiment; Higgs boson; Higgs to WW decay; Fake leptons; Fake factor method; Machine learning

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Chapter 1

Introduction

“..., 18, 19, 20. Ready or not, here I come!”, is what children learn to play. They are introduced to the idea of counting early in life and the concept has a central role in most cultures. Counting is also crucial in experimental high-energy physics, despite the probabilistic nature of the underlying physical processes. Measurements of cross sections are typically performed as counting experiments. In a large number of proton-proton collisions, only a small number of collision events produce Higgs bosons. The goal of a cross-section measurement is to count these events and derive from it the cross section, which determines the production rate of Higgs bosons.

Cross sections are a main characteristic of fundamental quantum mechanical processes and carry information about the interactions of the involved particles. In this thesis, the production cross section of the Higgs boson is measured. The Higgs boson is a basic component in the Standard Model of particle physics, the theory that describes fundamental particles and their interactions. Since its discovery in 2012, many measurements have characterized the Higgs boson and determined its properties. This thesis presents the most precise cross-section measurement to date in the decay to two W bosons. Two production modes are investigated: vector-boson fusion (VBF) and gluon fusion (ggF). In fact, the VBF signal is so prominent after the analysis of the data that its production with large statistical significance can be claimed.

To determine the cross section, one wants to count only collisions with a Higgs boson. But these events are difficult to identify and distinguish from other similar events, the background processes. The amount of background contamination is reduced by requiring that the collisions look similar to Higgs-boson decays, but some background events are inevitably still counted. Therefore, it is important to estimate the amount of remaining background. A particularly intricate background is comprised of events with deceiving signatures that lead to misidentification of particles. These events are called *fake events* and do not usually look similar to Higgs-boson decays, but the particle misidentification allows them to enter the count. The estimate of these fake events is a second focus of this thesis.

The number of fake events is estimated with a data-driven procedure, the Fake Factor Method. In this method, the original dataset is filtered for events with a signature different

from events containing a Higgs boson and the contribution of fake events is measured. Then, the measured yield is extrapolated into the Higgs-boson measurement to give an estimate of the background contribution. The Fake Factor Method is well established and used in various analyses in high-energy physics, but its mathematical details are not obvious, especially in situations where multiple misidentified particles enter an analysis. The derivation of the Fake Factor Method is a third major part of this thesis. It shows that the method works for cases with an arbitrary number of particles that can be misidentified. This is a more general result than given anywhere else in the literature.

1.1 Thesis Structure and Contribution

The basic concepts of the Standard Model of particle physics are summarized in chapter 2 and the relevance of the Higgs boson at the Large Hadron Collider is outlined. Chapter 3 gives an overview of the ATLAS detector, the experimental setup with which the proton-proton collisions are recorded, and the central algorithms to reconstruct signatures of various particle types. The recorded dataset and the corresponding simulations are described in chapter 4.

The description in these chapters is based on existing publications or documentation. The experimental setup is the result of decades of work by the ATLAS collaboration from detector design to reconstruction algorithms and simulations. The author contributed to the communal effort, for example, with feasibility studies for a new detector (see appendix A about the Inner Tracker), detector operation shifts in 2018 and technical improvements of core analysis software. Section 3.3.4 shows optimization studies for the later analyses. The work was performed by the author together with a colleague. This section is marked with a \star to indicate that knowledge of the later chapters simplifies the understanding.

Chapter 5 features the novel derivation of the data-driven Fake Factor Method together with a study of the uncertainties. These concepts are then applied to data in chapter 6, where they lay the foundation for a precise estimate of fake processes. Finally, the preparations in the previous chapters culminate in the measurement of the Higgs-boson cross section¹ in chapter 7 and the observation of the VBF production mode in the decay to two W bosons. The extension to Simplified Template Cross Sections is shown in chapter 8. Chapter 9 summarizes the results and lists potential improvements for future measurements.

Chapter 5 is based on the preceding concepts of the Matrix Method and Fake Factor Method. The coherent description, generalization and statistical studies were developed by the author and independently of the ATLAS collaboration. The estimate of fake events with the Z +fake analysis in chapter 6 builds on a previous analysis, but was overhauled with major improvements by the author, who had a leading role in this effort. For chapters 7 and 8, the author had a strong involvement in optimizing the lepton selection and rejection,

¹This measurement will be referred to as “HWW analysis” in later chapters.

defining signal and control regions, deriving theoretical uncertainties and developing hybrid fit models with data and simulation for validation purposes. Also the deep neural network, that was developed at SFU and replaced the earlier approach, was initiated by the author. Parts of sections 3.3.4, 6.2.4 and 6.2.5 as well as Appendix A were initially written by the author for ATLAS-internal documentation and replicated later in this thesis.

Chapter 2

Higgs Boson in the Standard Model

The Standard Model of particle physics is a consistent description of the fundamental particles known today and their interactions. It combines different forces and was able to predict some particles that were later discovered in experiments. The Higgs boson as the last missing particle was discovered in 2012 [1, 2].

This chapter is divided in two parts. The first one gives a brief overview of the Standard Model of particle physics with a focus on the electroweak symmetry breaking and the Higgs boson. This part mainly follows the textbook in Ref. [3] with some additional input from Refs. [4, 5]. To avoid unnecessary bloating of references, detailed citations of the original papers are not given. Please refer to the references in Ref. [3]. The second part of this chapter discusses in more detail the production and decay of the Higgs boson and its observation in previous measurements.

2.1 The Standard Model of Particle Physics

The lengthy equations of the Standard Model can be written more concisely by following some special notational conventions. The Einstein summation notation is used, summing over pairs of same indices in an equation. Typically, indices with Greek letters stand for summation over four space-time coordinates with the metric $g_{\mu,\nu} = (1, -1, -1, -1)$. In other cases indices of the Latin alphabet are used. Natural units are used by conventionally setting the speed of light and the reduced Planck constant to $c = \hbar = 1$.

2.1.1 Particle Content

All fundamental particles are classified into two categories depending on their spin. Particles with half-integer spin are called fermions and they comprise all classical matter. The other category, bosons, contains particles with integer spin. The bosons mediate the three forces,

the electromagnetic, the weak and the strong forces. By exchange of these force carriers, particles are able to interact with each other.

The properties of fermions are largely determined by the type of force with which they interact. To describe the coupling between particles and force carriers, they are assigned the property of charge. The charge, one for each force, determines whether and how strongly the particles interact. All quarks, a subgroup of fermions, carry one of three colour charges, required for the interaction via the strong force. The other fermion subgroup, leptons, do not carry any colour charge. The electric charge can take two values for each fermion subgroup. Quarks carry an electric charge of $2/3$ or $-1/3$. Leptons that carry an electric charge of -1 are called charged leptons, while leptons without electric charge are called neutrinos. The weak isospin, which depends on the chirality of the particle, describes the interaction with the weak force.

All fermions have a mass¹. Each of the four fermion types described above contains three physical fermions with different masses. The fermions are categorized in three generations from light to heavy. All fermions also have an anti-fermion partner that has all quantum numbers inverted. The “anti” is usually dropped, because the particle/antiparticle ambiguity can be resolved by context. When talking about experimental signatures, it is customary to refer to “charged leptons” simply as “leptons”.

The bosons with spin 1 are the gluon, photon and W^\pm and Z bosons. They mediate the strong, electromagnetic and weak interactions, respectively. Since some of them also carry the relevant charge, they can also interact with themselves. The Higgs boson is the only spin-0 particle. It is not associated with one of the fundamental forces and interacts with all particles that have mass. All particles and some of their properties are summarized in Figure 2.1.

2.1.2 Gauge Invariance of Lagrangian Density

Mathematically, the Standard Model is formulated as a relativistic quantum-field theory. It is expressed in terms of a Lagrangian density $\mathcal{L}(\phi, \partial_\mu\phi)$ as a function of the fields ϕ and their partial derivatives $\partial_\mu\phi = \frac{\partial}{\partial x^\mu}\phi$, where μ runs over the time and space components. Like in classical mechanics, the principle of least action determines the equivalent of the Euler-Lagrange equation

$$\partial_\mu \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial (\partial_\mu \phi)} \right) - \left(\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial \phi} \right) = 0. \quad (2.1)$$

¹Even though only upper limits on the mass have been measured, neutrino oscillations first discovered in Ref. [6] provide indirect evidence that neutrinos are massive. Because neutrino masses are comparatively small and do not directly affect the experimental chapters of this thesis, the description of the Standard Model in this chapter ignores neutrino masses and their implications on the particle content.

Figure 2.1: Particles in the Standard Model with their masses. The electric and colour charges as well as spins are indicated in the top right and bottom right corners, respectively. The mass values in the top left corner are taken from Ref. [7].

Then the free Lagrangians for spin-0, spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ and spin-1 particles are given by

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Klein-Gordon}} = \frac{1}{2}(\partial^\mu \phi)^*(\partial_\mu \phi) - \frac{m^2}{2}\phi^* \phi, \quad (2.2)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Dirac}} = \bar{\psi}(i\gamma^\mu \partial_\mu - m)\psi, \quad (2.3)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Proca}} = -\frac{1}{4}F^{\mu\nu}F_{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2}mA^\mu A_\mu, \quad (2.4)$$

because they give the Klein-Gordon, Dirac and Proca equations of motion after applying equation (2.1). The variable ϕ describes a spin-0 field, ψ a Dirac spinor and A^μ a vector field. The matrices γ^μ are the Dirac matrices, $\bar{\psi}$ is defined by $\bar{\psi} = \psi^\dagger \gamma^0$ and the field strength tensor $F^{\mu\nu}$ is defined by $F^{\mu\nu} = \partial^\mu A^\nu - \partial^\nu A^\mu$ in the case of an Abelian vector field². Every equation also contains a term involving the mass m of the particle.

In the Standard Model, the interactions of fermions are derived by requiring that the Standard Model be invariant under local gauge transformations of the gauge groups

$$G = SU(3)_C \times SU(2)_L \times U(1)_Y. \quad (2.5)$$

To make the free-particle Lagrangian in equation (2.3) locally gauge invariant, new gauge fields G_a^μ , W_i^μ and B^μ are introduced. These fields are included in the Lagrangian by replacing

²In case of non-Abelian vector fields, another term needs to be included in the field strength tensor, like seen in equation (2.10) for the $SU(3)$ and equation (2.18) for the $SU(2)$ groups.

∂_μ by the covariant derivative D_μ , which is defined as

$$D^\mu = \partial_\mu + ig_3 \frac{\lambda_a}{2} G_a^\mu + ig_2 \frac{\tau_i}{2} W_i^\mu + ig_1 Y B^\mu \quad (2.6)$$

with the constants g_1 , g_2 and g_3 . The new fields transform under gauge transformations such that they make the overall Lagrangian invariant. After correctly interpreting the gauge fields, they reveal the interactions of the Standard Model. The first additional term in the covariant derivative, which is associated with the strong interaction is described by Quantum Chromodynamics (QCD). This part of the Standard Model can be treated independently of the electroweak (EW) theory, whose interactions are determined by the last two terms in the covariant derivative. The Lagrangian of the Standard Model is the sum of the individual ones

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SM}} = \mathcal{L}_{\text{QCD}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{EW}}. \quad (2.7)$$

2.1.3 Quantum Chromodynamics

The Lagrangian density describing strong interactions is

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{QCD}} = \bar{q}_r^\alpha i \gamma_\mu D_\alpha^{\mu\beta} q_{r\beta} - \frac{1}{4} G_{\mu\nu}^i G^{\mu\nu i}. \quad (2.8)$$

The first term has the same form as equation (2.3) and describes the quarks q , whose flavour is labelled with the subscript $r = u, d, s, c, b, t$, and their interaction with gluons. Quarks also carry an explicit label α, β for their colour state, that can take the values r, g, b , commonly referred to as red, green, blue. Colour labels are also denoted explicitly in the covariant derivative, whose relevant part for QCD is

$$D_\alpha^{\mu\beta} = \partial^\mu \delta_\alpha^\beta + g_s \frac{\lambda_{a\alpha}^\beta}{2} G_a^\mu. \quad (2.9)$$

The matrices λ_a are the eight Gell-Mann matrices [8], the infinitesimal generators of the $SU(3)$ group. The fields G_a^μ represent gluons, the force carriers of the strong interaction. In order to interpret the gluon fields as spin-1 particles, a term corresponding to their kinetic energy is needed. This is the second term in equation (2.8) using the definition

$$G_{\mu\nu}^i = \partial_\mu G_\nu^i - \partial_\nu G_\mu^i - g_s f_{ijk} G_\mu^j G_\nu^k, \quad (2.10)$$

where the tensor f_{ijk} is defined by the relation $[\lambda_i, \lambda_j] = 2i f_{ijk} \lambda_k$. Because the symmetry group $SU(3)$ is non-Abelian, the Lagrangian contains terms with up to four gluons, describing the self-interaction of the strong force carriers.

In comparison with the covariant derivative in equation (2.6), the generic constant g_3 is replaced with g_s in equation (2.9) and interpreted as the strong coupling constant. When transition amplitudes are calculated for processes with higher-order corrections,

divergences occur. By renormalizing these equations, the divergences are absorbed into physical observables, conventionally the coupling constant. As a consequence, the effective coupling constant $g_s(\mu_R^2)$ depends on the renormalization scale μ_R , at which the divergences are cut off. Due to the self-interaction of gluons, the effective coupling constant decreases as a function of energy. Hence, the strong interaction is small for processes with large momentum transfer. This effect is described as asymptotic freedom. Conversely, for processes with small momentum transfer, which is associated with long distances, the coupling constant is large and consequently free colour charges do not occur.

When quarks form bound states, their overall color is neutral. This can be achieved by cancelling a colour charge with the respective anti-colour charge. This happens in mesons with one quark and one anti-quark $q\bar{q}$. The alternative is to combine the three colour charges or three anti-colour charges to colour-neutral objects. These objects are called baryons and consist of three quarks qqq or three anti-quarks $\bar{q}\bar{q}\bar{q}$. Collectively, these two particle types are called hadrons.

The low-energetic behaviour of the strong interaction inside hadrons is governed by non-perturbative QCD. To describe the composition of hadrons, the corresponding behaviour below a certain energy, the factorization scale μ_F , is absorbed into parton distribution functions (PDF) $f_i(x, \mu_F^2)$. These PDFs describe the number density of the quark and gluon³ types in a hadron as a function of the factorization scale and the fraction of the hadron momentum x carried by parton i . Because PDFs cannot be calculated perturbatively, they are measured in data. It is possible to extrapolate a PDF at fixed momentum fraction x to other values of μ_F^2 using the DGLAP equations, named after the authors of Refs. [9–11]. This is how Figure 2.2 was created.

2.1.4 Electroweak Theory

The weak and electromagnetic parts of the Standard Model are treated together because they are unified in the electroweak theory. The Lagrangian can be split into multiple parts

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{EW}} = \mathcal{L}_f + \mathcal{L}_{\text{gauge}} + \mathcal{L}_\phi + \mathcal{L}_{\text{Yuk}}. \quad (2.11)$$

The weak force treats fermions differently depending on their chirality. The left-chiral and right-chiral projection operators are $P_L = (1 - \gamma^5)/2$ and $P_R = (1 + \gamma^5)/2$, respectively. The operators have the opposite effect when acting on anti-fermions. The left-chiral fermions are combined into doublets in $SU(2)_L$ space, whereas right-chiral fermions are singlets:

$$q_L^0 = \begin{pmatrix} u_L^0 \\ d_L^0 \end{pmatrix}, u_R^0, d_R^0; \quad l_L^0 = \begin{pmatrix} \nu_L^0 \\ e_L^0 \end{pmatrix}, e_R^0. \quad (2.12)$$

³Quarks and gluons are collectively called partons.

Figure 2.2: The PDFs $f_i(x, Q^2)$ in a proton times momentum fraction x . In this combination, the integrals over all distributions sum up to 1, the total proton momentum. Shown are the four lightest quarks and anti-quarks as well as the gluon at the energy scale $Q = 125$ GeV. The gluon is shown as solid line and each quark/anti-quark type with a different dash pattern. The lines for the c and \bar{c} quark are undistinguishable in this figure. The PDFs have been calculated from the PDF4LHC15 [12] set at NNLO using APFEL 2.7.1 Web [13].

In a doublet, the upper fermion has a weak isospin of $T^3 = \frac{1}{2}$, while the lower fermion has $T^3 = -\frac{1}{2}$. Right-chiral particles carry no weak isospin. The weak hypercharge Y has the same role in $U(1)_Y$ as weak isospin does in $SU(2)_L$. It is defined as

$$Y = Q - T^3, \quad (2.13)$$

where Q and T^3 refer to the electric charge and third component of the weak isospin of a field. With these definitions, the first part of the electroweak Lagrangian can be written as

$$\mathcal{L}_f = \sum_f \bar{f}^0 i \gamma^\mu D_\mu f^0, \quad (2.14)$$

where the sum loops over all fermions in equation (2.12) and the relevant part of the covariant derivative is

$$D^\mu = \partial^\mu + ig_2 \frac{\tau_i}{2} W_i^\mu + ig_1 Y B^\mu. \quad (2.15)$$

Equivalently to the second term in equation (2.8), the newly introduced fields have a kinetic-energy term

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{gauge}} = -\frac{1}{4} W_{\mu\nu}^i W^{\mu\nu i} - \frac{1}{4} B_{\mu\nu} B^{\mu\nu}, \quad (2.16)$$

	left-chiral			right-chiral		
	T^3	Q	Y	T^3	Q	Y
ν^0	1/2	0	-1/2	-	-	-
e^0	-1/2	-1	-1/2	0	-1	-1
u^0	1/2	2/3	1/6	0	2/3	2/3
d^0	-1/2	-1/3	1/6	0	-1/3	-1/3

Table 2.1: Third component of the weak isospin T^3 , electric charge Q and weak hypercharge Y for fermions.

where the field strength tensor for the Abelian field B^μ is defined like in section 2.1.2 and the tensor for the non-Abelian W^μ has an additional term like in the strong interaction

$$B_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu B_\nu - \partial_\nu B_\mu \quad (2.17)$$

$$W_{\mu\nu}^i = \partial_\mu W_\nu^i - \partial_\nu W_\mu^i - g_2 \epsilon_{ijk} W_\mu^j W_\nu^k. \quad (2.18)$$

The last two terms in equation (2.11) involve a complex, scalar field ϕ , that is a doublet in $SU(2)_L$ like the left-chiral quarks and leptons, and is parametrized as

$$\phi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} \phi_1 + i\phi_2 \\ \phi_3 + i\phi_4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \phi^+ \\ \phi^0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (2.19)$$

The first corresponding entry in the Lagrangian density is

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = (D^\mu \phi)^\dagger D_\mu \phi - V(\phi) \quad (2.20)$$

$$\text{with } V(\phi) = \mu^2 \phi^\dagger \phi + \lambda (\phi^\dagger \phi)^2. \quad (2.21)$$

In all of the Lagrangians so far, only fermions of one generation are written explicitly. To generalize the equations for the three fermion generations in the Standard Model, a sum over three generations can be added. For the last term of the electroweak Lagrangian in equation (2.11), this sum is written explicitly to allow mixing between the terms of different generations.

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Yuk}} = - \sum_{m,n=1}^3 (\Gamma_{mn}^u \bar{q}_{mL}^0 \tilde{\phi} u_{nR}^0 + \Gamma_{mn}^d \bar{q}_{mL}^0 \phi d_{nR}^0 + \Gamma_{mn}^e \bar{\ell}_{mL}^0 \phi e_{nR}^0) + \text{h.c.} \quad (2.22)$$

The matrices Γ define the fermion masses. The variable $\tilde{\phi}$ is defined as $\tilde{\phi} = i\tau^2 \phi^\dagger$.

The physical relevance of the electroweak Lagrangian becomes visible after two additional steps, in which the Lagrangian is rewritten. Firstly, the multiplication of $\tau_i W_i^\mu$ reveals that the interaction between electrons and neutrinos is mediated by a combination of the fields W_1^μ and W_2^μ . These linear combinations are reinterpreted as the physical W^\pm bosons. Similarly,

the fields W_3^μ and B_0^μ are reinterpreted as the photon field A^μ and the Z boson Z^μ

$$W^{\pm\mu} = \frac{W_1^\mu \mp W_2^\mu}{\sqrt{2}} \quad Z^\mu = \frac{-g_1 B^\mu + g_2 W_3^\mu}{\sqrt{g_1^2 + g_2^2}} \quad A^\mu = \frac{g_1 B^\mu + g_2 W_3^\mu}{\sqrt{g_1^2 + g_2^2}}. \quad (2.23)$$

The relation between the constants g_1 and g_2 can be expressed in terms of an angle θ_W , known as Weinberg angle, that is defined as $\tan \theta_W = g_1/g_2$. The definitions $g_Z = \sqrt{g_1^2 + g_2^2}$ and $e = g_1 g_2 / g_Z$ will simplify the following equations.

The second step is the electroweak symmetry breaking, which is related to the potential in equation (2.21). The shape of the potential is dictated by the pre-factors $\mu^2 < 0$ and $\lambda > 0$. They cause the minimum of the potential to lie at $\phi_1^2 + \phi_2^2 + \phi_3^2 + \phi_4^2 = \sqrt{-\mu^2/\lambda} = v$. One minimum is chosen explicitly by setting $\phi_1 = \phi_2 = \phi_4 = 0$, but the choice is arbitrary and can be changed by applying a gauge transformation. Excitations away from the minimum, however, are parametrized explicitly with a scalar field H . Then ϕ is written as

$$\phi = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ v + H \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.24)$$

so that the related Lagrangian density reads

$$\mathcal{L}_\phi = \frac{g_2^2 v^2}{4} W^{+\mu} W_\mu^- \left(1 + \frac{H}{v}\right)^2 + \frac{g_Z^2 v^2}{8} Z^\mu Z_\mu \left(1 + \frac{H}{v}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2} (\partial_\mu H)^2 - V(\phi). \quad (2.25)$$

The expansion around the minimum gives rise to terms that can be interpreted as masses by comparison to equation (2.4), specifically $M_W = g_2 v / 2$ and $M_Z = g_Z v / 2 = M_W / \cos \theta_W$. The precise choice of the mixing between the fields W_3^μ and B^μ in equations (2.23) eliminates mixed terms with A^μ and Z^μ and causes the photon field to be massless. This method of generating mass terms in the Lagrangian is called BEH-mechanism after the authors of Refs. [14, 15].

When inspecting equation (2.25), the scalar field H has a kinetic energy term, interactions with the W^\pm and Z fields and even an associated mass that hides in the potential

$$-V(\phi) = +\frac{\mu^4}{4\lambda} + \mu^2 H^2 - \lambda v H^3 - \frac{\lambda}{4} H^4 \quad (2.26)$$

as $M_H = \sqrt{-2\mu^2/\lambda} = \sqrt{2\lambda} v$. The field H is therefore interpreted as the physical Higgs boson. It also exhibits self-interactions corresponding to the cubic and quartic terms in the potential.

The Yukawa part of the Lagrangian in equation (2.22) is written such that the electroweak symmetry breaking lets combinations of fermions with different type disappear. The matrices Γ are non-diagonal, which allows mass eigenstates of fermions f to be different from their weak interaction eigenstates f^0 , which are written with an explicit superscript 0. After

diagonalizing the matrices Γ , the equation simplifies to

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{Yuk}} = \sum_{n=1}^3 \sum_f -\bar{f}_n m_{f_n} \left(1 + \frac{H}{v}\right) f_n, \quad (2.27)$$

where the first sum iterates over the three generations and the variable f sums over all fermion types. This form of the equation exhibits fermion masses m_f . It shows that the strength of the interaction between the Higgs boson and a fermion is proportional to the fermion mass. This is in contrast to equation (2.25), that shows a quadratic mass dependence when the Higgs boson interacts with a boson.

The fact that the mass eigenstates of the physical fermions are different from the eigenstates of the weak interaction also affects the fermion part of the Lagrangian in equation (2.14). When rewriting it for the physical quarks, it allows quarks to interact across different particle generations. By convention, this is expressed as the CKM mixing matrix [16, 17]

$$\begin{pmatrix} d^0 \\ s^0 \\ b^0 \end{pmatrix} = V_{\text{CKM}} \begin{pmatrix} d \\ s \\ b \end{pmatrix}, \quad (2.28)$$

which relates the down, strange and bottom quarks to their weak interaction eigenstates.

Lastly, the fermion Lagrangian can be written after electroweak symmetry breaking as

$$\mathcal{L}_f = + \sum_f \bar{f}^0 i \gamma^\mu \partial_\mu f^0 \quad (2.29)$$

$$- \frac{g_2}{\sqrt{2}} (W_\mu^+ \gamma^\mu (\bar{\nu}_L^0 e_L^0 + \bar{u}_L^0 d_L^0) + W_\mu^- \gamma^\mu (\bar{e}_L^0 \nu_L^0 + \bar{d}_L^0 u_L^0)) \quad (2.30)$$

$$- \frac{g_Z}{2} \sum_f Z_\mu \gamma^\mu (\bar{f}_L^0 T^3 f_L^0 - \bar{f}^0 2Q \sin \theta_W f^0) \quad (2.31)$$

$$- e \sum_f \bar{f}^0 A_\mu \gamma^\mu Q f^0. \quad (2.32)$$

The kinetic term in the first row is unchanged with respect to equation (2.14). The second row contains the weak, charged interaction between left-chiral fermions or right-chiral anti-fermions in the same doublet. The coupling to specific chirality eigenstates violates both parity P and charge conjugation C symmetry [18]. If the weak eigenstates of quarks are substituted by their mass eigenstates, the elements of the CKM matrix appear to mix quarks of different generations. The violation of CP symmetry in the weak interaction [19] is described by complex phases in the CKM matrix. The third row shows the weak interaction mediated by the neutral Z boson. Its first term only involves left-chiral fermions like the charged current and the second term couples to all fermions. Thus, the combined interaction also violates the P and C symmetries. The last row shows the electromagnetic interaction

that couples to all fermions and violates neither the P nor C symmetries. The variable $e = g_1 g_2 / g_Z$ can be identified as the electric charge of the positron.

2.1.5 Limitations of the Standard Model

For over four decades, the Standard Model of particle physics has successfully described and predicted many experimental results including new particles and their properties. The generality of the derivation, namely the use of a Lagrangian density that is required to be invariant under certain local gauge transformations, is compelling. But there are good reasons to believe that the Standard Model is not the full theory.

One would expect from a fundamental theory that the number of free parameters is fairly small. The Standard Model has at least⁴ 18 parameters: the masses of the nine massive fermions, three coupling strengths g_1 , g_2 , g_3 , two parameters defining the Higgs potential and four parameters in the CKM matrix. Particularly the fermion masses are puzzling, because they all seem to be independent and span a wide range.

Even though all interactions are derived with the local-gauge-invariance argument, there are effects that are special to particular interactions and do not have a fundamental explanation, for instance the chirality-dependence of the weak interaction. It is also surprising that the electromagnetic and weak interactions are unified, while QCD can be treated as an independent part of the theory. Also the role of gravity, which is not part of the Standard Model, is unknown. Related to gravity is the observation of different gravitational effects in astronomical data which can be explained with a new form of matter, called dark matter because it does not seem to interact electromagnetically.

The violation of CP symmetry is explicitly parametrized in the CKM matrix. Other possible occurrences are in the equivalent matrix for leptons, that is called PMNS matrix and can be introduced to extend the Standard Model by neutrino masses. It is also conceivable that QCD violates CP symmetry through an additional term in the Lagrangian, but there is no evidence for such violation (strong CP problem). A possible solution to this fine-tuning is the Peccei-Quinn mechanism that introduces an additional symmetry for QCD. The symmetry is spontaneously broken, eliminates the CP violation and leaves an axion behind, a new particle for which no experimental evidence has been found. The reason to search for sources CP violation is that today's universe consists of matter, not anti-matter. With the currently known CP violating processes, this asymmetry cannot be explained.

The fact that the Higgs boson has spin 0 exposes it to quantum corrections differently from fermions and spin-1 gauge bosons. These corrections become important if the Standard Model is embedded into a larger theory, for example one that also describes gravity. The natural energy scales for such a theory would be much higher than the Higgs boson mass. But if

⁴The parameters with a (near-)zero value, the pre-factor of a CP -violating term in QCD and the neutrino masses, are not included here. Also the number of fermion generations, which seems arbitrary in the Standard Model is not counted.

Figure 2.3: Feynman diagrams of leading order Higgs boson production. They show the processes (a) ggF , (b) VBF , (c) VH and (d) $t\bar{t}H$.

quantum corrections affect the Higgs mass, it is surprising that the Higgs mass is not of the same order of magnitude as these new energy scales. While this does not necessarily constitute a problem for the mathematical description, this mismatch of energy scales seems unnatural.

2.2 The Higgs Boson at the LHC

This section follows the summary of Higgs boson physics in Ref. [7]. This reference also contains useful additional information and references, for example about the following cross section calculations.

2.2.1 Production

At the LHC with its proton-proton collisions, there are four major mechanisms through which Higgs bosons can be produced. Figure 2.3 summarizes the lowest-order Feynman diagrams and gives an idea about their detector signature. Apart from these leading-order (LO) contributions, often also higher-order corrections are considered. With an increasing number of additional interaction vertices, the contributions are called next-to-leading order (NLO), next-to-next-to-leading (NNLO), followed by N3LO. In Figure 2.4, the cross section of a selection of Higgs boson production modes is shown as a function of the centre-of-mass energy. The cross-section values are taken from [20] and are quoted for Higgs bosons with a mass of 125 GeV produced at a centre-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV.

Figure 2.4: Cross section of different Higgs production mechanisms as a function of the centre-of-mass energy in proton-proton collisions [20].

Starting with the process with the largest cross section, gluon fusion (ggF) is initiated by the massless gluons, which need a quark-loop to couple indirectly to the Higgs boson. The top quark contributes the most to this process because of its high mass. In the approximation of an infinitely large top-quark mass, the cross section can be calculated at N3LO. The best theoretical result is achieved after rescaling this result by the ratio of two cross section calculations at LO, one with finite, the other one with infinite top-quark mass. With this, the cross section is calculated to be [20]

$$\sigma_{ggF} = 48.6 \text{ pb} \begin{matrix} +4.6\% \\ -6.7\% \end{matrix} (\text{theory}) \pm 3.2\% (\text{PDF} + \alpha_s). \quad (2.33)$$

The vector-boson fusion process (VBF) has the next-highest production cross section. It is initiated by two quarks from the protons radiating massive vector bosons, which fuse together to produce a Higgs boson. Because the initial-state quarks merely radiate vector bosons, they tend to keep much of their longitudinal momentum while acquiring additional transverse momentum. These kinematic properties create forward jets close to the beamline, a characteristic signature of VBF -induced events. Because the only particles with colour charge are the forward quarks, the central region of the detector is typically depleted of jets. The cross section [20] has been calculated in the deep-inelastic-scattering approximation at NNLO in QCD to which electroweak corrections at NLO are applied. To this result, a photon-induced component is added. VBF diagrams with a vector boson, that is created by the annihilation of two other particles (s -channel), are not included. Following this approach,

the total cross section is

$$\sigma_{\text{VBF}} = 3.78 \text{ pb } \begin{matrix} +0.43\% \\ -0.33\% \end{matrix} (\text{scale}) \pm 2.1\% (\text{PDF} + \alpha_s) \pm 1.5\% (\text{EW}). \quad (2.34)$$

The other major relevant production modes at the LHC are the associated production mechanisms VH , where the letter V identifies either a W^\pm or a Z boson, and $t\bar{t}H$, where a top-quark pair is produced in association with a Higgs boson. Both processes are less relevant in the context of this thesis because of their distinctive signatures. For completeness, their cross sections are also given here [20].

$$\sigma_{\text{WH}} = 1.37 \text{ pb } \begin{matrix} +2.0\% \\ -2.1\% \end{matrix} \quad (2.35)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{ZH}} = 0.88 \text{ pb } \begin{matrix} +4.1\% \\ -3.5\% \end{matrix} \quad (2.36)$$

$$\sigma_{\text{t}\bar{\text{t}}\text{H}} = 0.50 \text{ pb } \begin{matrix} +6.9\% \\ -9.9\% \end{matrix} \quad (2.37)$$

Two processes that are particularly interesting from a theoretical perspective are the production of tH , because the value of the cross section is sensitive to the sign of the top-quark Yukawa coupling, and the di-Higgs production, because it is sensitive to the parameter λ in the Higgs boson potential. An experimental measurement of these two processes, however, is out of reach with the currently available data [21–23].

It is common for analyses to be overwhelmed by background processes that occur more frequently than the signal process. For a comparison with the Higgs boson cross sections, Figure 2.5 shows the measured cross sections for various processes in proton-proton collisions. A big part of the challenge when extracting information about the Higgs boson is to find good selection criteria that are efficient in selecting Higgs boson processes, but reject backgrounds.

2.2.2 Decay Channels

The Higgs boson decays into a wide range of particles allowing to probe it through various experimental signatures. The Higgs coupling to fermions is proportional to the square of the fermion mass and the coupling to quarks has a relative factor of 3 with respect to leptons taking into account different colour configurations. Thus, the Higgs boson decay into a $b\bar{b}$ pair is the most frequent with a branching fraction of $BR(H \rightarrow b\bar{b}) = 58.2\%$ followed by $BR(H \rightarrow \tau^+\tau^-) = 6.27\%$. Both cases are experimentally difficult to detect given large jet backgrounds at the LHC. The Higgs decay to other fermions are $BR(H \rightarrow c\bar{c}) = 2.89\%$ and $BR(H \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-) = 0.0218\%$. All branching fractions are taken from [20]. The relative uncertainty for most processes is below 2%.

The Higgs boson also couples to massive vector bosons W^\pm and Z . Even though the coupling strength to Z bosons is higher, the decay into a pair of W^\pm is more probable. The reason is that the invariant mass of the Z -boson pair exceeds the Higgs boson mass

Standard Model Production Cross Section Measurements

Status: July 2021

Figure 2.5: Measurements by the ATLAS experiment of the cross section of various processes in the Standard Model and the corresponding theory expectations [24]. Compare the columns H and Hjj to the most relevant background processes Z , $t\bar{t}$ and VV , specifically the entries involving two W bosons if applicable.

by 20 GeV more than the mass of the W -boson pair does. The branching fractions are $BR(H \rightarrow W^+W^-) = 21.4\%$ and $BR(H \rightarrow ZZ) = 2.62\%$. The decay into two Z bosons allows one to probe the clean experimental signature of four final-state leptons, while the fully leptonic decay of the W -boson pair produces at least two neutrinos. Enabled by a loop of W bosons or quarks, the Higgs boson can also produce a final state of two photons with a branching fraction of $BR(H \rightarrow \gamma\gamma) = 0.227\%$ or a final state with two gluons $BR(H \rightarrow gg) = 8.19\%$.

Figure 2.6 summarizes the branching ratios. It also splits the decay into two W bosons, which is relevant for the HWW analysis, further according to the final-state signature. Because the mass of the two W bosons exceeds the Higgs mass, one of the virtual particles has to be off-shell. Out of the two possible combinations $H^* \rightarrow WW$ and $H \rightarrow WW^*$, where the asterisk indicates that a particle is off-shell, the latter one occurs more often. This is also the component that will be investigated in this thesis.

Figure 2.6: Branching ratios of the Higgs boson. In the case of gg and $\gamma\gamma$, the Higgs boson decays via a loop of top or W bosons. The category “others” contains the processes $\mu^+\mu^-$ and $Z\gamma$. The decay into W bosons is split up more finely according to the final-state fermions. The letter ℓ refers to a charged lepton of any flavour.

2.2.3 Experimental Status

The discovery of the Higgs boson in 2012 by the ATLAS and CMS experiments [1, 2] with a mass of $m_H \approx 125$ GeV shifted the experimental focus. After the mass-agnostic searches at the LHC and previous colliders, experiments started to analyze the Higgs boson properties and production rates. Some notable results are summarized here with a focus on results including the HWW process. The latest analyses by ATLAS and CMS are referenced, sometimes also older ones that include more details about the specific measurement.

In order to measure the mass of the Higgs boson precisely, it is crucial to reconstruct all final-state particles so that their invariant mass can be determined. Therefore, decay into four leptons via a pair of Z bosons and the decay into two photons offer the highest precision, despite their small branching ratio. The combination of ATLAS and CMS measurements with Run 1 data gives a value of $m_H = (125.09 \pm 0.24)$ GeV [25]. The measurements taken during Run 2 have not yet been combined, but confirm mass values around $m_H \approx 125$ GeV [26–28].

There are various ways to measure the width of the Higgs boson, which is $\Gamma_H = 4.1$ MeV according to the Standard Model prediction for a Higgs boson with a mass of 125 GeV. The width of the mass distribution in reconstructed Higgs candidates is limited by the detector resolution and only upper limits have been measured [29, 30]. A lower limit, on the other hand, is quoted by CMS after measuring the displacement between the interaction point and the vertex of a four-lepton final state [31].

Another approach to measuring the width of the Higgs boson is to compare the production rates of on-shell and off-shell Higgs bosons [32, 33]. In the first case, the production rate depends on the decay width, in the latter it does not. Assuming that the couplings are the same at both energy scales, the ratio of the two production rates is sensitive to the

Figure 2.7: Decay of a Higgs boson into two W bosons in the restframe of the Higgs boson with a specific spin configuration [41]. The direction of motion is indicated by plain arrows, the spin projection along the direction of motion is indicated by double arrows. For simplicity, the leptons of different W -boson decays are assumed to decay exactly into the same direction. A more elaborate sketch with all variable angles can be found in Refs. [40, 42].

decay width. Due to negative interference of the off-shell Higgs boson signal and the continuum VV production, the off-shell Higgs production effectively reduces the expected event yield [34]. These measurements in the decay to $ZZ^{(*)}$ and $WW^{(*)}$ currently give the most precise upper constraints on the decay width [35–37] and even allow a measurement of $\Gamma_H = 3.2^{+2.8}_{-2.2}$ MeV [38].

In the Standard Model, the Higgs boson has spin J , parity P and charge conjugation C eigenvalues of $J^{PC} = 0^{++}$. These three properties affect the kinematics of the Higgs boson decay and are therefore sometimes measured simultaneously. In the decay to $\gamma\gamma$, the angle between the two photons and their transverse momentum is sensitive to the Higgs boson spin. The measurements of ATLAS and CMS agree well with the hypothesis of spin-0 and positive parity [39, 40]. Similar conclusions are drawn from analyses with a Higgs decay into ZZ [39, 40]. The variables sensitive to the Higgs boson properties are the mass of the Z bosons and various production and decay angles.

Also the $H \rightarrow WW^*$ decay is sensitive to the spin of the Higgs boson. The kinematics of the leptons can qualitatively be understood due to the parity violation of the weak charged current. Consider first the leptonic decay of a W^- boson with spin a spin projection of 1 along a spin quantization axis. The weak boson decays into a left-chiral charged lepton and a right-chiral anti-neutrino. Because the neutrino is massless, its helicity, the spin projection onto its direction of motion, is equal to its chirality. Thus, the neutrino is right-handed. In order for spin to be conserved in the decay, the neutrino is preferably emitted in the polarization direction of the W^- boson and the charged lepton in the opposite direction. Following the same argument, the charged anti-lepton in a W^+ -boson decay travels preferably in the direction of the W^+ -boson polarization, the neutrino in the opposite direction.

When considering the decay $H \rightarrow WW^*$, the W bosons only carry a small momentum in the restframe of the Higgs boson. The reason is that the masses of the W bosons approximately add up to the mass of the Higgs boson with at least one of the bosons

being off-shell. Hence, only little energy is available to boost the W bosons. Therefore, the argument from above applies directly in the Higgs-boson restframe and no boost needs to be taken into account.

The Higgs boson has a spin of 0. When it decays into two spin-1 W bosons, their spin projections can be $(+1, -1)$, $(0, 0)$, $(-1, +1)$. One of the two cases with transverse polarization is shown in Figure 2.7. In both of the cases, the W bosons have opposite spin orientation. Using the conclusion from above about the W -boson decay, the two charged leptons are preferably emitted in the same direction and also the neutrinos tend to travel in the same direction⁵. This is a characteristic signature of a spin-0 Higgs boson that is confirmed experimentally [39, 40, 44]. If, conversely, the Higgs boson had spin 2, the same reasoning would predict anti-aligned leptons⁶. The third possible case, where both W bosons are longitudinally polarized corresponding to a spin projection of 0, has no preferential direction and therefore blurs this effect.

The CP properties of the Higgs boson and anomalous couplings between the Higgs and vector bosons are tested in $H \rightarrow ZZ$ analyses [38, 45]. Also the decay to $\tau\tau$ offers sensitivity to anomalous vector-boson couplings in the VBF production mode [46, 47]. The $t\bar{t}H$ production mode with the Higgs boson decaying into two photons allows to measure the CP properties of the top Yukawa coupling [48, 49]. In all cases, the results are compatible with the Standard Model.

In ggF -initiated events with a Higgs-boson decay into two W bosons and two additional jets created in the ggF production mechanism, the CP properties of the top Yukawa coupling can be probed. The process is sensitive to loop effects induced by particles beyond the Standard Model. Potential deviations from the expectation can be measured in the kinematics of the two additional jets, especially the angle between both jets. In a similar way, the angular dependence of the jets in VBF -initiated events carries information about the polarization states of the Higgs boson. In both production modes, results compatible with the Standard Model are reported [50].

Apart from looking for specific properties or models, ATLAS and CMS also perform cross section measurements in different Higgs production and decay modes. The motivation is that any disagreement with the Standard Model can give hints towards new physics. An overview of the recent results is given in combination publications by the experiments [51–54]. Figure 2.8 visually displays the result of such a combination by ATLAS. The HWW analysis that entered this combination is Ref. [55], the predecessor of the analysis that is discussed in detail in chapter 7.

⁵This reasoning about the polarization gives a nice explanation for the small opening angle between the leptons. However, Ref. [43] shows that the interference between the configurations with longitudinal and transverse polarization is the main reason for this signature.

⁶In any other than the spin-0 case, a full treatment would additionally require to consider the spin states of the initial-state particles.

Figure 2.8: Combination of cross section measurements [51]. The solid lines show contours at 68 % confidence level after a likelihood fit as a function of ggF and VBF -initiated cross sections. The combination of the individual decay channels is shown in black with a dashed line indicating the 95 % confidence level. All contours can be compared to the values predicted by theory shown in the pink, filled ellipsis.

The concept of Simplified Template Cross Sections (STXS) [20, 56, 57] was developed in an effort to make the cross-section measurements more generic and to facilitate combinations of analyses with different Higgs decay channels. The STXS framework describes a standardized scheme of splitting the Higgs signal into different fiducial categories. These categories are chosen according to the production mechanism and related kinematic variables, such as the number of jets N_j , the transverse momentum of the Higgs boson $p_{T,H}$, the transverse momentum of the Higgs boson including the two leading jets $p_{T,Hjj}$ and the invariant mass of the two leading jets m_{jj} .

An STXS analysis measures the cross sections of all categories in parallel. The categorization allows to extract with a high granularity the kinematic properties related to the Higgs-boson production. Since the categorization is standardized and only uses variables related to the production mechanism, it is straightforward to combine measurements from different decay channels. The combination is also facilitated by the fact that the measurement is not interpreted up to this point. The only inherent model dependence comes from using the interactions of the Standard Model to produce a kinematic template of the Higgs boson.

The specific definition of the fiducial categories is based on multiple principles. Firstly, the categories are chosen to reduce the influence of theory uncertainties on the measurement. For instance, the number of jets in an event depends on scale uncertainties. By categorizing the signal process in fiducial regions according to the number of jets, the effect of the scale uncertainty is exposed in the category definition. In this way, the scale uncertainty affects the measurement of category cross sections less. Instead, the scale uncertainty becomes relevant when interpreting the STXS result. This has the advantage that the scale uncertainty can be

treated consistently between different measurements and allows for easier reinterpretation. Secondly, phase space regions are combined when they have a similar uncertainty composition. Thirdly, the category boundaries are guided by typical selection criteria in experiments and the granularity by the experimental sensitivity. Because the experimental sensitivity depends on the amount of available data, the category definitions are updated in stages. Lastly, effects from hypothetical signatures beyond the Standard Model are isolated into specific categories.

Once the cross-section measurements are finalized, they can be interpreted in a next step. An example for a straightforward interpretation is the signal strength, which is defined as the ratio of the measured and the expected cross section. A similar idea is also used by the more elaborate interpretation in the κ framework [58]. A free parameter at each vertex type allows to analyze separately the production and decay. To make full use of differential measurements, an interpretation as an effective field theory (EFT) [20] has become the new standard. In this approach, the Lagrangian density of the Standard Model is extended by higher-dimensional operators in order to parametrize the effects of new physics at high energies. In a statistical analysis, each operator is constrained by the data through a prefactor. The interpretation as generic operators again facilitates combinations of different measurements. An EFT interpretation of a Higgs combination of STXS measurements can be found in Ref. [59].

2.2.4 Cross Section Measurements of HWW

Historically, additional credibility was given to the theory of the Higgs boson after it was noticed that its coupling to the W bosons resolves a theoretical problem associated with WW scattering. When considering the contact interaction of four W bosons, where all four bosons are longitudinally polarized, the transition amplitude diverges as a function of transferred energy. This violates the unitarity principle above energies of 1.2 TeV [60]. The existence of the Higgs boson, and its coupling to W bosons resolve this unphysical situation, because it introduces a similar process with an s -channel exchange of the Higgs boson [61]. This process has a term in its amplitude that cancels with the diverging WW -scattering term. However, if the strength of the HWW interaction deviates from the predicted value, unitarity would not be ensured and the need for new physics would arise. This is a strong motivation for the measurement of the HWW coupling, because any deviation from the Standard Model would have extensive ramifications.

Independently of the theoretical motivation, the HWW process is also very suitable for a measurement of the couplings between the Higgs and vector bosons. In the VBF production mode, this coupling is exposed twice, once at the production and once at the decay vertex. This double dependence makes the couplings measurement particularly sensitive. Due to the larger event yield, this measurement promises smaller statistical uncertainties than the corresponding HZZ measurement [62].

The cross-section measurement is discussed in detail in chapter 7 of this thesis. It has the goal to measure the cross section of the ggF and VBF production modes of the Higgs boson and subsequent decay into two W bosons. It builds on previous ATLAS analyses that used smaller datasets for the same purpose. In the data from the LHC Run 1 with an integrated luminosity of 25/fb, the HWW process was observed for the first time with a significance⁷ of 6.1σ observed (5.8σ expected) [41] and evidence for the VBF production mode was found with a significance of 3.2σ (2.7σ). With the data of the first two years of Run 2 corresponding to 36/fb, the HWW measurement in the ggF production mode passed the threshold for observation with 6.0σ (5.3σ) [55]. The signal strength in the VBF production mode was measured to be $0.62_{-0.35}^{+0.36}$ and is dominated by statistical uncertainties. The deviation of the signal strength from 1 can be explained as a fluctuation of the data.

The CMS experiment published a similar set of measurements in the HWW channel. The Run 1 publication found evidence for the process [63] and the first measurement in Run 2 combined the four major production modes for observation with a significance of 9.1σ (7.1σ) [64]. With the full dataset collected during Run 2, a fiducial cross-section measurement was published that was consistent with the Standard Model [65].

⁷Statistical significance quantifies the compatibility of a measurement with the background-only hypothesis. Conventionally, significances higher than 5σ are considered an observation and significances higher than 3σ evidence for a phenomenon.

Chapter 3

Experimental Setup

3.1 Large Hadron Collider

The Large Hadron Collider (LHC) [66–69] was built to create high-energetic proton-proton collisions. It receives protons from an upstream accelerator, stores them, accelerates them further, and collides the high-energetic protons in different experimental setups. The LHC is housed in a 26.7 km long tunnel that is located at a depth of approximately 100 m below the CERN laboratory¹ and the surrounding region. It has two vacuum beam pipes that hold beams of protons. The protons in different beam pipes travel in opposite direction on a near-circular path along eight arcs that are interlaced with eight straight segments.

The protons are forced on the arc trajectory by a total of 1232 dipole magnets. These magnets consist of copper and a Nb-Ti alloy that is superconducting at the operating temperature of 1.9 K. At currents of up to 12 kA, the dipole magnets produce magnetic fields of 8.3 T. Higher-order multipole magnets focus the protons and correct the beam trajectory.

The LHC receives protons only after they have passed a series of pre-accelerators. Starting with hydrogen gas, electrons are removed and the remaining protons accelerated in the Linear accelerator 2. After the Proton Synchrotron Booster, the protons are filled into the Proton Synchrotron and later into the Super Proton Synchrotron. While passing this chain of accelerators, the protons are combined into bunches with a spacing of 25 ns containing roughly $1.1 \cdot 10^{11}$ protons each [70]. After reaching an energy of 450 GeV, the protons are filled into the LHC, where they are further accelerated to 6.5 TeV. This acceleration takes place separately for both beams in one of the straight segments by superconducting radio-frequency cavities. Thus, a centre-of-mass energy of 13 TeV per colliding proton pair is reached in symmetric collisions.

Other straight segments at the LHC provide space for operational structures, like the beam dump, where the proton beams can be deposited at the end of a run or in case of a

¹The acronym CERN derives from the French “Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire”. The organization, however, is called “Organisation Européenne pour la Recherche Nucléaire”, European Organization for Nuclear Research.

Figure 3.1: Schematic view of the LHC and its pre-accelerators [71]. Starting at the proton source and radio-frequency quadrupole (RFQ), the chain continues via the Linear accelerator 2 (LINAC2), Proton Synchrotron Booster (PSB), Proton Synchrotron (PS) and the Super Proton Synchrotron (SPS) to the Large Hadron Collider (LHC). The location of the four experiments is indicated in the straight sections at point 1, 2, 5 and 8.

malfunction. Four out of the eight straight segments are occupied by the main experiments as displayed in Figure 3.1. They are built around the interaction points, where the proton beams collide. LHCb is specialized for b -hadron physics and ALICE has a focus on collisions of lead-ions, which the LHC is also able to accelerate. Both ATLAS and CMS are general-purpose detectors designed to reconstruct tracks from interactions with high instantaneous luminosity.

The instantaneous luminosity [7]

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{f_{\text{coll}} n_1 n_2}{4\pi\sigma_x\sigma_y} \mathcal{F} \quad (3.1)$$

is purely determined by the parameters of the beams at an interaction point, the frequency of collisions f_{coll} , the number of protons in each bunch n_1, n_2 and the widths of the Gaussian profiles of the proton bunches σ_x, σ_y . The variable $\mathcal{F} \approx 1$ parametrizes higher-order effects. Then, a process with the cross section σ is expected to occur

$$N = \sigma \int \mathcal{L} dt \quad (3.2)$$

times. During the entire Run 2, particle collisions during stable beams were recorded at ATLAS corresponding to an integrated luminosity of 139/fb [73]. The integrated luminosity as a function of time is shown in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: Integrated luminosity recorded during Run 2 by the ATLAS experiment [72]. The blue area corresponds to the proton-proton collisions recorded during stable beams that are used for general physics analyses.

Figure 3.3: Mean number of inelastic interactions per bunch crossing split up according to data-taking year [72]. The distribution is calculated based on the measured instantaneous luminosity and the cross section for inelastic interactions $\sigma_{\text{inel}} = 80 \text{ mb}$ at 13 TeV.

With higher instantaneous luminosities, the number of inelastic interactions per bunch crossing increases. In addition to the hard interaction, characterized by the highest momentum transfer, other proton-proton pairs collide and produce particles. The jets originating from these additional interactions are called pile-up jets [74]. They typically occur in the forward region of the detector and imitate the signature of *VBF*-initiated events. Figure 3.3 shows the mean number of interactions per bunch crossing in the Run 2 dataset.

3.2 The ATLAS Experiment

The design of the ATLAS experiment [75–77] was guided by the goal to perform precision measurements of known particles and processes as well as searches for new particles. Some of the precision measurements were intended for the *W* boson mass, gauge boson couplings and *CP* violation. Also the mass and the interactions of the top quark played a major role, which clearly manifests itself in calling the LHC a “top-quark factory” [78]. Concerning searches for new particles, various models were considered, eg. supersymmetric models and heavy gauge bosons. The main motivation, however, were searches for the Higgs boson. Since the Higgs boson mass was unknown at the time and therefore also the relevance of the various decay channels, a major aim was to build a detector that is sensitive to Higgs boson decays independently of the mass.

These physics objectives lead to the main requirements of the experiment. Reconstruction of all particle tracks is essential with a precise momentum measurement, particularly for leptons which are part of many final-state signatures, but also for hadrons. High-precision tracking allows to measure the displacement of secondary vertices, which is crucial to identify τ leptons and jets initiated by a *b* quark. A large coverage angle of the detector ensures a high acceptance and makes measurements of missing transverse momentum possible. In order to be sensitive to signatures with small lepton momenta, like the $H \rightarrow WW^*$ decay, event triggering on low- p_T objects is important. At the same time, the detector material needs to withstand a large amount of radiation that is released in the proton-proton collisions.

These considerations result in a cylindrical design of the experiment, with the cylinder axis oriented along the beamline. This is also reflected in the ATLAS coordinate system, which uses the azimuthal angle ϕ to parametrize the angle around the beam axis. The radius r specifies the perpendicular distance from the axis and z the position along the beam axis with the origin in the centre of the detector. An alternative parametrization uses the polar angle θ to define the angle from the z axis. The trajectory of particles originating from the origin is typically measured in the azimuthal angle ϕ and pseudorapidity $\eta = -\ln \tan(\theta/2)$. The pseudorapidity is an approximation of rapidity $y = 1/2 \ln((E + p_z)/(E - p_z))$ for massless particles with the particle energy E and longitudinal momentum p_z . As a distance measure between two points i and j in the detector, the quantity $\Delta R = (\eta_i - \eta_j)^2 + (\phi_i - \phi_j)^2$ is often used.

Figure 3.4: The ATLAS detector with labeled subsystems [77].

Figure 3.4 gives an overview of the detector, whose main components are arranged in a cylindrical shape with a barrel and two end-cap sections. Closest to the centre, the Inner Detector measures trace points of the charged particles traversing it, which is crucial for the reconstruction of particle trajectories, called tracking. A calorimeter is placed around the ID. It performs a destructive measurement of the particle energy. On the outside, muon chambers measure the trajectory of muons that are able to pass through the calorimeter. The entire apparatus is immersed in a magnetic field that bends the particle tracks and allows to measure momentum based on the deflection. The magnetic field is provided by the solenoid and toroid magnets.

The following sections give a more detailed overview of the detector subsystems. Their description is mainly taken from the summary in Ref. [77]. The technical design reports of the subsystems are cited for further reference.

3.2.1 Inner Detector

To achieve the goal of particle tracking, the Inner Detector (ID) [79, 80] contains three independent subdetectors. The pixel detector and SemiConductor Tracker (SCT) are based on silicon and detect ionizing particles as they penetrate the material. On the outside, the Transition Radiation Tracker (TRT) is a gas detector that detects charges produced from ionization. All three detectors follow the cylindrical design of the ATLAS detector. They consist of barrel layers that are perpendicular to r at low pseudorapidities and end-caps perpendicular to the z -coordinate at larger pseudorapidities.

The pixel detector has four barrel and three end-cap layers on each side. The innermost barrel layer, the insertable b-layer (IBL) [81, 82], was installed before Run 2 commenced.

It is mounted onto the beampipe to provide a track measurement as close as possible to the interaction point with an average sensor radius of 3.35 cm. The pixels have a pitch of $250\ \mu\text{m} \times 50\ \mu\text{m}$ in the z and ϕ direction. The IBL measures a track point up to $|\eta| < 3$, which complements the other three layers of the pixel detector and compensates for damaged sensors in the second layer, which is being operated beyond its expected lifetime.

The three following layers consist of barrels and end-caps. Most pixels have a pitch of $400\ \mu\text{m} \times 50\ \mu\text{m}$. In the barrels, the long pixel side is oriented along the beamline, while in the end-caps the long side extends radially. This way, a precise measurement of the angle ϕ can be performed, which is important when calculating the particle momentum. All sensors and electronics are designed to sustain reliable operation after absorbing large amounts of radiation, most important for IBL.

The SCT is placed outside of the pixel detector with a similar arrangement of the four barrel and nine end-cap layers. Each layer holds two silicon sensors that are segmented into strips of $6.4\ \text{cm} \times 80\ \mu\text{m}$. One of the two sensors has strips oriented along the beamline, the other one is rotated by 40 mrad. In combination, they obtain a resolution of $580\ \mu\text{m} \times 17\ \mu\text{m}$. In the end-caps, a similar resolution is achieved with strips that are oriented radially and have varying strip length. Also here, adjacent sensors are rotated by 40 mrad.

Both silicon detectors are designed such that a particle travelling in a direction $|\eta| < 2.5$ from the interaction point typically traverses four pixel and four SCT sensors. The penetrating particle loses energy and promotes electrons into the conduction band of the semiconductor creating electron-hole pairs along the particle trajectory. The silicon is doped such that it has a p-n junction. It is operated with a negative bias voltage of up to 600 V for the pixel detector and 300 V for the SCT, which depletes the bulk silicon of free charges and produces an electric field across the bulk silicon. The electron-hole pairs created by the passing particle move towards the electrodes and induce a signal. The signal is amplified and if it exceeds a certain threshold, the hit information is digitized and stored until it is requested by the Read-Out System.

The space-points determined by the silicon detectors are complemented by 36 hits on average in the TRT at pseudorapidities of $|\eta| < 2$. This detector is made of gas-filled straw tubes with a wire on the inside. Traversing charged particles ionize the gas and the free electrons travel to the central wire, where they leave a signal. Between the straws, polypropylene fibres are placed. Electrons are light enough to emit transition radiation when traversing the fibres due to the changing dielectric constant at the material interface. By detecting large signals from transition radiation, electrons can be identified and distinguished from pions.

The solenoid magnetic field that reaches 2 T in the centre of ATLAS permeates the ID and bends charged particles. Assuming that the particle has an electric charge of $\pm 1 e$, its momentum can be determined from the trajectory. The relative uncertainty of the momentum measurement is proportional to the momentum $\sigma_{p_T}/p_T \propto p_T$ [83]. Apart from the momentum measurement, the measured trajectories are extrapolated to reconstruct the

originating vertex. As an example, a vertex resolution in the order of $10\ \mu\text{m}$ and $200\ \mu\text{m}$ is achieved in the radial direction and along the beamline, respectively, in $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ events [84]. This precision allows to reconstruct displaced, secondary vertices of b -hadrons or τ decays.

The first upgrade to the ID was performed before Run 2, when the IBL was inserted. When after completion of Run 3 the LHC is upgraded to the High-Luminosity LHC, the ID will be replaced by the new Inner Tracker (ITk) [85, 86], that has silicon pixel and strip sensors. Contributing to the detector development, the author of this thesis studied the insulation requirements between silicon strip sensors. A self-contained report was written and can be found in the appendix A.

3.2.2 Calorimeters

While the ID is designed to interact little with the incident particle, the calorimeter design follows the opposite strategy. A large amount of material is placed around the ID to absorb the penetrating particle. In a shower of interactions, the particle transfers its energy to the detector, where the energy deposits are measured and added up for an energy estimate. For electrons with energy $E \gtrsim 10\ \text{MeV}$, the energy loss is dominated by bremsstrahlung [7]. In this case, the calorimeter depth is parametrized by the radiation length X_0 , the distance over which the electron energy reduces on average by a factor of $1/e$ [83]. Hadrons typically lose their energy over longer distances through nuclear interactions. In this case, the interaction length λ is used to quantify the distance within which a hadron first interacts. The probability of a particle penetrating a distance λ into the material without interacting is $1/e$ [87].

All calorimeters in ATLAS are cylindrical sampling calorimeters with a passive and an active component. The passive material has a high density with the intention to expedite the interaction cascade of an incident particle. Interleaved with the passive layer, an active material absorbs energy due to ionization or excitation. The amount of energy deposited in the active layer is measured to give an estimate for the particle energy. Most ATLAS calorimeters use liquid argon [88] as an active material because it is radiation-hard. Only the Tile calorimeter [89] that is exposed to less radiation uses scintillators.

The electromagnetic calorimeter uses lead as a passive absorber material. The sheets of lead are folded in an accordion-like fashion to create a geometry with full coverage in ϕ direction. In-between adjacent sheets is liquid argon, that gets ionized by the electromagnetic shower of electrons and photons. The ions travel in an electric field towards an electrode, where they induce a signal. The electromagnetic calorimeter has a barrel and an end-cap component with a transition at $1.37 < |\eta| < 1.52$ and with a radiation length of at least $22\ X_0$ and $24\ X_0$, respectively. The calorimeter covers pseudorapidities $|\eta| < 3.2$ and has a presampler layer at $|\eta| < 1.8$ with fine granularity in η to allow to correct for energy loss and to resolve close-by photons created by the decay of a neutral pion.

The end-caps of the hadronic calorimeter at $1.5 < |\eta| < 3.2$ use planar copper wedges in ϕ as an absorber. The forward calorimeter end-caps at $3.1 < |\eta| < 4.9$ also use copper in the first layer to allow for high heat conductivity due to the high particle flux, while tungsten

is used in the second and third layer. In the barrel region of the hadronic calorimeter at $|\eta| < 1.7$, steel and scintillator tiles alternate as passive and active materials, respectively. The light emitted by the scintillator is guided to and digitized at photomultiplier tubes. The interaction lengths of the hadronic and forward calorimeters range between 7λ to 10λ from the central to the forward region.

Since electrons and photons lose their energy in an electromagnetic cascade of interactions, the signal in the detector is proportional to the deposited particle energy with good precision. In hadronic showers, on the other hand, some energy is absorbed by the detector material, whose nuclear bonds break [83]. The associated 30-40 % invisible energy [90] complicate the energy scale measurement and reduce the energy resolution. In general, the stochastic noise in particle showers follows a Poisson distribution, whose characteristic width decreases as a function of the energy as $\sigma_E/E \propto 1/\sqrt{E}$ [91]. Other sources of uncertainty might scale differently, but typically the energy resolution improves at higher energies. This complements the momentum measurement from the ID, which shows opposite scaling with energy.

3.2.3 Muon Chambers

The energy loss due to bremsstrahlung is inversely proportional to the particle mass squared [83]. This implies that muons do not lose a significant energy due to bremsstrahlung. Bremsstrahlung starts to contribute to the energy loss only at energies above hundreds of GeV. Below these energies, muons move through the calorimeter with little energy loss and eventually leave the detector. In order to measure the muon momentum more precisely, a dedicated muon spectrometer forms the outermost layer of the experiment.

Outside of the calorimeter, the eight superconducting coils of the barrel toroid magnet create an average magnetic field of 0.5 T, predominantly in the ϕ direction. At higher pseudorapidities, the field is produced by end-caps, one on either side of the detector. The toroid magnet shares the space with the muon detectors [92], which extend up to $|\eta| < 2.7$ and mostly² consist of monitored drift tubes [93] (MDT). The three layers of the muon chambers contain multiple tubes each. The tubes have a diameter of 3 cm and a central wire with a positive voltage. Thus, the wire attracts electrons that are produced by ionizing muons. The time, at which a signal is first detected, depends on the smallest distance between the muon trajectory and the wire. Measuring that time allows to constrain the position of the muon trajectory to two lines. The ambiguity is resolved by comparison with other tubes. The tubes are oriented along the azimuthal direction so that the time measurement constrains the z and the r coordinate in the barrel and end-caps, respectively, with a precision of about 80 μm per tube [94]. This precision is needed to achieve the benchmark of a 10 % uncertainty on the momentum measurement of a 1 TeV muon.

²The first end-cap layer of the muon detector system is made of Cathode-Strip Chambers due to higher particle rates. These chambers function similarly to the TGCs, that are mentioned below.

The ϕ coordinate that is not constrained by the MDTs is measured in a secondary muon detector system. This system consists of resistive plate chambers (RPCs) at $|\eta| < 1.05$ and thin gap chambers (TGCs) in the forward region at $1.05 < |\eta| < 2.4$. These two detectors are designed for triggering, but also provide resolution in the 2d plane. Their measured ϕ coordinate of a muon track is complementary to the precision measurement in the MDTs. The RPCs cover the barrel region. Their active material is a 2 mm thick gas volume with planar electrodes on either sides to collect free charges. Good timing information is achieved with a signal width of 5 ns. The TGCs are multi-wire proportional chambers. They are used in the forward region, because they are better suited for high particle rates. A row of wires is strung in azimuthal direction and read-out strips extract the signal position in the orthogonal direction. The timing resolution is less than 25 ns for almost all hits.

3.2.4 Trigger System

The collision rate of 40 MHz is too large to read out and store all detector data for each collision. To reduce the amount of information, a two-stage trigger system selects events in real time. In this way, many events from processes with large cross section are rejected, but processes of particular interest are recorded³. The process of selecting and storing events is handled by the Trigger and Data Acquisition System [95].

The first level (L1) of the trigger system [96] is hardware-based. It uses information from the calorimeter and the dedicated muon detectors. With reduced granularity, clusters in the calorimeter exceeding a programmable energy level are identified. Also event-wide information, like the total transverse energy, is approximated and can be used for event selection. The muon detectors require coincidence between different detector layers to identify muon candidates. The discrepancy between the data and a straight-muon-track hypothesis is used as a selection criterion. The information from different trigger systems is combined, so that the L1 decision can be based on event-level quantities, such as the number of certain objects (eg. muons, jets) above a threshold. The decision is taken with a latency of 2.5 μ s and an output rate of up to 100 kHz. Additionally, the L1 trigger defines regions of interest (RoIs) for the next trigger stage.

After a positive L1 decision, the entire detector information is read out and buffered in the Read-Out System. It is made available to the high-level trigger (HLT) that can request parts of the event information or all of it. The HLT is based on software that is run on a dedicated computing farm. It analyzes the data starting from the RoIs and follows multiple hypothesis algorithms. A decision is reached after hundreds of milliseconds. At a rate of 1.2 kHz on average, the event data is transferred to permanent storage.

³Figure 2.5 serves as a good reminder for the vast difference of production cross section in the collisions and thus illustrates the need for a trigger system.

3.3 Event Reconstruction

After the raw data from the detector is saved to disk and tape, both at CERN and over an international computing grid, it is analyzed in multiple steps. For typical physics analyses, the basic reconstruction of hits in detector layers is performed centrally. The output contains basic, physics-motivated objects, like electrons, muons or jets. To refine the selection and achieve the necessary signal purity, further criteria on the objects are applied based on the needs of a specific analysis. These criteria are often referred to as working points. This section gives an overview of the basic reconstruction algorithms and defines the working points used in the HWW analysis. These working points are also relevant for the data-driven background estimate in chapter 6.

3.3.1 Tracking

Information from the ID is essential for the reconstruction of all particles. The trajectories of charged particles can be identified (tracking) and even for neutral particles the lack of hits in the ID provides important information. The term hit is used for a signal in a single detector layer at a specific position in space, while the term track refers to a set of hits that is grouped together by reconstruction algorithms and believed to belong together.

The process of tracking [97] starts in the silicon layers of the ID. The individual hits in close-by pixels or strips are clustered, because a passing particle often leaves a signal in more than one readout channel. Depending on the geometry of the cluster and the energy deposition, three-dimensional space points are constructed as an estimate for the intercept of the particle with the detector layer. In a next step, track seeds are identified as clusters from three space points in the SCT and basic requirements are applied. A Kalman filter [98] builds track candidates by including space points from other silicon layers.

In events with high particle multiplicities, the hits of different particles can be merged into one cluster. A neural network [99] is used to identify these merged clusters in the pixel detector. To reduce the number of clusters that are shared by multiple track candidates despite being identified as unmerged, a score is assigned to each track candidate based on the momentum, fit quality, number of hits and number of silicon layers without associated cluster. An algorithm removes clusters from track candidates with more than one shared, but unmerged cluster by giving preference to tracks with a higher score. Tracks with low scores are rejected. Afterwards, a global fit is performed to optimize the track parameters, before the tracks are extrapolated into the TRT and matched with its hits [100]. Another global fit determines the final track parameters.

The collection of tracks is used to identify primary vertices in the proton-proton collisions [101]. First, the point of closest approach to the beamspot is reconstructed for each track. The mode of this distribution in the z direction is used as a seed for the primary vertex algorithm. A numerical fit of the three-dimensional vertex position is performed. This fit is repeated multiple times and tracks that are incompatible with the current vertex estimate

get assigned a smaller weight in every iteration. After a vertex position is reconstructed, the compatible tracks are assigned to this primary vertex. Then, the entire algorithm is repeated using all unassigned tracks to find other primary vertices. This is done as long as vertices with at least two tracks are found.

Like in most other physics analyses, only tracks originating from one primary vertex are used in the HWW analysis. This vertex is chosen as the vertex with the highest quadrature sum of associated transverse track momenta.

3.3.2 Muons

Before muons are reconstructed [102], a tracking algorithm is performed using only information from the muon spectrometer. Initial track candidates are constructed with the help of a Hough transform [103] assuming that the trajectory follows a parabola. Afterwards, a first fit is performed to obtain a more precise estimate, while taking into account a potential misalignment of the detector. After including unused hits that are compatible with the fit and removing incongruous ones, the fit is repeated. With a similar quality criterion as used for tracking in the ID, low-quality track candidates are removed in favour of high-quality candidates, if they share too many hits. Lastly, it is required that the track is loosely compatible with originating from the interaction point and a final fit is performed considering potential energy loss in the calorimeter.

There are five independent algorithms to reconstruct muons. The first one matches tracks reconstructed in the ID with tracks from the muon detector. With this additional information, the hits in the muon spectrometer are reassigned and fitted again. Also tracks at large pseudorapidities are considered that lie partially outside of the ID acceptance. The second algorithm starts with tracks built in the ID and extrapolates to the muon spectrometer, where at least three hits are required. With respect to the first one, this algorithm recovers tracks with low transverse momentum or with missing hits in the muon detector. Only muons from these two algorithms are used in the HWW analysis as part of further selection criteria, because they provide the best-measured muons. Of the remaining three algorithms, the first one uses only tracks built from the muon detector, the second one combines track segments in the ID with track segments in the muon detector and the third one uses calorimeter deposits that are compatible with a minimum ionizing particle.

A set of working points [102] are defined to set requirements on the quality of the reconstructed muons. This way, muon tracks with wrongly assigned hits are suppressed as well as muons originating from semileptonic decays of hadrons (light hadrons) not containing c or b quarks. These non-prompt muons tend to have a kink in their trajectory when they decay resulting in a lower quality track. The working points are called *Loose*, *Medium* and *Tight*. The *Tight* working point contains a subset of the *Medium* muons and the *Medium* working point contains all muons in *Loose*. Tighter working points have an improved background rejection at the cost of a smaller muon efficiency. There are also two working points optimized for muon selections with very low or high transverse momentum.

In the HWW analysis, muons are required to satisfy the *Tight* quality requirements. Only the first two reconstruction algorithms mentioned above are considered. At least two precision layers of the muon detector are required to have at least three hits and the track needs to satisfy $\chi^2/N_{\text{dof}} < 8$ to the track to remove light hadron decays, where χ^2 is a goodness-of-fit measure and is divided by the number of degrees of freedom N_{dof} . Two additional variables compare the momentum reconstruction and the charge-over- p_T ratio between the measurement in the ID and the muon spectrometer. Cuts are applied as a function of η and ϕ and purify the selection of low- p_T muons. The *Tight* working point is approximately 93% efficient for muons with $p_T > 20$ GeV and only allows 0.12% hadrons in the selection. The efficiencies are taken from simulation by analyzing all reconstructed tracks in the ID and matching them to a particle type in the primary interaction.

At this point, the only significant source of unwanted muons comes from semileptonic decays of heavy-flavour hadrons that contain a c or b quark. The tracks of these unwanted muons typically have a better quality than their light-hadron counter parts, but can be identified with isolation requirements. If the muon is produced as part of a jet, any nearby (hadronic) activity can give an indication. This motivates the use of isolation working points.

The isolation variable $p_T^{\text{cone}X}$ is defined as the scalar sum of transverse momenta of all tracks within $\Delta R < 0.01 X$ around the muon track. Only tracks from the primary vertex above a transverse-momentum threshold are considered and the muon track is excluded. The variable $p_T^{\text{varcone}X}$ uses a matching criterion that depends on the muon p_T , specifically $\Delta R < \min(10 \text{ GeV}/p_{T,\mu}, 0.01 X)$. The transverse energy $E_T^{\text{cone}X}$ is similarly defined as the sum of calorimeter deposits around the muon track after subtracting the estimated background due to pile-up. While the track-based isolation has a higher resolution and is less affected by pile-up, the calorimeter-based isolation naturally takes neutral particles into account and low- p_T contributions. For the HWW analysis, the cuts $p_T^{\text{varcone}30} < 0.04 p_{T,\mu}$ and $E_T^{\text{cone}20} < 0.15 p_{T,\mu}$ were found to be suitable. For transverse momenta in the range of $20 \text{ GeV} < p_{T,\mu} < 100 \text{ GeV}$, the isolation working point has a muon efficiency of approximately⁴ 89% and a heavy-flavour efficiency of around 1% [102].

Additionally, requirements on the impact parameter of the muon track can reduce contamination from heavy-flavour decays, that often emerge slightly displaced from the primary vertex. The transverse impact parameter $|d_0|$ is defined as the shortest distance between the beamline and the muon track as depicted in Figure 3.5. The uncertainties on the muon track and the beamspot width are estimated to determine the uncertainty on the impact parameter σ_{d_0} . The longitudinal impact parameter z_0 is the z -coordinate of the track point closest to the beamline, measured from the primary vertex. Lastly, θ is the polar angle of the track at the point of closest approach. In the HWW signal selection, the cuts $|d_0|/\sigma_{d_0} < 3$ and $|z_0 \sin \theta| < 0.5 \text{ mm}$ are applied for muon tracks.

⁴These numbers were obtained from simulation after using the *Medium* quality working point, not *Tight* as in the HWW analysis. The efficiencies in both cases are expected to be similar.

Figure 3.5: Parametrization of particle tracks close to the interaction point [104]. The impact parameter d_0 , the longitudinal impact parameter z_0 and the polar track angle θ are shown.

3.3.3 Electrons

The reconstruction [105] of electrons and photons is closely intertwined. The reason is that they deposit energy via the same electromagnetic shower mechanism, but also that a sizeable fraction of photons (20% to 65% depending on the pseudorapidity [105]) converts into electron pairs while traversing the ID. This section focusses on electrons that are more relevant to the HWW analysis, but similar algorithms are also used for photon reconstruction.

The clustering of energy deposits in the electromagnetic calorimeter starts with seed cells, in which the detected signal exceeds the noise by a factor of 4. Layers of adjacent cells are added as long as the signal-to-noise ratio is greater than 2. Lastly, one additional layer of cells is added to the cluster. To reject the bulk of hadron decays, the cluster energy in the electromagnetic calorimeter is required to be at least half of the total cluster energy including the hadronic calorimeter. With the additional information from clustering, the tracks from section 3.3.1 are reanalyzed accounting for large amounts of bremsstrahlung. Also different types photon-conversion vertices are reconstructed, before the tracks and clusters are matched.

In the next step, the previously described clusters are combined to superclusters. For electrons, the process is seeded by clusters that are associated with at least four hits in silicon detector layers and an energy above 1 GeV. This seed cluster is combined with close-by clusters and with slightly farther ones if they match the same track. After rematching tracks to superclusters, a dedicated algorithm removes overlap between electron and photon candidates, which have independent supercluster algorithms. In case of doubt, both objects are kept and tagged as ambiguous. At this point, the reconstruction efficiency for electrons with $p_T > 15$ GeV is above 95%. A calibration algorithm [106] estimates the energy of the physical electron from the energy deposits in the supercluster using various shower-development variables tested in $Z \rightarrow ee$ events in data. The uncertainty of the electron energy is largest in the endcaps with at most 0.2% [105].

As for muons, a set of working points is defined to allow each physics analysis to purify the electron selection according to their needs. Many variables can be used to discriminate

electrons from light-flavour jets, heavy-flavour jets and photons [107]. Information from the calorimeter, like the shower width in different layers, mostly proves useful to reject light jets. Variables from the ID, like the number of hits in the pixel and SCT detectors, help to discriminate between electrons and photons. These variables are used as input to likelihood functions, one for electrons, one for background. The ratio of both functions forms a discriminant variable. The likelihood functions are constructed from data events. For electrons, events compatible with a $Z \rightarrow ee$ or $J/\psi \rightarrow ee$ decay are used to extract the distributions that define the likelihood. A selection of single-electron events targets dijet production and defines the background likelihood.

Based on the discriminant value, four likelihood working points are defined, *VeryLooseLH*, *LooseLH*, *MediumLH* and *TightLH*, with decreasing efficiency. Electrons in a given category automatically satisfy the requirements of any looser category. An additional working point *LooseLH-with-b-layer* is defined. It requires a hit in the b-layer, but is otherwise identical to the *LooseLH* working point. The *TightLH* working point is used for electrons below 25 GeV in transverse momentum, the *MediumLH* otherwise to define the signal selection in the HWW analysis.

Light hadrons and heavy-flavour decays are further reduced by applying an isolation working point. With the same definitions as in section 3.3.2, the HWW analysis uses $E_T^{\text{cone}20} < 0.06 p_{T,e}$ and $p_T^{\text{varcone}20} < 0.06 p_{T,e}$ to select signal electrons. At a transverse momentum of 20 GeV, the likelihood working point is around 65 % efficient and the isolation working point⁵ 75 %. The efficiency of both increase steeply as a function of $p_{T,e}$.

3.3.4 Choice of Lepton Working Points ★

Many different working points were considered for the lepton selection before choosing the ones mentioned above. In principle, the choice can be seen as an optimization problem with a trade-off between two major effects. A tighter selection reduces uncertainties from misidentified leptons, which is reflected in a smaller background contamination, specifically of fake processes, like W +jets. Conversely, a looser selection allows more events into the signal region implying a higher statistical precision. This is also advantageous for control regions and the estimate of other uncertainties.

To optimize the choice of lepton working points, the data-driven estimate of fake processes was used. Due to the different working points in each configuration, a separate set of fake factors needs to be derived and validated. This additional effort pays off, because the yield of fake processes and their uncertainties can be estimated more precisely than with simulation. Because the isolation working points have a larger influence on the analysis, they were optimized first.

⁵Like for the muon working point, the isolation efficiency here is reported with respect to the *MediumLH* likelihood.

In a first test, a figure of merit was defined in the preliminary signal regions as

$$Z = \frac{s}{\sqrt{s + b + \sigma_b^2}}, \quad (3.3)$$

where s and b stand for the estimated signal and background yields and σ_b for the systematic uncertainties on the background yield. The denominator constitutes a rough approximation for the statistical uncertainty in the data and the systematic uncertainty on the background estimate. In this form, the equation resembles the approximation for the significance [108]. With this figure of merit, a number of suitable working points were identified.

For the VBF production mode specifically, another step of optimization was performed. The statistical, experimental and preliminary fake-factor uncertainties were used as input to a statistical fit. Uncertainties from theoretical sources had not been estimated at the time and were neglected. The result of the statistical fit, a more precise estimate of the significance, was used as a figure of merit. In contrast to the first optimization step, the electron and muon working points were modified simultaneously to accurately take into account the statistical uncertainty in all configurations.

The results of the optimization process are the working points specified above. They are a compromise between the needs of the ggF and VBF analyses, that use the same working points. Also technical limitations and the availability of scale factors, which account for different selection efficiencies in data and simulation were considered. Since the decision for these working points was taken, the development of the lepton selection has advanced. This progress makes it promising to reevaluate the currently available working points for a future version of the analysis, especially for electrons, whose selection criteria have a higher impact on the final result.

After the isolation working points were chosen, also the likelihood working point for electrons was optimized. Three different configurations were tested, the *TightLH*, *MediumLH* and a combination of both, namely the *TightLH* or *MediumLH* for electrons with transverse momentum below or above 25 GeV. The split into low- and high- p_T electrons had proved useful in the previous analysis [55] and was therefore also considered here⁶. The significance of the VBF signal was estimated with a fit and only showed small variations. The worst result was obtained for the *TightLH* working point, the other two configurations were comparable.

3.3.5 Jets

After partons are created in the primary interaction, they lose some of their energy to create a shower of new particles and then hadronize. The signature of these hadrons in the detector features deposits in the calorimeter, mostly the hadronic part, often associated with multiple tracks in the ID depending on the hadron charge. All of the objects that are believed to

⁶This configuration was also used while studying the different isolation working points.

stem from the same parton are grouped together and called a *jet*. The reconstruction of jets relies on dedicated algorithms to group calorimeter clusters and tracking information.

Jet reconstruction [109] starts by clustering calorimeter deposits with a similar algorithm that is described for electrons. For certain clusters, that can be associated with high-quality tracks, the information from the tracking system can complement the energy measurement of the calorimeter. A dedicated algorithm, called particle flow [109, 110], is used to match tracks with clusters. Only high-quality tracks in non-dense environments are considered in a momentum range of 0.5 GeV to 100 GeV if they are not reconstructed as an electron or muon. They are matched by a ΔR criterion to clusters with a minimum energy requirement. It is estimated how much energy each track would deposit on average in the calorimeter. If this energy exceeds the cluster energy or if it is within the uncertainties, the track measurement is taken. Otherwise, for example in the presence of neutral hadrons, the information from the calorimeter is used after the estimated energy from charged tracks is subtracted.

The cluster and track information is used as input to the inclusive anti- k_t algorithm [111, 112] that defines the jets. For each pair of objects i, j , the distance measure

$$d_{ij} = \min(k_{ti}^{2p}, k_{tj}^{2p}) \frac{\Delta R_{ij}^2}{R^2} \quad (3.4)$$

is introduced with $p = -1$. The variable k_t describes the transverse momentum and ΔR_{ij} the distance between both objects in y - ϕ space⁷. The parameter R determines the characteristic size of the final jets and is chosen to be $R = 0.4$. The iterative procedure groups the two objects i and j with the smallest distance $\min(d_{ij})$ together. They are treated as one object from this point onward and its transverse momentum is reevaluated. If at any point $k_{ti}^{2p} < \min(d_{ij})$, the object i is declared a final jet and not used anymore in the algorithm. This is repeated until no objects are left to be combined to jets.

The jet energy is calibrated in a multi-step procedure. First, the amount of signal is corrected for contributions from pile-up, which mostly depends on the jet area and the number of primary interactions. The absolute energy calibration is taken from simulated dijet events by comparing the energy in the reconstructed jets to the energy of particle-level jets⁸. The calibration is performed as a function of pseudorapidity. Also the pseudorapidity measurement itself is corrected for a bias that occurs when a jet signal is spread over subdetectors with a different energy response. The next calibration step aims to reduce the systematic dependence of the jet energy on the flavour of the initiating quark and the energy distribution of the constituent jet particles. Multiplicative corrections are applied depending on six jet variables, such as the energy fraction in a certain calorimeter layer or number of charged tracks. In the last step of the calibration, differences between simulation and

⁷Same definition as ΔR in section 3.2, but with rapidity instead of pseudorapidity.

⁸Reconstructed jets are simulated jets that have undergone the entire simulation chain including the detector simulation. In contrast, particle-level jets are defined before the detector simulation. See section 4.2.5 for more details.

data are removed by comparing jets to well-measured reference objects. The ratio of the jet energy and the energy of the reference object is formed independently in simulation and data. The double ratio is applied to the energy response in data as final calibration step. The final uncertainty on the energy calibration is 4% for jets at $p_T = 20$ GeV and decreases as a function of p_T .

To pick jets originating from the primary vertex in an environment with many pile-up jets, a dedicated jet vertex tagger (JVT) [113] is used. The algorithm combines information from the tracker and outputs a discriminant that helps to distinguish pile-up jets from hard-scatter jets. To be considered for the HWW analysis, jets that fall in the tracker acceptance region of the detector and are between 20 GeV and 60 GeV need to be ranked higher than 0.5 by the JVT.

Jets that are initiated by c or b -quarks exhibit slightly different signatures than jets from light quarks. These signatures are used for flavour-tagging [114] in the detector region at $|\eta| < 2.5$ covered by the ID. The hadrons with heavy-flavour quarks have a sufficiently long lifetime to travel away from the primary vertex before decaying. Relativistic b -hadrons, for instance, cover a distance in the order of 0.5 mm [7]. Hence, the tracks from their decay can be associated with a displaced, secondary vertex. In a novel approach, not only the impact parameters of individual tracks, but also the correlation between them is taken into account. Also the presence of a soft muon in the jet can be an indicator for a heavy quark flavour. Dedicated variables are constructed for these three criteria and their output is combined into a boosted decision tree, that calculates a discriminating variable to identify heavy-flavour jets. In the HWW analysis, b -tagged jets are helpful to identify decays involving top quarks. A working point with a b -jet efficiency of 85% is used.

3.3.6 Missing Transverse Energy

Neutrinos are notoriously difficult to detect, because they interact neither electromagnetically nor strongly and can only be detected following a weak interaction. Therefore, they escape the experiment without leaving a direct signal behind. But the momentum imbalance in the transverse plane gives an indication that a particle escaped without interacting. This is also a common signature of physics beyond the Standard Model.

The imbalance is quantified as missing transverse energy \vec{E}_T^{miss} [115]. It is defined as the negative vector sum of the transverse momenta of all detector signals associated with the primary vertex. The detector signals are split into two main contributions, the reconstructed objects (hard term) and the unused tracks (soft term). The identified objects have the advantage that their energy is already calibrated and only overlap between them needs to be removed⁹. The soft term is reconstructed exclusively from tracks in the ID originating from the primary vertex with minimum quality criteria and not associated to any objects in the hard term. The contribution of neutral particles to the soft term is neglected, because their

⁹See explanation in section 3.3.7.

calorimeter deposits are contaminated by pile-up. This treatment provides better results than the inclusion of neutral particles using calorimeter deposits.

3.3.7 Overlap Removal

Because the different object reconstruction algorithms are independent, there is potential overlap in the results. This could mean that the same detector deposit is reconstructed as two different objects. The overlap removal (OLR) procedure is intended to resolve this inconsistency and only keep the object that is more plausible. In case two particles are reconstructed close-by from different detector deposits, OLR tries to identify which of the two particles comes from the hard interaction and which one is produced later in the event evolution. The most important measure to identify overlap is the angular distance ΔR between two objects. Three steps of OLR are most relevant for the HWW analysis.

When electrons and muons are observed in close proximity, this signature is typically caused by high-energetic photon radiation emitted by a muon. The calorimeter energy from the photon, together with the associated muon track, are incorrectly reconstructed as an electron. Hence, a reconstructed electron is removed if it shares a track with a muon.

A physical electron has a track and leaves a deposit in the calorimeter. Thus, it is often also reconstructed as a jet. On the other hand, an electron can be produced during the jet evolution, in which case the detector deposit should be identified as a jet. These two cases are distinguished by a proximity criterion. If a jet is within $\Delta R < 0.2$ of an electron and it is not b -tagged, then it is rejected in favour of the electron. If an electron is within $\Delta R < 0.4$ of any remaining jet, then the electron is removed except if the jet is identified as a pile-up jet. The explicit requirement of b -tagging poses tighter criteria for electron identification and effectively rejects events with fake electrons. The same mechanism also works for muons.

Muons and jets typically overlap, because a muon is produced during the jet formation by a heavy-flavour decay. However, a muon depositing an exceptional amount of energy can also be misidentified as a jet. To resolve this ambiguity, the same procedure is used as for electrons, but the jet removal in the vicinity of the muon requires that the jet has few tracks or a large p_T with respect to the muon.

3.3.8 Object Selection

The reconstruction of electrons, muons and jets is independent and can be performed in parallel. Afterwards, these objects are used as input to the OLR. It is sensible to apply only loose identification requirements before OLR. As an example, consider the case that a genuine muon leaves a signature in the detector and is reconstructed both as a muon and an electron. Tight identification requirements are applied and the reconstructed muon gets removed prematurely because of close-by calorimeter deposits. Then, OLR is applied and the muon is not available anymore to remove the overlapping electron that should ideally have been removed.

object type	object preselection	object selection
muons	$ \eta_\mu < 2.7$ <i>LooseLH</i>	$p_{T,\mu} > 10 \text{ GeV}$ $ \eta_\mu < 2.5$ <i>MediumLH</i> $ z_0 \sin \theta < 1.5 \text{ mm}$ $ d_0 /\sigma_{d_0} < 15$
electrons	$ \eta_e < 2.47$ <i>LooseLH</i>	$p_{T,e} > 10 \text{ GeV}$ $ \eta_e < 1.37 \text{ or } 1.52 < \eta_e < 2.47$ <i>MediumLH</i> $ z_0 \sin \theta < 0.5 \text{ mm}$ $ d_0 /\sigma_{d_0} < 5$
jets	$p_{T,j} > 20 \text{ GeV}$	$p_{T,j} > 25 \text{ GeV}$ $\eta < 4.5$ $\text{JVT} > 0.5$
<i>b</i> -jets		$p_{T,j} > 20 \text{ GeV}$ $\eta < 2.5$ $\text{JVT} > 0.5$ <i>b</i> -tagged

Table 3.1: Two steps of object selection, one before and one after OLR. The JVT criterion is only applied to *b*-jets with $|\eta_j| < 2.4$ and $20 \text{ GeV} < p_{T,j} < 60 \text{ GeV}$. Note that *b*-jets have a lower transverse-momentum requirement than jets. Hence for the purpose of the HWW analysis, *b*-jets with $p_T < 25 \text{ GeV}$ are only in the *b*-jet collection and not in the jet collection.

To address this problem, the object selection is performed in two steps. An object preselection applies a first set of requirements for all objects except jets. These objects and the tracks are used as input for the reconstruction of \vec{E}_T^{miss} . Then, the preselection requirements are applied to jets and all preselected objects undergo OLR. After this, the object selection is performed that determines which objects are considered in the analysis. At each object selection step, objects are removed in case they do not satisfy the requirements. The requirements for muons, electrons and jets are listed in Table 3.1.

Later on there will also be a third (and final) selection based on object properties. But this time entire events will be rejected if leptons do not satisfy the requirements. This final selection can vary between cases and an overview is given in Table 6.1. The column “tight” corresponds to the identification working points that were mentioned previously in the sections 3.3.2 to 3.3.5.

For some object and trigger selections, it is known that the selection efficiency is different in simulation and data. This effect is typically mitigated by measuring scale factors that account for the difference. When a certain selection is applied, the simulated event yield is weighted by the scale factor to recover the same selection efficiency as in data. The scale factors often depend on particle properties, like their kinematics.

Chapter 4

Data and Simulation

4.1 The ATLAS Dataset

The dataset analyzed in this thesis was recorded between 2015 and 2018, referred to as Run 2. It contains collisions of proton-proton bunches separated by 25 ns at a centre-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{s} = 13$ TeV. Only events are considered that pass the trigger requirements relevant for the HWW analysis. These requirements¹ are summarized in Table 4.1.

Three different lepton triggers are used in the HWW analysis and their decision is combined by a logic OR. A single-electron HLT [116] selects events with electron candidates satisfying $p_{T,e} > 26$ GeV, tight identification and loose isolation. The identification and isolation are calculated with fast algorithms giving an approximation for the more computing-intensive procedures described in section 3.3. The lower lepton rate at higher transverse momenta allows to loosen the trigger requirements. Therefore, the trigger above is complemented by electron triggers with $p_{T,e} > 60$ GeV and $p_{T,e} > 140$ GeV. These additional triggers use looser identification criteria and require no isolation. For all three energy thresholds, an electromagnetic calorimeter object is required at L1 stage, with an energy deposit of $E_T \gtrsim 22$ GeV. The exact requirement varies as a function of $|\eta|$ to account for energy loss of the particle before reaching the calorimeter. Already at this level, a loose isolation criterion is applied. The combined trigger efficiency for the L1 and HLT electron selection is between 75 % close to the trigger threshold and 95 % at high transverse momenta.

A single-muon trigger [117] with two thresholds is employed, $p_{T,\mu} > 26$ GeV and $p_{T,\mu} > 50$ GeV. The first one requires the muon to be isolated using an approximate matching of tracks to the muon vertex, the second one does not require any isolation. In both cases, an L1 trigger with $p_{T,\mu} > 20$ GeV is used as a seed. The overall efficiency increases as a function of $p_{T,\mu}$. It is approximately 10 % higher in the end-cap than in the barrel region, where the efficiency ranges between 60 % and 70 %.

¹The triggers for the data taken in 2015 differ slightly. Most notably, they have a lower p_T threshold. Since only a small part of the dataset was collected in 2015, the details are omitted here.

Lepton	L1	HLT		
	threshold	threshold	e Likelihood	Isolation
e	$E_{T,e} \gtrsim 22 \text{ GeV}$	$p_{T,e} > 26 \text{ GeV}$	<i>TightLH</i>	$p_T^{\text{cone}20} < 0.1 E_{T,e}$
		$p_{T,e} > 60 \text{ GeV}$	<i>MediumLH</i>	
		$p_{T,e} > 140 \text{ GeV}$	<i>LooseLH</i>	
μ	$p_{T,\mu} > 20 \text{ GeV}$	$p_{T,\mu} > 26 \text{ GeV}$		$p_T^{\Delta z < d} < 0.07 p_{T,\mu}$
		$p_{T,\mu} > 50 \text{ GeV}$		
$e\mu$	$E_{T,e} \gtrsim 15 \text{ GeV}$	$p_{T,e} > 17 \text{ GeV}$	<i>LooseLH</i>	
	$p_{T,\mu} > 10 \text{ GeV}$	$p_{T,\mu} > 14 \text{ GeV}$		

Table 4.1: Event triggers for the HWW analysis. The energy and momentum thresholds of the L1 and HLT triggers are listed as well as the electron likelihood and isolation criteria. The isolation criterion for electrons [116] is calculated similarly to the description in section 3.3. For muons [117], the isolation is approximated by summing over tracks within a distance d of the muon vertex with $d = 6 \text{ mm}$ for the 2015-2017 and $d = 2 \text{ mm}$ for the 2018 data-taking period. For single-lepton triggers, each line defines an independent trigger. For the dilepton trigger, the criteria for both the electron and muon need to be satisfied.

Finally, a dilepton trigger combines an electron and a muon requirement and allows to collect events with lower- p_T leptons, an electron with $p_{T,e} > 17 \text{ GeV}$ and a muon with $p_{T,\mu} > 14 \text{ GeV}$. This trigger recovers events with leptons close to the momentum threshold of the single-lepton triggers, where the selection efficiency is comparatively low [118]. In addition, the loose requirements select a sizeable number of events that are used for the data-driven background estimate in chapter 6. Compared to using only single-lepton triggers, the selection efficiency of events with one loose and one tight lepton is increased by approximately 50 %, the efficiency of events with two loose leptons even by over 300 %.

In the ATLAS detector, many intricate components distributed over multiple subsystems need to work together to collect high-quality data. To ensure the necessary data quality [119], the recorded events are scrutinized depending on the detector conditions during data-taking. Only if every subdetector performs adequately, are the corresponding events flagged as good for physics analyses. Also issues in the trigger system or during reconstruction can cause data to be rejected. Out of the recorded data for general physics analyses, 95.6 % satisfy the requirements. This dataset has an integrated luminosity of $\int \mathcal{L} dt = (139.0 \pm 2.4)/\text{fb}$ [73].

4.2 Monte Carlo Simulation

The physics of particle collisions is described by the quantum field theory in chapter 2. But not all of the interactions can be calculated with exact methods. This is most relevant for QCD. When QCD processes are simulated, the high-energetic interactions with a small coupling constant, that can be approximated with perturbation theory, are separated from low-energetic interactions. The non-perturbative behaviour at low energies in the initial state is described by measured PDFs and the DGLAP equations. In the final state, parton-shower

algorithms approximate the impact of QCD on the parton radiation and hadronization methods model the formation of bound states.

The phase space of the produced final-state particles grows with the number of particles and states. To integrate over the potentially large space, the simulations use Monte-Carlo (MC) methods characterized by repeated random sampling. The following sections give an overview of the most basic ingredients of current MC generators following Refs. [7, 120].

4.2.1 Hard Interaction

Among the many interactions in proton-proton collisions, the interaction with the highest energy and momentum transfer is typically the relevant one (*hard interaction*). Because of the high energies involved, it can be described by perturbation theory. The fundamental transition amplitude of a process $a, b \rightarrow n$ with incoming partons a, b and outgoing particles n is given by the matrix element $\mathcal{M}_{a,b \rightarrow n}$, which can be calculated with the help of Feynman rules. The particles n are the products of the hard interaction, eg. leptons or partons, and do not include showering and hadronization. To calculate the cross section, the matrix element that depends on the kinematic variables of the produced particles is integrated over the PDFs of the particles associated with a, b and the kinematically allowed phase space of the final-state particles. It is also averaged over the possible initial-state and summed over the possible final-state configurations, namely the colour and helicity. The result is the total cross section

$$\sigma_0 = \int_0^1 dx_a dx_b \frac{1}{2x_a x_b s} f_a(x_a, \mu_F) f_b(x_b, \mu_F) \int d\Phi_n |\mathcal{M}_{a,b \rightarrow n}|^2(\Phi_n, \mu_F, \mu_R). \quad (4.1)$$

The PDFs f_a and f_b depend on the momentum fraction x_a and x_b of the partons a and b . The cross section also depends on the centre-of-mass energy \sqrt{s} of the colliding protons. The second part of the equation integrates the matrix element over the allowed phase space $d\Phi_n$ of the final-state particles n , which also depends on the initial-state kinematics. The perturbative approximation is part of the matrix element and its precision depends on the Feynman diagrams that are included in the calculation.

4.2.2 Parton Shower

The cross section in equation (4.1) is independent of the further evolution of the outgoing particles at lower energies. Facilitated by the running QCD coupling constant, partons split into a multitude of low-energetic partons, that are later — after hadronization and after depositing their energy in the calorimeter — collectively used as input to reconstruct jets in the detector. To simulate this repeated splitting, parton shower algorithms are used.

Parton showers estimate how probable it is to generate a certain amount of additional parton radiation. They are based on perturbative approximations for low-energetic (soft) and small-angle (collinear) radiation. Given a final state and its cross section, a related cross section can be calculated of the same process with one additional radiated parton,

if the parton energy and its emission angle are in a certain range. The differential cross section diverges in the case of soft or collinear parton emissions. These states, however, are not physically meaningful, because they cannot be distinguished by physical observables. Therefore, parton showers apply a cut-off and do not model explicitly this infrared radiation.

One can incorporate the energy and angular dependence of the cross section into one ordering variable, called hardness. By comparing the cross section of the original process and the same process dressed with a parton in a certain hardness range, an emission probability can be derived. Parton shower algorithms make use of this probability when generating parton radiation. They start at the hardness scale of the primary process and generate random variables that determine the hardness at which parton splittings occur. This evolution is terminated when the hardness reaches the hadronization scale, at which partons start to combine to hadrons. In a similar way, also the initial-state partons undergo a parton-shower evolution. This is simulated by starting at large hardness scale and evolving backwards in time towards the initial hadron with a small hardness and high momentum fraction. Below these scales, the proton evolution is described by its PDF.

4.2.3 Matching

A matrix element calculation predicts hard and well-separated radiation, but diverges if confronted with low-energetic radiation. On the other hand, parton shower algorithms use the approximation of small emission angles or soft radiation. Because of their different validity, the two approaches are combined in MC simulation to describe the different regions of phase space accurately. It is challenging to harmonize these two approaches in a way that avoids double-counting.

The first methods that were developed matched LO matrix elements with showers. These methods were extended to be compatible with LO matrix-element calculations that include real corrections. In order to use matrix-element calculations at NLO that include effects of real and virtual corrections, even different matching methods are needed. Finally, some MC generators also combine these two procedures and generate higher-order matrix elements together with additional radiation.

For each of the cases above, appropriate matching methods need to be used to combine two regimes of hard and soft radiation. An overview can be found in Ref. [121]. The configurations of MC simulation in section 4.3 make use of matching algorithms without explicitly discussing them.

4.2.4 Hadronization

After the parton shower has generated all soft emissions down to the hadronization scale, the partons form hadronic bound states. This process is non-perturbative and therefore MC generators use “QCD-inspired phenomenological models” [7] to simulate this stage. Two models are most commonly used, the Lund String model and the Cluster model.

The Lund String model is based on the linear colour potential caused by gluon self-interactions. As quarks move away from each other, they are thought to be connected by a string representing the linear potential. When the distance between the quarks increases, the string breaks with a probability that is proportional to the string length such that breaks commonly occur at distances of 1 fm to 5 fm. The energy released by the string break spawns a new pair of quarks that also participate in further string formation. The separation of the two newly created quarks is modeled by quantum mechanical tunnelling, which determines the distribution of their transverse momenta with respect to the string axis. The tunnelling is also used to explain that strange quarks are produced less frequently and that heavier quarks are effectively not produced.

The string formation continues between all quarks and stops only once the invariant mass of the individual $q\bar{q}$ systems is too low to create further quarks. Gluons have two colour charges and can therefore be incorporated into the Lund String model by introducing a kink into the string. A string that would usually connect two quarks directly, now connects them indirectly via the gluon. This procedure is infrared-safe, implying that low-energetic gluon radiation does not change physical observables significantly.

In the next step, adjacent quarks are combined to hadrons. They acquire a momentum along the string axis that is determined by energy conservation. The spin states and flavour properties of the hadrons are not intrinsically predicted by the Lund String model. They are described by tuneable parameters that are adjusted to match data.

The Cluster model takes a different approach and first constructs clusters of quarks, which decay into hadrons later. Starting after the parton shower, all gluons are forced to decay into quarks. At this stage, the production of strange quarks is suppressed with respect to up and down quarks. Next, close-by $q\bar{q}$ pairs are combined into meson-like clusters. This procedure produces clusters with a characteristic invariant-mass distribution that is observed during the parton shower. Many clusters have masses below 1 GeV, but a long tail extends towards higher masses. Light clusters are treated as excited mesons that decay into a lower-energetic state. Clusters with higher energy decay and can produce heavy-flavour and strange quarks.

The Lund String model is used in the PYTHIA event generator and tends to have a higher accuracy than the Cluster model [120]. The advantage of the Cluster model, however, is that it contains fewer free parameters, while retaining a decent agreement with collider data. The Cluster model is most notably used in the HERWIG and SHERPA event generators. Free model parameters are tuned to data within physically sensible boundaries of the model.

4.2.5 Decays and Underlying Event

After hadronization, the event record still contains unstable states that need to decay further before interacting with the detector. These can be excited hadrons, but also τ leptons or exotic particles. The decay of these particles can be simulated with different levels of

sophistication and each MC generator has a certain set of procedures implemented. Typically, dedicated matrix elements are calculated and they can contain various physical effects.

In the description above, only the hard interaction and the directly related interactions, such as decays and parton shower, have been described. The *underlying event* denotes all effects that are indirectly related to the hard interaction. The main contribution comes from colour exchanges between the products of the hard interaction and the remnants of the fragmenting hadrons. It is possible that also other partons interact in the same hadron pair, called *multiple-parton interactions*. Despite the comparatively small momentum transfer, the colour flow in multi-parton interactions can affect the topology of the entire event.

The collective term pile-up [122] describes all other processes that can deposit a signal in the detector. It is dominated by inelastic collisions of other protons pairs than the ones involved in the hard interaction. These inelastic collisions have a large cross section (cf. Figure 2.5). They constitute a significant background, whose typical jet signature is simulated with MC generators. Inelastic proton-proton interactions can be split into in-time and out-of-time pile-up depending on whether they occur in the same bunch-crossing as the hard interaction. Subdetectors respond differently to out-of-time pile-up depending on their internal time resolution. Other contributions to pile-up come from proton collisions with residual gas in the beampipe, with upstream accelerator elements, cavern backgrounds and cosmic radiation.

At this point of the simulation, the physical information from the high-energetic proton interaction is encoded in the generated particles. The event record at this point is often referred to as *particle level*. In order to compare the simulated events to the actual data, also the particle trajectories through the magnetic field and the detector response need to be simulated.

4.2.6 Detector Simulation and Digitization

In the ATLAS simulation infrastructure [123], the detector geometry is defined with its material composition. This is needed as an input to the GEANT4 [124–126] framework, which simulates how the generated particles interact with the detector matter. The simulation output comprises the amount of energy deposited in each detector element as a function of time.

In the next step, the energy deposits from pile-up are overlaid to the detector simulation. Also detector noise is added, before the energy deposits are digitized and passed through an emulated version of the read-out electronics. The output is in a similar format as the raw data from the detector and can be used directly for the event reconstruction (section 3.3). Additionally, intermediate information from the simulation can be stored, such as particle-level kinematics or decay chains. These are not used directly in an analysis, but can be helpful, for example to evaluate reconstruction efficiencies or systematic uncertainties.

Process	Matrix element (alternative)	PDF set	UEPS model (alternative model)	Prediction order for total cross section	Analysis
ggF H	POWHEG BOX v2 (MG5_aMC@NLO)	PDF4LHC15NNLO	PYTHIA 8.2 (HERWIG 7)	N3LO QCD + NLO EW	HWW
VBF H	POWHEG BOX v2 (MG5_aMC@NLO)	PDF4LHC15NLO	PYTHIA 8.2 (HERWIG 7)	NNLO QCD + NLO EW	HWW
VH excl. $gg \rightarrow ZH$	POWHEG BOX v2	PDF4LHC15NLO	PYTHIA 8.2	NNLO QCD + NLO EW	HWW
$gg \rightarrow ZH$	POWHEG BOX v2	PDF4LHC15NLO	PYTHIA 8.2	NNLL	HWW
$qq \rightarrow WW$	SHERPA 2.2.2	NNPDF3.0NNLO	SHERPA 2.2.2	NLO	HWW, Z +fake
$qq \rightarrow WWqq$	SHERPA 2.1.1	CT10	SHERPA 2.2.1	LO	HWW
$gg \rightarrow WW$	SHERPA 2.2.2	NNPDF3.0NNLO	SHERPA 2.2.2	NLO	HWW
$WZ/\gamma^*, ZZ \rightarrow$ leptons	SHERPA 2.2.2	NNPDF3.0NNLO	SHERPA 2.2.2	NLO	HWW, Z +fake
Other $WZ/\gamma^*, ZZ$	POWHEG BOX v2	CT10	PYTHIA 8.1	NLO	HWW
$VVV \rightarrow$ leptons	SHERPA 2.2.2	NNPDF3.0NNLO	SHERPA 2.2.2	NLO	Z +fake
$V\gamma$	SHERPA 2.2.8	NNPDF3.0NNLO	SHERPA 2.2.8	NLO	HWW, Z +fake
Z/γ^*	SHERPA 2.2.1 (MG5_aMC@NLO)	NNPDF3.0NNLO	SHERPA 2.2.1 (PYTHIA 8.1)	NNLO	HWW
Z/γ^*	POWHEG BOX v1	CT10	PYTHIA 8.2	NNLO	Z +fake
$t\bar{t}$	POWHEG BOX v2 (MG5_aMC@NLO)	NNPDF3.0NLO	PYTHIA 8.2 (HERWIG 7)	NNLO +NNLL	HWW, Z +fake
Wt	POWHEG BOX v2 (MG5_aMC@NLO)	NNPDF3.0NLO	PYTHIA 8.2 (HERWIG 7)	NNLO	HWW, Z +fake

Table 4.2: Configurations used to simulate signal and background processes (cf. Ref. [127]). The columns show the matrix element generator and the corresponding PDF set, followed by the tool to simulate the underlying event, parton shower (UEPS) and hadronization. The accuracy of the cross-section calculation is given. The last column indicates if the sample is used in the main HWW analysis or in the Z +fake analysis. Rows with entries in parentheses show secondary setups used to estimate systematic uncertainties.

4.3 MC Samples

MC simulation is needed both for the HWW analysis in chapter 7 and for the partly data-driven background estimate in chapter 6. In addition to the nominal yield prediction, it is also used to estimate various systematic uncertainties. A concise overview of the different samples is given and summarized in Table 4.2. The description and referenced publications largely follow ATLAS-internal documentation.

All Higgs-boson processes are simulated with the POWHEG BOX v2 generator [128–134] and assume a Higgs-boson mass of $m_H = 125$ GeV. The parton shower and hadronization are modeled with PYTHIA 8.2 [135] using the AZNLO tune [136]. The branching ratios are calculated with HDECAY [137–139] and PROPHECY4F [140–142] as described and calculated in Ref. [20]. Also the Higgs-boson cross sections are taken from this reference.

The ggF production mode is simulated at NNLO in QCD with the PDF4LHC15NNLO set [12] with the renormalization and factorization scales set to half the Higgs-boson mass. The cross section for the sample normalization is taken from a calculation at N3LO in QCD (using the infinite top-mass approximation above NLO) and NLO in electroweak effects (cf. equation (2.33)).

The VBF events are generated with NLO accuracy with the PDF4LHC15NLO set and use the W -boson mass as renormalization and factorization scale. The cross section normalization is calculated at NNLO in QCD and NLO for electroweak corrections (cf. equation (2.34)). For the Higgs-radiation processes VH , the qq -initiated processes are generated with the same accuracy as the VBF production mode. The gg -initiated ZH process is simulated separately at LO with the PDF4LHC15NLO set with a cross-section normalization calculated at NLO.

The other processes involving two heavy vector bosons [143] in the Standard Model, namely WW , WZ , ZZ , with leptonic decays are simulated with the SHERPA [144] event generator. Most processes use version SHERPA 2.2.2. They are required to contain at least two charged leptons with $p_T > 5$ GeV. Up to one additional parton is generated at NLO in QCD and up to two further partons at LO. The invariant mass of the diboson system $\mu = m_{VV}$ is used as the core scale, which is the basis for determining the parton-shower dependent renormalization and factorization scale. For the processes WW and ZZ , the production mode initiated by a gluon pair is simulated separately at LO with one additional parton. The diagrams with WW vector-boson scattering and two additional partons in the final state are the only ones simulated with SHERPA 2.1.1. They are generated at LO. Triboson production is generated with zero partons at NLO and two additional partons at LO. Diboson production with semileptonic decays is simulated with POWHEG BOX v2 and PYTHIA 8.186 [145].

SHERPA 2.2.8 [144] is used to generate heavy vector bosons with an additional photon, $W+\gamma$ and $Z+\gamma$. Up to one additional parton is produced at NLO accuracy in QCD, two more partons at LO. Photons are required to have a transverse momentum of at least 7 GeV.

To enhance the fraction of events generated with large transverse momentum, events are biased towards large transverse momenta of the heavy vector boson or photon.

The nominal leptonic Z/γ^* sample [146] is generated with SHERPA 2.2.1. Up to two additional partons are generated in the matrix element at NLO, up to four partons at LO. In order to enhance the statistics in the phase space with large transverse momenta, the sample is split into several subsamples according to the variable $\max(H_T, p_{T,Z})$, where H_T is the scalar sum of the transverse momentum of all final-state particles at parton level. A different Z/γ^* sample is used for the Z +fake analysis in chapter 6. It is generated with POWHEG BOX v1 at NLO. The invariant mass of the two charged leptons is required to be $m_{\ell\ell} > 60$ GeV. The parton shower and underlying event are simulated with PYTHIA 8.210 using the AZNLO tune [147]. The PDF sets CT10 [148] and CTEQ6L1 [149] are used for the scattering process and parton shower, respectively. Both setups use the same cross section calculated at NNLO [150].

In all SHERPA samples, the PDF set NNPDF3.0NNLO [151] is used together with a tune provided by the SHERPA authors. The matching and merging between matrix element and parton shower in the heavy vector-boson samples follows the MEPS@NLO [152] scheme. The $V+\gamma$ samples use a merging scheme in the electroweak coupling that is described in Ref. [153].

Events containing a pair of top quarks [154] are generated with the POWHEG BOX v2 [128–130, 155] event generator and the NNPDF3.0NLO set. The model parameter h_{damp} [156, 157], which is related to the matching method in POWHEG BOX and controls the amount of radiation, is set to 1.5 times the top-quark mass $m_t = 172.5$ GeV. The parton shower and underlying event is simulated with PYTHIA 8.230 [135] in combination with the A14 tune [158] and the NNPDF2.3LO [159] set. The renormalization and factorization scales are set to $\mu = \sqrt{m_t^2 + p_T^2}$ with the transverse momentum of the top quark p_T . The cross section of the $t\bar{t}$ process is calculated independently at NNLO accuracy in QCD with the TOP++2.0 program [160].

The production of a top quark and an associated W boson is simulated analogously to the $t\bar{t}$ process. Overlap with $t\bar{t}$ production is removed according to the method in Ref. [161] and corrections to the cross section are calculated following Ref. [162]. The renormalization and factorization scales are set to m_t .

Chapter 5

Data-driven Estimation Techniques

Backgrounds to analyses, such as the HWW analysis, are commonly estimated with simulated datasets for each background source. As an alternative, data-driven methods estimate the expected yield of a process directly from data. A variety of different methods have been developed [163], often tailored to the needs of an analysis. To estimate the background from events with misidentified leptons, the Matrix Method is a popular choice, because of the straightforward derivation and clear underlying idea. As an alternative, the Fake Factor Method has been used increasingly in the past years, because it has advantages in practice. Most notably, it allows to estimate yields in a blinded signal region. The connection between the two methods is shown in this chapter proving that the Fake Factor Method can be derived exactly from the Matrix Method.

After an overview of the motivation in section 5.1 and notation in section 5.2, the Matrix Method is introduced in section 5.3. This section serves as the basis for the derivation of the Fake Factor Method in section 5.4. The equations for one-lepton and two-lepton events are considered separately to highlight how the equations generalize to multi-lepton events. Afterwards, also the case with an arbitrary number of leptons is shown. The latter, most general case is used in analyses, but its mathematical derivation has not been documented to the knowledge of the author. Section 5.5 summarizes practical considerations and section 5.6 investigates the statistical properties of the Fake Factor Method.

5.1 Motivation

When data from particle collisions are processed, reconstruction algorithms try to identify the particle that caused a specific detector signature. If an object is correctly reconstructed, i.e. as the same particle that was produced in the final state of the hard interaction, it is called *real*, otherwise *fake*. In this chapter, the relevant example of *real* and *fake leptons* will be used, but the methods are not specific to leptons.

In theory, charged stable leptons are straightforward to identify; electrons by their tracks and deposits in the electromagnetic calorimeter and muons by their long track that extends all the way into the muon spectrometer. But in practice, other particles can produce similar

signatures. A typical example for fake processes are photons converting into electrons once they reach the beampipe or first detector layers. If their decay kinematics is compatible with an electron from the interaction point, they can easily be misidentified. Another example is a jet containing a b hadron, whose decay produces a non-prompt muon. In this case, the jet could be misidentified as a muon with additional radiation. Generally, fake leptons can be objects with a genuine lepton that is only produced after the hard interaction (*non-prompt leptons*) or wrongly reconstructed objects (*misidentified leptons*). The reconstruction algorithms have been refined extensively to identify the particle at the hard-interaction level, but it is still possible for detector signatures to be mistaken for a wrong particle.

Of the current analyses by ATLAS and CMS with leptons in the final state, many do not use simulation to estimate the contribution of misidentified leptons. Even though this is rarely mentioned explicitly, the main reason is the inaccurate modelling of jet signatures and the inability to describe data after applying identification criteria¹ [164, 165]. There are a number of reasons for mismodelling.

Firstly, there are many different mechanisms through which jets can mistakenly be identified as leptons. To predict fake rates accurately, MC simulation would need to predict the rate and signatures of these different mechanisms correctly. Secondly, identification algorithms use empirical variables, optimized and evaluated on data with tag-and-probe methods [102, 105]. These variables cannot be predicted from first principles [166]. Furthermore, identification and isolation algorithms have a high rejection rate for jets in the order of 100 to 1000 [102], so that only the odd jet is able to fake a lepton. Because of their rarity, it is difficult to find a general description that works well for both typical jets and also for jets prone to faking leptons. For a similar reason, also the detector simulation of jets has an impact on the fake estimate. In the rare case that the detector response resembles a lepton, the “non-Gaussian tails” [167] are difficult to model causing an inaccurate prediction of the fake rate.

To not depend on modelling deficiencies of simulation, data-driven methods are used to measure the number of events (*fake events*) containing at least one object misidentified as a lepton (*fake lepton*). This is particularly important in analyses, where the number of leptons is a key signature of the physical process.

5.2 Orthogonal Selections and Notation

The goal of the Matrix and Fake Factor Methods is to estimate the number of events, in which a certain number of leptons are fake leptons. To this end, a *control selection* is defined

¹It should be mentioned that some analyses do not need to describe misidentified leptons explicitly, for example when the contribution is negligible or when a parametric function is used to estimate the background.

in addition to the *signal selection* which is used in the nominal analysis². While the signal selection aims to reduce the number of events containing fake leptons, the control selection is designed to be enriched in fake events.

The signal selection typically requires that all leptons pass the identification criteria. By inverting these quality requirements (and potentially introducing additional, looser requirements), control selections can be constructed. Inverting the criteria for all leptons independently allows to construct $(2^M - 1)$ control selections in an analysis with M leptons. To identify these selections and their leptons more easily, a lepton is called *tight* if it passes the quality cuts. A lepton is called *loose* if it satisfies the control-selection criteria that are orthogonal to the tight quality criteria. The union of both categories is called *baseline*.

It is important to appreciate the difference between signal regions or control regions and signal selections or control selections. The regions are defined by applying cuts on variables related to the event or individual objects. Their purpose is to construct regions in phase space that are pure in signal or background. For each of these regions, 2^M different signal or control selections exist defined by applying the regular or inverted identification criteria to each lepton. For each region, the fake event yield in the signal selection can be estimated from the fake event yield in the control selections as shown in section 5.3. To prepare for this analysis, the notation is quickly summarized here. The notation is based on ATLAS-internal documentation.

Given a real baseline lepton, the probability that it is categorized as tight is denoted with the conditional probability $r = P(t|r)$. Similarly, the probability that a fake baseline lepton is tight is parametrized by $f = P(t|f)$. Then the probability that a real or fake lepton ends up in the loose selection is $P(l|r) = (1 - r)$ or $P(l|f) = (1 - f)$, respectively. Since each lepton can unambiguously be assigned one category, the probabilities here should be understood in the Frequentist interpretation. Because the probabilities are measured as a fraction of events satisfying certain requirements, they are often called *real* and *fake efficiencies*.

Most equations describe the number of events N with a specific lepton configuration. For each of the M leptons in the event, a subscript labels the true origin of the lepton, r for real and f for fake³. Superscripts indicate if a lepton is reconstructed as a tight t or loose l lepton. If sub- or superscripts are omitted, the lepton can belong to either of the categories, eg. $N = N^t + N^l$ and $N_r = N_r^t + N_r^l$. The leptons are in a fixed order⁴ implying that N_{rf}^{tl}

²The control selection is sometimes referred to as a “control sample”. This term is not used here, because the equivalent term “signal sample” is typically reserved for the main signal process in an analysis.

³Note that the subscript labels are chosen like the real and fake efficiencies earlier. This is done on purpose, but the meaning is different. If r and f are used as subscript, they specify the true origin of a lepton. If they are used as a variable, they refer to the probability that a real or fake lepton is reconstructed as a tight lepton.

⁴The method with which leptons are ordered is not important, but it matters that leptons can be labeled unambiguously. In practice, leptons are often ordered by their transverse momentum.

describes different events than N_{fr}^{tt} . The first subscript describes the same lepton as the first superscript and so on.

The real and fake efficiencies r and f can depend on the lepton properties, like the kinematics and the lepton flavour. They can therefore differ between events and also between leptons in the same event. The event-dependent efficiencies are ignored in this derivation, but section 5.5.1 will show how to generalize the method. For the derivation here, it is important to know that different lepton efficiencies in the same event carry an index i that corresponds to lepton i .

5.3 Matrix Method

5.3.1 One Lepton

The idea of the Matrix Method is to construct a relation between the fake yield and measurable quantities. The connection is established with the help of fake efficiencies. If the lepton is a real lepton, the probability that it is tight is r . For a fake lepton, the probability that it is tight is f . With these definitions the number of events with a real or fake lepton can be mapped onto the number of events with a tight or loose lepton

$$\begin{pmatrix} N^t \\ N^l \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r & f \\ 1-r & 1-f \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} N_r \\ N_f \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.1)$$

The entries of the vector on the left-hand side can be measured in an analysis, but the terms on the right-hand side are unknown. If the efficiencies r and f can be determined in a different way, the number of events with fake and real leptons can be calculated by solving the system of equations. After matrix inversion, the equation is

$$\frac{1}{f-r} \begin{pmatrix} f-1 & f \\ 1-r & -r \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} N^t \\ N^l \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} N_r \\ N_f \end{pmatrix}. \quad (5.2)$$

The variable of interest is N_f^t , the number of events with a fake lepton in the tight (i.e. signal) selection. It can be read off equation (5.2)

$$N_f^t = fN_f = \frac{f}{f-r} ((1-r)N^t - rN^l). \quad (5.3)$$

This equation relates the number of events in the measurable tight and loose regions to the expected number of fake leptons in the tight region. This equation is only helpful if r and f can be determined elsewhere. How these efficiencies can be measured will be explained in section 5.5 using the Fake Factor Method.

In equation (5.3), every event has exactly one lepton. As long as this is the case, the variable N can also be interpreted as number of leptons. This interpretation might be easier to grasp, but it does not work anymore in the following sections.

5.3.2 Two Leptons

With two leptons in the analysis selection, equation (5.1) needs to be extended and different efficiencies r and f need to be introduced for the first and second lepton. This takes into account that the efficiencies depend on the kinematics of the lepton or the lepton flavour. They will carry indices indicating which lepton they refer to.

$$\begin{pmatrix} N^{tt} \\ N^{tl} \\ N^{lt} \\ N^{ll} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} r_1 r_2 & r_1 f_2 & f_1 r_2 & f_1 f_2 \\ r_1(1-r_2) & r_1(1-f_2) & f_1(1-r_2) & f_1(1-f_2) \\ (1-r_1)r_2 & (1-r_1)f_2 & (1-f_1)r_2 & (1-f_1)f_2 \\ (1-r_1)(1-r_2) & (1-r_1)(1-f_2) & (1-f_1)(1-r_2) & (1-f_1)(1-f_2) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} N_{rr} \\ N_{rf} \\ N_{fr} \\ N_{ff} \end{pmatrix} \quad (5.4)$$

With more than one lepton in the final state, the variable of interest can vary between analyses. Typically a two-lepton signal region would be used to detect a signal with two real leptons. For such an analysis, the relevant background will be events with exactly two tight leptons of which at least one is a fake lepton (*fake events* as defined above). The three possible combinations are N_{rf}^{tt} , N_{fr}^{tt} , N_{ff}^{tt} and their sum can be rewritten using the notation $N^{tt} = N_{rr}^{tt} + N_{rf}^{tt} + N_{fr}^{tt} + N_{ff}^{tt}$. Then the number of fake events is given by

$$\begin{aligned} N^{tt} - N_{rr}^{tt} &= N_{rf}^{tt} + N_{fr}^{tt} + N_{ff}^{tt} = r_1 f_2 N_{rf} + f_1 r_2 N_{fr} + f_1 f_2 N_{ff} \\ &= \frac{1}{(f_1 - r_1)(f_2 - r_2)} \\ &\quad \cdot [(f_1 f_2 - f_2 r_1 - f_1 r_2 + f_1 r_1 r_2 + f_2 r_1 r_2 - f_1 f_2 r_1 r_2) N^{tt} \\ &\quad + (f_2 r_1 r_2 - f_1 f_2 r_1 r_2) N^{tl} \\ &\quad + (f_1 r_1 r_2 - f_1 f_2 r_1 r_2) N^{lt} \\ &\quad - (f_1 f_2 r_1 r_2) N^{ll}] \end{aligned} \quad (5.5)$$

The last step can be reproduced by inverting the matrix in equation (5.4) and calculating the individual components N_{rf} , N_{fr} , N_{ff} . The inverted matrix is shown in Appendix B.1.

5.3.3 Any Number of Leptons

The equations (5.1) and (5.4) can be generalized to an arbitrary number of leptons M

$$N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} = \sum_{i_1 \in \{r, f\}} \sum_{i_2 \in \{r, f\}} \dots \sum_{i_M \in \{r, f\}} \left(\prod_{k=1}^M \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right) N_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_M}, \quad (5.7)$$

where the superscripts j stand for the tight and loose lepton categories t and l . The indices i stand for the real and fake leptons r and f and the sums iterate over all possible combinations of them. The elements of the $2^M \times 2^M$ matrix of real and fake lepton efficiencies are given by

the product of ϵ terms. These are defined as

$$\epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} = \begin{cases} r_k, & \text{if } j_k = t, i_k = r \\ f_k, & \text{if } j_k = t, i_k = f \\ (1 - r_k), & \text{if } j_k = l, i_k = r \\ (1 - f_k), & \text{if } j_k = l, i_k = f \end{cases} \quad (5.8)$$

For a given number of leptons, equation (5.7) can be inverted and used to estimate the number of fake events.

5.3.4 Drawbacks of the Matrix Method

Even though the Matrix Method is straightforward to write down, solving the equation for more than two leptons is difficult in practice. It also requires the definition and measurement of many control selections and it is not immediately obvious which terms are negligible for the final result.

Another significant drawback is that the number of fake events depends on the number of events in the signal selection. In the one-lepton example, this is the N^t term in equation (5.3). Analyses in high-energy physics are typically *blinded*, meaning that the data in the signal region is deliberately disregarded during the optimization of the analysis. Only when the optimization, uncertainty estimate and statistical analysis are finalized, is the data unblinded. Thus, the fake estimate in the signal region is unknown until the analysis is unblinded. This impedes the estimate of expected uncertainties on the measured variable, because the fake estimate cannot fully be taken into account.

A conceptual drawback is that the Matrix Method is not statistically independent of the measurement in the signal selection. If there is a fluctuation in the signal selection, the Matrix Method automatically shifts the fake estimate to accommodate the fluctuation. Again, in the one-lepton selection the term N^t is responsible for this. This needs to be considered explicitly in the statistical analysis.

5.4 Fake Factor Method

The Fake Factor Method solves the problems above by simulating the contribution of events with only real leptons. Hence, unlike the Matrix Method, the Fake Factor Method is not a fully data-driven estimate, but depends partly on simulation. However, since real leptons are generally well-modelled in simulation, this does not defeat the motivation of using a data-driven estimate. With the additional information from simulation, the equations become independent of the signal region yield. Like for the Matrix Method, the one- and two-lepton cases are shown explicitly before the general treatment is outlined.

	signal region	control region
signal selection (tight lepton)	$N_A = N^t - N_r^t$	$N_B = N'^t - N_r'^t$
control selection (loose lepton)	$N_C = N^l - N_r^l$	$N_D = N'^l - N_r'^l$

Figure 5.1: Relation between ABCD method and Fake Factor Method in a one-lepton signal region. The columns show different regions and the rows different lepton selections. To distinguish terms in the signal and control regions, the yields in the control region are primed.

5.4.1 One Lepton

Starting at equation (5.1), both sides of the equation can be multiplied from the left-hand side by a row vector with the entries $(1, -\frac{f}{1-f})$.

$$N^t - \frac{f}{1-f}N^l = rN_r + fN_f - \frac{f}{1-f}(1-r)N_r - \frac{f}{1-f}(1-f)N_f \quad (5.9)$$

$$rN_r + N_f^t - \frac{f}{1-f}N^l = rN_r - \frac{f}{1-f}N_r^l \quad (5.10)$$

$$N_f^t = F(N^l - N_r^l) \quad (5.11)$$

To get to the second line, the equations $N^t = N_r^t + N_f^t$, $N_r^t = rN_r$ and $N_r^l = (1-r)N_r$ are used. In the last line, the new variable

$$F = \frac{f}{1-f} \quad (5.12)$$

is introduced. This term is commonly called *fake factor* and gives the Fake Factor Method its name.

Equation (5.11) is the equivalent of equation (5.3) in the Matrix Method. It expresses the variable of interest, N_f^t , in terms of lepton identification efficiencies and the term N^l , that can be measured in data. But instead of the variable N^t , that is used in the Matrix Method and that is not available in a blinded analysis, the Fake Factor Method depends on N_r^l . Since it requires that the involved lepton is a real lepton, the term cannot be measured directly and is taken from Monte Carlo simulation. Hence, by dismissing the fully data-driven approach and using simulation to model real leptons, the Fake Factor Method can give an estimate of the fake yield without unblinding the signal region.

It is noteworthy that the one-lepton Fake Factor equation is equivalent to the ABCD method [168]. This becomes clear in section 5.5, where the measurement of the fake factor is explained. As illustrated in Figure 5.1, each of the four regions is defined by the difference in event yield between data and real-lepton events. Then the equation $N_A = N_C \frac{N_B}{N_D}$ reproduces

the result of equation (5.11):

$$N_A = N^t - N_r^t = (N^l - N_r^l) \frac{N^{tt} - N_r^{tt}}{N^{tl} - N_r^{tl}} = N_C \frac{N_B}{N_D}. \quad (5.13)$$

The fake factor can be identified as $F = \frac{N_B}{N_D}$. In order to extend the ABCD method to more than one lepton, the visual representation in Figure 5.1 would need to obtain one additional dimension for each added lepton.

5.4.2 Two Leptons

The Fake Factor Method with two leptons is derived similarly to the one-lepton selection. The row vector that will simplify equation (5.4) is $(1, -F_2, -F_1, F_1 F_2)$. Explicitly writing out the multiplication leads to the expression

$$\begin{aligned} & N^{tt} - F_2 N^{tl} - F_1 N^{tt} + F_1 F_2 N^{ll} \\ = & (r_1 r_2 - r_1(1 - r_2)F_2 - F_1(1 - r_1)r_2 + F_1 F_2(1 - r_1)(1 - r_2))N_{rr} \\ & + (r_1 f_2 - r_1 f_2 - F_1(1 - r_1)f_2 + F_1 f_2(1 - r_1))N_{rf} \\ & + (f_1 r_2 - f_1(1 - r_2)F_2 - f_1 r_2 + F_2 f_1(1 - r_2))N_{fr} \\ & + (f_1 f_2 - f_1 f_2 - f_1 f_2 + f_1 f_2)N_{ff}. \end{aligned} \quad (5.14)$$

The row vector is chosen to let the second, third and fourth row vanish. This illustrates the concept of the Fake Factor Method: it eliminates all terms containing fake leptons by absorbing them into the measurable terms on the left-hand side. The terms in the first row combine and constitute the subtraction of processes with real leptons. It can be rewritten to give the following equation, which estimates the number of events with at least one fake lepton

$$N^{tt} - N_{rr}^{tt} = F_2(N^{tl} - N_{rr}^{tl}) + F_1(N^{tt} - N_{rr}^{tt}) - F_1 F_2(N^{ll} - N_{rr}^{ll}). \quad (5.15)$$

5.4.3 Any Number of Leptons

Equation (5.7) holds for any combination of j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M . Just like in the one- and two-lepton case, this equation will be multiplied by a row vector from the left. In index notation, the equivalent of equation (5.15) is obtained by multiplying every N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} by a corresponding factor z^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} and then summing over all of them

$$\sum_{\text{comb. } j} z^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} = \sum_{\text{comb. } j} z^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} \sum_{\text{comb. } i} \left(\prod_{k=1}^M \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right) N_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_M}. \quad (5.16)$$

The notation $\text{comb. } i$ indicates that all combinations of i are summed over; similarly $\text{comb. } j$ indicates the summation over all combinations of j . It is used as a shorthand for the more explicit notation in equation (5.7). To evoke the same cancellation as in the one- and

two-lepton case, the row vector is chosen as

$$z^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} = \prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \quad \text{with} \quad \zeta^{j_k} = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j_k = t \\ -F_k, & \text{if } j_k = l \end{cases} \quad (5.17)$$

The entries of this row vector and the product of efficiencies in equation (5.8) are supposed to cancel out the fake contributions. So it is not surprising that they have a similar form. Combining the two terms yields

$$\zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} = \begin{cases} r_k, & \text{if } j_k = t, i_k = r \\ f_k, & \text{if } j_k = t, i_k = f \\ -F_k(1 - r_k), & \text{if } j_k = l, i_k = r \\ -f_k, & \text{if } j_k = l, i_k = f \end{cases} \quad (5.18)$$

After substituting the entries of the row vector and swapping the two sums on the right-hand side, equation (5.16) can be rewritten as

$$\sum_{\text{comb. } j} \left(\prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \right) N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} = \sum_{\text{comb. } i} \sum_{\text{comb. } j} \left(\prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right) N_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_M} \quad (5.19)$$

Consider now the right-hand side of the equation for a fixed combination of i and write the first term of the sum over j explicitly.

$$\sum_{\text{comb. } j} \left(\prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right) N_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_M} \quad (5.20)$$

$$= \sum_{j_2 \in \{t, l\}} \sum_{j_3 \in \{t, l\}} \dots \sum_{j_M \in \{t, l\}} \left(\left[\prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right]_{j_1=t_1} + \left[\prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right]_{j_1=l_1} \right) N_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_M} \quad (5.21)$$

$$= \sum_{j_2 \in \{t, l\}} \sum_{j_3 \in \{t, l\}} \dots \sum_{j_M \in \{t, l\}} \left(\left[\zeta_{i_1}^{t_1} \epsilon_{i_1}^{t_1} \prod_{k=2}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right] + \left[\zeta_{i_1}^{l_1} \epsilon_{i_1}^{l_1} \prod_{k=2}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right] \right) N_{i_1, i_2, \dots, i_M} \quad (5.22)$$

Next, consider this equation for combinations of i containing at least one fake lepton, i.e. $i_l = f$ for at least one index l . Without loss of generality, one can choose $l = 1$ and substitute into expression (5.22):

$$\sum_{\text{comb. } j} \prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} N_{f_1, i_2, \dots, i_M} \quad (5.23)$$

$$= \sum_{j_2 \in \{t, l\}} \sum_{j_3 \in \{t, l\}} \dots \sum_{j_M \in \{t, l\}} \left(\left[f_1 \prod_{k=2}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right] + \left[-f_1 \prod_{k=2}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{i_k}^{j_k} \right] \right) N_{f_1, i_2, \dots, i_M} \quad (5.24)$$

$$= 0 \quad (5.25)$$

The explicit substitution of the efficiencies $\zeta^{l_1} \epsilon_{f_1}^{l_1}$ and $\zeta^{t_1} \epsilon_{f_1}^{t_1}$ from equation (5.18) shows that all terms with at least one fake lepton vanish. Hence, on the right-hand side of equation (5.19) only terms with real-lepton contributions remain so that the sum over all combinations i becomes obsolete. Thus, equation (5.19) can be written as

$$\sum_{\text{comb. } j} \left(\prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \right) N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} = \sum_{\text{comb. } j} \left(\prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{r_k}^{j_k} \right) N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M} \quad (5.26)$$

The product on the right-hand side constitutes the remaining real contributions. When writing out the sums over j , a pattern emerges:

$$\sum_{\text{comb. } j} \left(\prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{r_k}^{j_k} \right) N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M} \quad (5.27)$$

$$= \sum_{j_2 \in \{t, l\}} \sum_{j_3 \in \{t, l\}} \dots \sum_{j_M \in \{t, l\}} \left(\prod_{k=2}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{r_k}^{j_k} \right) (\zeta^{t_1} \epsilon_{r_1}^{t_1} + \zeta^{l_1} \epsilon_{r_1}^{l_1}) N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M} \quad (5.28)$$

$$= \sum_{j_2 \in \{t, l\}} \sum_{j_3 \in \{t, l\}} \dots \sum_{j_M \in \{t, l\}} \left(\prod_{k=2}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{r_k}^{j_k} \right) (N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{t_1} - F_1 N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{l_1}) \quad (5.29)$$

$$= \sum_{j_3 \in \{t, l\}} \sum_{j_4 \in \{t, l\}} \dots \sum_{j_M \in \{t, l\}} \left(\prod_{k=3}^M \zeta^{j_k} \epsilon_{r_k}^{j_k} \right) (N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{t_1, t_2} - F_1 N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{l_1, t_2} - F_2 N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{t_1, l_2} + F_1 F_2 N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{l_1, l_2}) \quad (5.30)$$

$$= \sum_{\text{comb. } j} N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} \prod_{k=1}^M \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j_k = t \\ -F_k, & \text{if } j_k = l \end{cases} \quad (5.31)$$

The efficiencies from the ϵ terms decorate the variables N with superscripts and all combinations of tight and loose fake categories with real leptons appear. Due to the ζ terms, the summands pick up a factor $-F_k$ for each lepton k in the loose category.

The product on the left-hand side of equation (5.26) only contains ζ terms and no ϵ terms. Therefore, they only pick up a factor of $-F_k$ for each loose lepton and do not change superscripts:

$$\sum_{\text{comb. } j} \left(\prod_{k=1}^M \zeta^{j_k} \right) N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} = \sum_{\text{comb. } j} N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} \prod_{k=1}^M \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j_k = t \\ -F_k, & \text{if } j_k = l \end{cases} \quad (5.32)$$

The expressions in equations (5.31) and (5.32) are equal as was established in equation (5.26):

$$\sum_{\text{comb. } j} N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} \prod_{k=1}^M \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j_k = t \\ -F_k, & \text{if } j_k = l \end{cases} = \sum_{\text{comb. } j} N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} \prod_{k=1}^M \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j_k = t \\ -F_k, & \text{if } j_k = l \end{cases} \quad (5.33)$$

$$N^{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_M} - N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{t_1, t_2, \dots, t_M} = \sum_{\substack{\text{comb. } j \\ \text{except all } t}} (N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} - N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M}) \prod_{k=1}^M \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } j_k = t \\ -F_k, & \text{if } j_k = l \end{cases} \quad (5.34)$$

In the last line, the terms from both sides are combined to single out the components with only tight leptons. The sum generates all possible combinations of the terms j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M except for the combination t, t, \dots, t . This equation is the general form of the Fake Factor equation. The left-hand side is the number of events with at least one fake lepton in the signal selection. The right-hand side provides the estimate in all control selections using data for the total number of events and MC simulation to estimate the contribution of events with only real leptons.

If the order of the leptons is irrelevant, the equation can be simplified by combining events with the same number of loose leptons

$$N^{t, t, \dots, t} - N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{t, t, \dots, t} = \sum_{k=1}^M (N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{k \text{ loose}} - N^{k \text{ loose}}) (-1)^k \prod_{m=1}^k F_{l_m}. \quad (5.35)$$

The term F_{l_m} specifies the fake factor of the m -th loose lepton and $N^{k \text{ loose}}$ refers to the number of events with exactly k loose leptons.

Equation (5.35) shows that every event gets multiplied by a fake factor for each loose lepton it contains. Since the signal selection is designed to be depleted of fake events, the fake efficiency is typically small and therefore also the fake factor. Thus, the sum becomes less relevant as the index k increases. Provided that the number of events does not increase significantly with the number of loose leptons, the first terms of the sum provide a good estimate for the fake yield. If for instance the first two summands are considered, the equation can be approximated as

$$N^{t, t, \dots, t} - N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{t, t, \dots, t} \approx F_{l_1} (N^{\text{one loose}} - N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{\text{one loose}}) - F_{l_1} F_{l_2} (N^{\text{two loose}} - N_{r_1, r_2, \dots, r_M}^{\text{two loose}}). \quad (5.36)$$

It is worth noticing that the sign of successive elements in the sum alternates.

Other derivations of the Fake Factor Method can be found in literature with varying level of detail: for example Ref. [169] for the one-lepton equation, Ref. [170] for an approximate two-lepton derivation starting with the Matrix Method, Ref. [171] for a derivation for three leptons. But to the author's knowledge, it has neither been shown before that the Fake Factor Method works for any number of leptons nor that the Fake Factor equation can be derived exactly from the Matrix Method for large lepton multiplicities.

5.5 Fake Factor Method in Practice

This section is concerned with multiple issues that were ignored in the previous derivation, but are necessary to successfully use the Fake Factor Method in an analysis. The question of fake factors that vary between events is addressed; the extension of the Fake Factor Method to histograms; and the measurement of fake factors.

5.5.1 Event-dependent Fake Factors

It was mentioned in section 5.2 that fake efficiencies can vary between events. It turns out that this is easy to incorporate into the fake estimate, because all equations are linear in the number of events N . The Fake Factor equations can be split into many estimates for smaller, consistent datasets and added in the end. This can be done such that every individual estimate shares the same lepton identification efficiencies.

In practice, it is convenient to go even one step further and apply the estimate event-by-event and sum over the contributions of all events later. Hence, for every event in the control selections a weight is calculated consisting of the product of the negative of the fake factors of all loose leptons. Data events get an overall minus sign. If applicable, simulated events are multiplied by their generator-assigned weight. The sum of all weights is then equivalent to the fake estimate.

5.5.2 Application to Histograms

It is worth noting that the derived equations can be used to estimate the fake event yield in a differential distribution of a variable x . The fake estimate can be used for a particular histogram bin $x_1 < x < x_2$, which acts like an additional region requirement that the signal and all control selections need to satisfy. This procedure can be iteratively applied to each histogram bin $x_k < x < x_{k+1}$. If the fake factor depends on the variable x , this needs to be taken into account. It is imperative, however, that the signal and control selections are not constructed by using the variable x .

5.5.3 Measuring the Fake Factor

The question of how to measure the fake factor F has been deferred until now. The fake factor is related to the fake lepton efficiency f via $F = \frac{f}{1-f}$. It needs to be extracted in a region, where the fake lepton can reliably be identified. Furthermore, this region should also be independent of the regions exploited by the Fake Factor equations. A two-lepton analysis, for example, would typically be affected by fakes from W +jets. Then, a three-lepton region could be used to determine the fake factor from the Z +jets process. A Z -boson candidate would be reconstructed from two leptons and the third lepton would likely be the fake lepton. The properties of this lepton would then determine the fake factor.

To measure the fake factor, recall from section 5.2 the definition of the fake efficiency f , which is the fraction of fake leptons that are reconstructed as tight leptons. This can be expressed in terms of event yields as $f = \frac{N_f^t}{N_f^t + N_f^l}$. Using the definition of the fake factor, one can write

$$F = \frac{f}{1-f} = \frac{\frac{N_f^t}{N_f^t + N_f^l}}{1 - \frac{N_f^t}{N_f^t + N_f^l}} = \frac{N_f^t}{N_f^l} = \frac{N^t - N_r^t}{N^l - N_r^l} = \frac{N'^t - N_r'^t}{N'^l - N_r'^l}. \quad (5.37)$$

The last step indicates that the fake factor is the same in events with different signatures (N'), as long as the definition of tight and loose events and the properties of the fake lepton are the same. Using the example from above, N would be the event yield in W +jets and N' in Z +jets events.

Extracting the fake factor in one type of event and applying it to another type implicitly assumes that the fake rate is independent of the event signature. This is a justified assumption in many cases, because the relevant identification variables only use local information from a small detector region around the lepton. If the remaining event signature is outside of this small detector region, then the fake rate should be independent. Furthermore, the mechanisms causing misidentification occur late in the event evolution, too late to affect other particles produced in the hard interaction through quantum-mechanical processes.

The only properties that affect the misidentification rate are the properties of the misidentified particle, such as the momentum, pseudorapidity or origin of the fake lepton (*fake origin*, eg. the parton flavour). The first two variables have the advantage that the lepton momentum and pseudorapidity provide a good estimate for the equivalent properties of the misidentified particle. Then the fake factor can be measured as a function of these variables. This is more difficult for the fake origin, which cannot be determined easily and has an impact on the available fake processes. The dependence can be neglected if the signal and extraction region have the same composition of fake origin. Otherwise, both regions have systematically different fake efficiencies.

There are multiple ways to deal with the different properties of the misidentified particle. The easiest way is to choose a region in which the properties are similar to the signal region. Alternatively, efficiencies can be measured and applied separately for each source of fake leptons. This requires that additional subregions of tight and loose leptons be defined to target specific sources of fake leptons. Fake factors can be measured independently for these subregions. Another possibility is to trust Monte Carlo simulation to correct for this effect. Even though they do sometimes not predict fake rates accurately, it can be argued that the relative fake rate between processes is modelled better.

5.5.4 Lepton Selection Bias

The Fake Factor Method measures yields in a control selection and extrapolates into the signal selection based on fake factors. It is important that the signal and control selections, i.e. the loose and tight lepton definitions, are consistent throughout the entire procedure. This section considers cases in which the loose and tight selections are not identical.

Suppose that the fake factor is determined with the tight and loose selections as before. But the control selection in the signal region uses the tight selection and a medium selection, where the medium selection is in-between the tight and loose definitions. In this case, the lepton definitions are not consistent and cause biased results. This scenario can occur due to an inevitable additional selection or it could be a conscious design choice. In experiments, lepton triggers are often the reason for implicit event selections. This situation can specifically occur if lepton categories are looser than the trigger requirements, i.e. for leptons that do not pass the trigger threshold.

Consider an M -lepton event with a single-lepton trigger that is tighter than the loose lepton requirements. If the first lepton is triggered, the event will be recorded and there are no requirements on the other $M - 1$ leptons. If none of the $M - 1$ other leptons satisfy the single lepton trigger requirements, the first lepton has implicit requirements. If the first lepton were looser than the trigger requirements, then the event would not be recorded. Thus, by applying an event-level trigger selection, implicit requirements are set on the leptons.

The implicit requirement leads to a bias in the fake estimate. The following paragraphs outline the mathematical treatment of a fake estimate in a two-lepton selection with the described trigger setup. A similar approach can be taken for events with more than two leptons and for a similar selection bias that is not related to the trigger.

A lepton in category j , that passes the trigger selection, is displayed with the superscript T and a lepton failing this selection with the superscript !T. Because all leptons either pass or fail the trigger requirements, the number of events can be split up into the different combinations

$$N^{j_1, j_2} = N^{j_1^T, j_2^T} + N^{j_1^T, j_2^{!T}} + N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^T} + N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^{!T}}. \quad (5.38)$$

The rightmost term, where neither of the leptons satisfy the trigger requirements, is problematic. It cannot be determined directly from data, because these events are not recorded. But if the trigger efficiency ε^j is known for a lepton in category j , this term can be rewritten as

$$N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^{!T}} = (1 - \varepsilon^{j_1})(1 - \varepsilon^{j_2})N^{j_1, j_2}. \quad (5.39)$$

This assumes that the trigger efficiencies are independent, which is a reasonable assumption because lepton triggers typically only consider a limited detector region. This equation is

substituted in equation (5.38)

$$N^{j_1, j_2} = \frac{N^{j_1^T, j_2^T} + N^{j_1^T, j_2^{!T}} + N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^T}}{1 - ((1 - \varepsilon^{j_1})(1 - \varepsilon^{j_2}))}. \quad (5.40)$$

If the trigger efficiency for a given lepton category can be measured, then this equation can be used to correct the lepton selection bias. Effectively, all other event yields are reweighted to account for the one missing contribution.

In the case of M leptons, the equivalent of equation (5.40) is

$$N^{j_1, j_2, \dots, j_M} = \frac{\left(\sum_{s_1 \in \{T, !T\}} \sum_{s_2 \in \{T, !T\}} \dots \sum_{s_M \in \{T, !T\}} N^{j_1^{s_1}, j_2^{s_2}, \dots, j_M^{s_M}} \right) - N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^{!T}, \dots, j_M^{!T}}}{1 - \prod_{k=1}^M (1 - \varepsilon^{j_k})}, \quad (5.41)$$

where the sums iterate over the different trigger decisions T and !T of each lepton. This equation shows why the trigger bias becomes small for a large number of leptons. If multiple leptons have a non-negligible trigger efficiency, the denominator is close to one and the correction is small.

It is interesting to see that other equations for reweighting event yields are equally valid. Going back to the two-lepton example for simplicity, if one trigger efficiency, say ε^{j_1} , has large associated uncertainties, it can be beneficial to reweight only a part of the events. The definition of the trigger efficiency can be used

$$\frac{N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^{!T}}}{1 - \varepsilon^{j_2}} = N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2} = \frac{N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^T}}{\varepsilon^{j_2}}. \quad (5.42)$$

When combined with equation (5.38), it gives the result

$$N^{j_1, j_2} = N^{j_1^T, j_2^T} + N^{j_1^T, j_2^{!T}} + N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^T} + N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^T} \frac{1 - \varepsilon^{j_2}}{\varepsilon^{j_2}} \quad (5.43)$$

$$N^{j_1, j_2} = N^{j_1^T, j_2^T} + N^{j_1^T, j_2^{!T}} + \frac{N^{j_1^{!T}, j_2^T}}{\varepsilon^{j_2}}. \quad (5.44)$$

Compared to equation (5.40), this expression reweights a smaller number of events with a larger factor. Both approaches are equally valid, but the result will have different uncertainties depending on the input values. This illustrates that different corrections can be equally valid mathematically, but be more or less useful because of their associated uncertainties.

5.6 Fake Factor Equation as Estimator

In the previous sections, equations were derived that dictate how to combine efficiencies and event yields to determine the fake yield in a signal region. The derivation does not use approximations and derives exact equations both for the Matrix Method and Fake Factor

Method. Hence, the true fake yield can be calculated if the true event yields in the other regions are known.

The true yields, however, are not known in an experiment. A measured event yield will have statistical uncertainties. And even if statistical uncertainties are small, there could be systematic uncertainties spoiling the measurements. From a statistical point of view, the yield measurements are random variables drawn from a distribution defined by the true, underlying variables. Because of these random inputs, the derived equations are in practice used as estimators for the true fake yield in the signal region. It is therefore justified to ask how suitable these estimators are.

Even though the true values of the fake yields are unknown, the types of probability distributions from which they are sampled are known. All measurements in data follow a Poisson distribution, the binomial distribution in the limit of many trials and a small success probability. In a collider experiment, this translates to a large number of collisions and a small fraction of events with the selected signature. The yields of real-lepton backgrounds are taken from Monte-Carlo simulation and follow a Gaussian distribution. The reason is that Monte-Carlo generators typically assign a weight w_i to every generated event i and the sum of these weights is taken as the yield estimate. Independently of the distribution of weights w_i , their sum is Gaussian distributed in the limit of a large number of generated events according to the central-limit theorem. This knowledge about the qualitative shape of the involved probability distributions proves useful throughout the rest of this section.

This section will shed light on the Fake Factor equation viewed as an estimator. The goal is to highlight some configurations in which the Fake Factor equation gives better results than in others. This information can be useful when designing an analysis. At first, a framework to generate pseudo experiments is introduced and its scope is discussed. These pseudo experiments are used to understand properties of the Fake Factor equation, for instance the bias in section 5.6.3. Section 5.6.5 talks about uncertainty estimates on the fake yield and suggests a method to quantify how well a given procedure to calculate uncertainties performs. Lastly, other possible approaches to incorporating the fake estimate in an encompassing analysis are briefly mentioned.

5.6.1 Pseudo Experiments with faketoys

To understand the behaviour of the Fake Factor equation better, it is instructive to generate random variables from the relevant distributions and apply the estimator to them. If this is done to an ensemble of random variables, the ensemble of resulting estimates can reveal properties of the estimator. This procedure is often described as generating *pseudo experiments* or *toy experiments* in high-energy physics or as *bootstrapping* [172] in the field of statistics.

To generate pseudo experiments, a small python framework, `faketoys`, has been written to draw random numbers from different probability distributions and combine them. The name `faketoys` implies that the toy experiments are specifically designed to estimate fake

Term	Distribution	Mean	Std. dev.
N^t	Poisson	400	—
N_r^t	Gauss	200	10
N^l	Poisson	4900	—
N_r^l	Gauss	900	200
N^l	Poisson	900	—
N_r^l	Gauss	400	40

Table 5.1: Example parameters defining probability distributions for the inputs of the one-lepton Fake Factor equation shown in Figure 5.2. The Poisson distributions follow the form $f_P(k) = \frac{\lambda^k e^{-\lambda}}{k!}$, where λ is the mean of the distribution. The Gaussian distributions are given by $f_G(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-\mu)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right)$, where μ indicates the mean and σ the standard deviation.

yields. But the layout is more general and can easily be extended to simulate custom equations. The code can be found following Ref. [173].

To test the simulation and to give a qualitative display of the results, suppose that the true values of the fake processes are known. Table 5.1 shows the parameters of sample distributions. The probability distributions are chosen as Poisson and Gaussian distributions as argued above. They are used as input to the one-lepton Fake Factor equation (5.11) after substituting the fake factor from equation (5.37)

$$N_f^t = \frac{N^t - N_r^t}{N^l - N_r^l} (N^l - N_r^l). \quad (5.45)$$

In an analysis, the terms coming from the fake factor are derived in a different region (primed terms) than the signal region (unprimed terms).

The result of 10^6 pseudo experiments generated with these values are shown as a histogram in Figure 5.2. It displays how frequently an experimental fake estimate occurs, given the underlying probability distributions. The mean and median of the distribution deviate from the true value in opposite directions. The mean is shifted further away from the true value than its uncertainty, which indicates a bias. This effect is discussed in section 5.6.3. How this histogram can be used to estimate an uncertainty is shortly addressed in section 5.6.4, while section 5.6.5 focusses on the validation of an existing uncertainty estimate.

The figures that are based on pseudo experiments and are shown in this section can be reproduced following the documentation in Ref. [174].

5.6.2 Consistency

A property of estimators is consistency⁵. An estimator \hat{a} that depends on the random variables x_1, \dots, x_n is consistent if $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \hat{a}(x_1, \dots, x_n) \rightarrow a$, where a is the true value. Loosely

⁵The definition of *consistency* (also *bias* in the next section) can be found in textbooks like [175] or [176].

Figure 5.2: Fake factor estimate for 10^6 pseudo experiments generated with the distributions in Table 5.1. The histogram in the main panel shows how often a particular fake factor estimate occurs. The top panel shares its axis with the bottom panel. It shows the mean of the distribution $\mu = 25.068 \pm 0.004$, the median 24.86, the true fake yield of 25 events and the mean with the standard deviation $\sigma = 4.00$.

speaking, consistency means that the estimate converges to the true value when approaching an infinite number of measurements.

To see if the Fake Factor equation is consistent, first consider measurements of an event yield. Let n be the number of particle collisions and the variable $x_i = 1$ if the event i has a certain signature of interest and $x_i = 0$ otherwise. The sum $\hat{N} = \sum x_i$ is an estimator for the true yield N with the signature of interest. It is evident that any fundamental, physical quantity is independent of the number of recorded collisions n . Therefore, all reasonable estimators of physical quantities should be independent of n . This is accomplished by dividing the estimated yield by the integrated luminosity L (cf. equation (3.2)), which is proportional to n and therefore also to N . Hence, when talking about the consistency of the a yield measurement, the relevant estimator has the form \hat{N}/L .

The standard deviation of the yield measurement is $\sigma_{\hat{N}} = \sqrt{N}$. After dividing by the integrated luminosity it is $\sigma_{\hat{N}/L} \propto \frac{1}{\sqrt{N}}$, which converges to 0 for a large number of collected events. Since the standard deviation of \hat{N}/L converges to 0, then \hat{N}/L also converges. Suppose now that the expectation value of \hat{N} is equal to the true value N , which is written as $\langle \hat{N} \rangle = N$ and will be shown in section 5.6.3. This implies that the estimator \hat{N}/L converges to N/L and is therefore consistent. This reasoning applies to all terms entering the Fake Factor equation, which can be viewed as estimators themselves for the underlying true value.

To relate this insight to the Fake Factor equation, consider the continuous mapping theorem [177]. It states that if a sequence of random variables y_i converges to a value y , then the continuous function $f(y_i)$ converges to $f(y)$ [178]. Since all input estimators of the Fake Factor equation are consistent and therefore converge to the true value, the result of the Fake Factor equation also converges to its true value. Because the Fake Factor equation is exact, it estimates the fake yield consistently. This makes the implicit assumption that no systematic uncertainties are present, which could make the underlying estimators inconsistent.

5.6.3 Bias

Another property of estimators is bias. The estimator \hat{a} of the true value a has a bias b defined as

$$b(\hat{a}) = \langle \hat{a} \rangle - a, \quad (5.46)$$

where the angle brackets $\langle \hat{a} \rangle$ indicate the expectation value. This concept can be applied to the measurement of event yields from data following a Poisson distribution. If a true yield is given by N and its estimator \hat{N} is taken as the number of observed events, then the bias is

$$b = \langle \hat{N} \rangle - N = \left(\sum_{\hat{N}=0}^{\infty} \hat{N} f_P(\hat{N}, N) \right) - N \quad (5.47)$$

$$= \left(\sum_{\hat{N}=0}^{\infty} \hat{N} \frac{N^{\hat{N}}}{\hat{N}!} e^{-N} \right) - N \quad (5.48)$$

$$= \left(e^{-N} N \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{N^k}{k!} \right) - N \quad \text{with } k = \hat{N} - 1 \quad (5.49)$$

$$= 0, \quad (5.50)$$

where $f_P(\hat{N}, N) = N^{\hat{N}} e^{-N} / \hat{N}!$ is the Poisson probability distribution for measuring \hat{N} when the true value is N . This estimator is called *unbiased*, because its bias is $b = 0$.

To understand the bias of the Fake Factor equation, it is instructive to combine the unbiased inputs step by step and to see if the result is also unbiased. The different operations in equation (5.34) are addition, multiplication and division. If the random variables x and y are added, their bias also adds, because the expectation value is linear $\langle x + y \rangle = \langle x \rangle + \langle y \rangle$ and thus $b(x + y) = b(x) + b(y)$. For the multiplication of two random variables, the bias depends on whether x and y are independent. If they are, then the joint probability factorizes $p(x \wedge y) = p(x)p(y)$. In this case, also the expectation value factorizes $\langle xy \rangle = \langle x \rangle \langle y \rangle$ and the result is unbiased. The condition of independence is satisfied in an experiment if there is no systematic uncertainty affecting both variables x and y .

The division operation can be broken down into multiplication, which was considered above and does not cause a bias, and taking the inverse. Using as an example a simple probability distribution $f(x) = \frac{1}{2}(\delta(x - 1) + \delta(x - 2))$ shows that the expectation value of

Term	Distribution	Mean	Std. dev.
N^t	Poisson	125	—
N_r^t	Gauss	75	10
N^l	Poisson	{200, 250, 300, 400, 500, 600, 800, 1000}	—
N_r^l	Gauss	{0, 25, 50, 75, 100}	10
N^l	Poisson	9	—
N_r^l	Gauss	1	0

Table 5.2: Probability distributions for the inputs of the one-lepton Fake Factor equation used to generate Figure 5.3. All combinations of terms in the denominator N^l and N_r^l are generated.

the inverse is not in general equal to the inverse of the expectation value $\langle \frac{1}{x} \rangle = \frac{3}{4} \neq \frac{2}{3} = \frac{1}{\langle x \rangle}$. This also follows from Jensen’s inequality [179], which states that $\phi(\langle x \rangle) < \langle \phi(x) \rangle$ for a strictly convex function ϕ . If values with $x > 0$ are considered, the function $\phi = \frac{1}{x}$ is strictly convex and therefore $\langle \frac{1}{x} \rangle > \frac{1}{\langle x \rangle}$. It follows that the bias of the inverse is $b(\frac{1}{x}) = \langle \frac{1}{x} \rangle - \frac{1}{\langle x \rangle} > 0$.

In conclusion, if its inputs are independent and the denominators are greater than 0, the Fake Factor equation has a positive bias that is introduced by the division. To confirm this prediction, pseudo experiments are performed and analyzed for bias. Because the terms contributing to the Fake Factor equation are similar and for simplicity, the one-lepton Fake Factor equation as written in equation (5.45) is considered here.

To use this equation as an estimator for N_f^t , true values and corresponding probability distributions need to be assigned to the terms on the right-hand side. The distributions for this example are summarized in Table 5.2. The true values are equal to the means so that the inputs are unbiased. Since the denominator is expected to introduce a bias, configurations with different denominator distributions are generated.

The specific true values are chosen to reflect a conceivable scenario of an analysis with small fake yields in the signal region and a looser selection for the fake factor measurement. The possible fake factors range between 0.05 and 0.5. The terms in the denominator are intentionally chosen small enough to expose a bias. But they are large enough to avoid that the denominator in individual pseudo-experiments approaches zero, which would skew the distribution to unreasonably large values.

In fact, this last point deserves some more reflection. From a purely mathematical standpoint, the probability density is non-zero when the denominator vanishes, which prompts the question whether the integral in $\langle \frac{1}{x} \rangle$ is finite. This is the case, because the probability density is smooth around 0 and can be written as a Taylor approximation $p(x) \approx p(0) + \frac{dp(0)}{dx}x$. Therefore, the integral around $x = 0$ vanishes

$$\lim_{a \rightarrow 0} \int_{-a}^{+a} \frac{1}{x} p(x) dx \approx \lim_{a \rightarrow 0} \int_{-a}^{+a} \left(\frac{1}{x} p(0) + \frac{dp(0)}{dx} x \right) dx = 0.$$

Figure 5.3: Relative bias in the Fake Factor estimator. For each configuration from Table 5.2, $5 \cdot 10^6$ pseudo events are generated. The relative bias is calculated by dividing the bias by the true value. The uncertainties on the y-axis are the propagated standard deviation the mean. Datapoints are connected by lines to highlight the trend.

From an experimental point of view, however, denominators close to 0 or even at negative values would be rejected as unphysical. If this situation occurs when analyzing experimental data, the inputs would be scrutinized for mistakes, other estimates for the term N_r^l would be considered or an entirely different method would be chosen to estimate the fake yield. While this is a reasonable reaction when faced with estimates that correspond to unphysical configurations⁶, this approach constitutes another source of bias. In order to reflect this in the simulation, a requirement is imposed that denominators be greater than a minimum value. In the pseudo experiments here, the condition is $N^l - N_r^l > 1$. Compared to an experimental analysis, this condition is deliberately quite unrestrictive to not enhance the bias artificially.

Figure 5.3 shows the relative bias, i.e. the bias divided by the true value, after simulating $5 \cdot 10^6$ pseudo experiments for each configuration in Table 5.2. It is apparent that the bias grows as N^l decreases and N_r^l increases, both of which correspond to a shrinking denominator. Even for configurations with hundreds of measured events, a bias in the single-digit percent range is still possible. The positivity of the bias implies that the mean of many measurements will lie above the true value, causing an overestimate on average like predicted by Jensen's inequality.

⁶This also explains why the assumption $x > 0$ was made when applying Jensen's inequality.

In an actual experiment, the true values of the variables are not known. It is therefore impossible to simulate the bias and to correct for it, which would require knowledge of the true values. But a simulation, in which the true values are assumed to be equal or similar to the measured values, can help to estimate the systematic uncertainties that a bias can cause in a given configuration. The other lesson from this section is that the bias will be small if the denominator is large enough, which is a practical guideline for designing a fake factor estimate.

5.6.4 Bootstrapping

Before discussing the uncertainty estimate, the basics of the *bootstrapping method* [180], are reviewed. It relies on two basic ideas [172]. Firstly, the unknown probability distribution, from which the data is drawn, is replaced by an estimate based on the observed values. The maximum likelihood method is often used for this inference step. In the case of the Fake Factor equation, the type of the probability distributions is known so that the measured event yields are used to estimate the mean of the probability distributions. This procedure is called the *substitution principle* or *plug-in rule*. Secondly, the data is *resampled* many times from the estimated probability distributions.

The bootstrapping method is often used to determine confidence intervals of a point estimate. Resampling the data from the probability distributions gives many point estimates, from which confidence intervals can be derived [181]. This assumes, however, that the observed data is close enough to the true values so that the substitution principle does not affect the confidence levels significantly. This might be a good approximation in cases with many measurements, but it is not obvious that this is the case for the Fake Factor equation, if the measured yields are small.

As an example, consider a Gaussian distributions with mean $\mu = 100$ and standard deviation $\sigma = 0.1\mu$. Suppose that a random measurement is drawn and gives a down fluctuation to $x = 90$. Then, an uncertainty estimate with the substitution principle would give an uncertainty of $\sigma_{x-} = 9$. If on the other hand an up fluctuation is observed to $x = 110$, the uncertainty estimate would be $\sigma_{x+} = 11$. This results in an asymmetry of the uncertainties even though the initial configuration is symmetric. This effectively means that positive uncertainties are underestimated and negative uncertainties overestimated. A similar effect also occurs in the fake factor estimate as shown in the following section.

5.6.5 Uncertainty Estimate

Instead of following the bootstrapping approach to estimating confidence intervals, this section uses linear error propagation with a Gaussian shape to estimate uncertainties. Pseudo experiments are then used to assess how well this procedure performs to estimate uncertainties. The same approach could in principle also be applied to the bootstrapping method and it would be interesting to compare the uncertainty estimates. These studies were not performed in the interest of time.

In Frequentist statistics, uncertainties on a measurement x_m are specified as confidence intervals $[x_1, x_2]$ with confidence level $\gamma \in [0, 1]$. A confidence interval [175] is a range of parameters intended to satisfy the following statement: if a measurement to estimate a true value is repeated very often and confidence intervals are constructed for each measurement, a fraction γ of confidence intervals contains the true value.

When using linear error propagation to construct an uncertainty estimate, often a functional form $m(x)$ is derived as an uncertainty distribution. In order to interpret how well the uncertainty distribution performs, one can construct confidence intervals from it and assess to which degree the requirement on confidence levels above is satisfied. Treating $m(x)$ like a probability distribution, it is sensible to choose x_1 and x_2 by requiring that

$$\int_{x_1}^{x_2} m(x) dx = \gamma. \quad (5.51)$$

If the same method is used to construct confidence intervals for N pseudo experiments, γN of these confidence intervals should contain the true value. By comparing this expectation to the outcome in pseudo experiments, the performance of linear error propagation can be evaluated.

To assess the full shape of the uncertainty distribution, this test can be generalized to arbitrary confidence levels. For a given true value x_t , N different experiments are generated as an estimate for x_t . For each experiment i , an uncertainty distribution $m^i(x)$ is derived using linear error propagation. Let $p_1, p_2 \in [0, 1]$ be any values that satisfy $p_1 \leq p_2$ and let the equations

$$p_1 = \int_{-\infty}^{x_1^i} m^i(x) dx \quad \text{and} \quad p_2 = \int_{-\infty}^{x_2^i} m^i(x) dx, \quad (5.52)$$

define the variables x_1^i, x_2^i for each experiment. Then, for a good uncertainty estimate, the fraction of experiments i satisfying $x_1^i \leq x_t \leq x_2^i$ should be equal to $p_2 - p_1$ as $N \rightarrow \infty$. This can also be expressed as a probability $P(\cdot)$ defined on the ensemble of simulations i

$$P(x_1 \leq x_t \leq x_2) = p_2 - p_1 = \int_{x_1}^{x_2} m(x) dx. \quad (5.53)$$

The postulate above specifies a criterion for a good uncertainty distribution $m(x)$. It is chosen with the intention to reproduce Frequentist confidence intervals. For instance, to get a central confidence interval, where the probabilities below and above the integral are equal [175], with confidence level γ , the equations (5.52) can be used together with $p_1 = \frac{1-\gamma}{2}$, $p_2 = \frac{1+\gamma}{2}$ to define the interval $[x_1, x_2]$. Then equation (5.53) shows that $P(x_1 \leq x_t \leq x_2) = p_2 - p_1 = \gamma$. Thus, the quality criteria for the uncertainty distribution $m(x)$ chosen above reduce to Frequentist confidence intervals for specific values p_1, p_2 .

Figure 5.4: Sketch of the derivation of fake uncertainties. The true probability distribution characterizes the statistical uncertainty about the true value x_t in the measurement. For a given measurement x_m , an uncertainty distribution is derived. In pseudo experiments, the integral $p(x_t)$ can be used to estimate how well the uncertainty derivation performs on the true probability distribution.

Since the true value needs to be known, such an assessment cannot be performed in real data, but it can be in simulated pseudo experiments. To derive a more tangible signature of a good uncertainty estimate, the notation above is generalized to

$$p(x) = \int_{-\infty}^x m(x') dx'. \quad (5.54)$$

Since the function $p(x)$ is monotonic, the statement $x_1 \leq x_t \leq x_2$ is equivalent to $p(x_1) \leq p(x_t) \leq p(x_2)$. If $p(x_1) = 0$ is chosen, it follows directly that

$$P(x_1 \leq x_t \leq x_2) = P(-\infty \leq p(x_t) \leq p(x_2)) = P(p(x_t) \leq p(x_2)) = p(x_2). \quad (5.55)$$

This equation implies that $p(x_t)$ is uniformly distributed⁷ in the range $[0, 1]$ on the ensemble of simulations i . Note that this is not a probabilistic statement about x_t , which is fixed in all pseudo experiments, but rather about the ensemble of distributions $m^i(x)$. The uniformity of the variable $p(x_t)$ across pseudo experiments can easily be checked and serves as a measure for the quality of the uncertainty estimate.

⁷This conclusion is more apparent when rewriting the equation in simple variables. Consider the random variable $X \in [0, 1]$ that is drawn from a probability density $\rho(x)$. The equivalent of equation (5.55) is $P(X \leq y) = y$ for any $y \in [0, 1]$. This statement can be expressed with the probability density as $\int_0^y \rho(x) dx = y$, which is satisfied for a uniform $\rho(x) = 1$.

Term	Distribution	Mean	Std. dev.
N^{tt}	Poisson	500	—
N_r^{tt}	Gauss	0	5
N^{ll}	Poisson	500000	—
N_r^{ll}	Gauss	0	40
N^l	Poisson	10625	—
N_r^l	Gauss	0	625

Table 5.3: Probability distributions for the inputs of the one-lepton Fake Factor equation to estimate the quality of the uncertainty estimate in Figures 5.5 and 5.6. It also describes one of the configurations in Figure 5.7. The real-lepton subtraction is set to 0 to reduce the number of independent input parameters. These terms have a subordinate effect on the result.

Figure 5.4 illustrates how this process works in a single pseudo experiment. The purple, dashed line indicates the true value x_t and the purple function indicates the true probability distribution $t(x)$ from which measurements are drawn. The green, dashed line represents a random measurement x_m that exhibits an up fluctuation in this example. Based on the measurement x_m , the green uncertainty distribution $m(x)$ is constructed. In a real experiment, this uncertainty distribution would be taken as the uncertainty on the fake estimate.

To get a measure for the quality of $m(x)$, the integral $p(x_t)$ is calculated, which requires knowledge of the true value. This entire process is repeated for many measurements and the values $p^i(x_t)$ are plotted as a histogram. A flat distribution indicates that the method to estimate uncertainties gives results that are compatible with the idea of Frequentist confidence intervals.

To visualize how this method works, $5 \cdot 10^5$ pseudo experiments are generated from the example in Table 5.3. For simplicity, all terms constituting real-lepton subtractions are set to 0, because their uncertainty is parametrized separately. The distribution of values $p(x_t)$ is shown in Figure 5.5. It deviates from the ideal, uniform distribution at low and high values of $p(x_t)$, which indicates a mismatch at extreme measured values between the uncertainty estimate and the true value.

To visualize this further, a 2-dimensional scatter plot of this distribution and the fake estimate is shown in Figure 5.6. It reveals that there is a strong correlation between the two variables. This correlation is expected, because $p(x_t)$ depends on the measured value x_m as explained in Figure 5.4. The correlation is not perfect, because different random values in the underlying distributions can produce the same fake estimate x_m with a different uncertainty estimate. The scatter plot also confirms the speculation from above. When small fake estimates are measured, the uncertainty is underestimated, causing a peak in the distribution of $p(x_t)$. The opposite effect appears on the other side of the spectrum. Large fake estimates overestimate the uncertainty and therefore values close to 0 occur less frequently.

Figure 5.5: Distribution of values $p(x_t)$ for pseudo experiments generated from Table 5.3. Values around 0 correspond to configurations where the true value lies in the lower range of the uncertainty distribution. Similarly, values around 1 are generated by experiments, where the true value is in the high end of the uncertainty distribution. The dashed line indicates the expected yield for a uniform histogram. Figure 5.6 shows how the values $p(x_t)$ are related to the measured value.

To compare uncertainty estimates for different true values, it is helpful to quantify the deviation from the uniform expectation in Figure 5.5. With N generated events and n bins, a flat distribution has $\lambda = N/n$ events in each bin j . A straightforward figure of merit is the standard deviation σ of the bin contents away from λ . It can be defined as

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (C_j - \lambda)^2}, \quad (5.56)$$

where the number of events in a histogram bin j are denoted by C_j . A large value indicates a mismatch between the histogram and the uniform expectation. But even if C_j are drawn from a uniform distribution, σ still has a non-zero expectation value due to statistical fluctuations. In each bin, the number of entries follows a binomial distribution with a success rate of n^{-1} and total number of trials N . Therefore, the expectation value of the standard deviation σ can be calculated with

$$\langle \sigma_{\text{uniform}} \rangle \approx \sqrt{\left\langle \sum_{j=1}^n (C_j - \lambda)^2 \right\rangle} \approx \sqrt{n \langle (C - \lambda)^2 \rangle} = \sqrt{N \left(1 - \frac{1}{n}\right)}, \quad (5.57)$$

Figure 5.6: Correlation between the fake estimate and the integral $p(x_t)$ for pseudo experiments generated from Table 5.3.

where the variance for the binomial distribution $\langle (C - \lambda)^2 \rangle = \frac{N}{n} (1 - \frac{1}{n})$ is used in the last step⁸. In the previous example, the values are $\frac{\sigma}{n} \approx 81$ and $\frac{\langle \sigma_{\text{uniform}} \rangle}{n} = 14$ revealing the non-uniformity of the distribution.

With this method of quantifying the uniformity as a proxy for the quality of the uncertainty estimate, different true values can be compared. The configuration in Table 5.3 is extended in two dimensions with the values $N^l \in \{625, 1875, 3125, \dots, 24375\}$ and $\sigma_{N_r^l} \in \{25, 75, 125, \dots, 975\}$. For each of these configurations, a histogram like in Figure 5.5 is generated and the deviation from the uniform distribution σ determined. Figure 5.7 displays a 2-dimensional histogram of the variable $\frac{\sigma}{n}$ for each configuration and reveals an interesting pattern with three distinct features.

Looking at small values N^l , the accuracy of the uncertainty estimate improves as the uncertainty of N_r^l grows. Similarly, for small values of $\sigma_{N_r^l}$, the accuracy of the uncertainty estimate improves as N^l and simultaneously its uncertainty increase. The configurations on

⁸Two assumptions are made implicitly in this derivation. Firstly, the number of events in each bin is much larger than the uncertainty. Therefore, the expectation value and the square root can be swapped. Secondly, the number of bins is large. Then, the individual bins are uncorrelated and can be treated independently. The validity of this result is also confirmed by simulation.

Figure 5.7: Proxy for the quality of an uncertainty estimate for different configurations of the Fake Factor equation. Larger values of $\frac{\sigma}{n}$ correspond to a worse uncertainty estimate. A characteristic, diagonal band shows a suboptimal uncertainty estimate, which arises because relative uncertainties of similar size are multiplied. The blue line indicates the prediction for the configurations with the worst uncertainty estimate based on the condition that the relative uncertainties of the two numerator multiplicands are equal. The prediction agrees well with the simulation.

the diagonal exhibit a worse uncertainty estimate compared to the configurations away from the diagonal. Note that the previous example in Figure 5.5 was taken from this diagonal band.

To understand these three effects, it helps to inspect equation (5.45) and its input distributions in Table 5.3 closely. Because of the relatively large true values N^t , N^l and N^r , the associated Poisson distributions are approximately Gaussian. Hence, the three pairs of Poisson and Gaussian distributions also follow a Gaussian distribution. For easier identification, call these terms a , b , c

$$N_f^t = \frac{N^t - N_r^t}{N^l - N_r^l} (N^l - N_r^l) = \frac{a}{c} b. \quad (5.58)$$

The denominator has a small relative uncertainty $\sigma_c \approx 0.001$ compared to $\sigma_a \approx 0.05$. Hence, it is reasonable to assume that it has subordinate influence on the uncertainty estimate. In the multiplication ab , consider the case that the relative uncertainties are related by $\sigma_a^{\text{rel}} \gg \sigma_b^{\text{rel}}$. Then b effectively acts as a factor without uncertainty. This would result in a Gaussian uncertainty $\sigma_{ab} \approx b\sigma_a$ and give a small value of σ . By symmetry, the same argument holds for the case $\sigma_a^{\text{rel}} \ll \sigma_b^{\text{rel}}$. In all combinations in Figure 5.7, σ_a^{rel} is fixed,

whereas

$$\sigma_b^{\text{rel}} = \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_{N^l}^2 + \sigma_{N_r^l}^2}}{N^l - N_r^l} \quad (5.59)$$

$$= \frac{1}{\sqrt{N^l}} + \frac{\sigma_{N_r^l}}{N^l}, \quad (5.60)$$

using $\sigma_{N^l} = \sqrt{N^l}$ for a Poisson distribution. The second line of the equation sets $N_r^l = 0$ for the specific example considered here. This line shows that configurations in the bottom right of Figure 5.7 belong to the case $\sigma_a^{\text{rel}} \ll \sigma_b^{\text{rel}}$ and configurations in the top left reproduce the case $\sigma_a^{\text{rel}} \gg \sigma_b^{\text{rel}}$. The uncertainty estimate is relatively precise in both cases.

When the uncertainties are equal $\sigma_a^{\text{rel}} = \sigma_b^{\text{rel}}$, on the other hand, the multiplication of a and b distorts the shape of the distribution and the estimate is not well-represented by a Gaussian distribution. From this condition, the following expression can be derived⁹ using equation (5.59)

$$N^l = N_r^l + A \pm \sqrt{(N_r^l + A)^2 - N_r^{l2} + 2A\sigma_{N_r^l}^2} \quad (5.61)$$

$$\text{with } A = \frac{(N^{lt} - N_r^{lt})^2}{2(N^{lt} + \sigma_{N_r^{lt}}^2)}, \quad (5.62)$$

which simplifies for the input values of the current simulation in the first four lines of Table 5.3 to

$$N^l = A \pm \sqrt{A^2 + 2A\sigma_{N_r^l}^2} \approx A \pm \sqrt{2A} \sigma_{N_r^l} \quad \text{with } \sqrt{A} \approx 15. \quad (5.63)$$

The last approximation is valid for $\sigma_{N_r^l} \gg \sqrt{A}$, which is the case for all but the leftmost configurations in Figure 5.7. The positive solution of the equation is overlaid and shows good agreement with the simulation. It explains the origin of the diagonal pattern in the plot indicating a suboptimal uncertainty estimate. The negative solution is irrelevant, because it describes unphysical configurations with $N^l < N_r^l$.

5.6.6 Fakes in the Encompassing Analysis

A fake estimate is typically performed as part of a bigger measurement that views fake processes as contamination. In these cases, the impact of the fake contribution on the figure of merit is assessed in a statistical analysis. In a search for a new particle, for example, the agreement of data with the background-only hypothesis is determined. If disagreement is observed, the statistical analysis tries to answer how likely is it that such extreme results are observed, if a new particle does not exist. If such an analysis contains a fake process, the uncertainties associated with large deviations from the nominal fake estimate are relevant.

⁹See Appendix B.2 for the derivation.

This implies that it is not sufficient to estimate the uncertainty around the most likely value, but also the tails of the distribution need to be described accurately.

Whatever the case may be, different analyses may have different requirements for a fake estimate. Instead of estimating the uncertainty explicitly, it is, for instance, conceivable that the fake estimate is fully incorporated into the statistical analysis. This could be done as part of a maximum likelihood method by including all measurements that enter the Fake Factor equation in the definition of the likelihood. Alternatively, to reduce the number of nuisance parameters, the fake factors could be estimated and integrated into the likelihood. This way, the maximum likelihood method could directly use and constrain the uncertainties of fake factors.

Similar proposals have been made in the context of the Matrix Method. Ref. [182] advocates the maximum likelihood method, where lepton efficiencies are estimated in different categories. The authors find that this method performs significantly better especially with small predicted fake yields. Ref. [166] suggests a similar approach that is also based on a maximum likelihood fit and Ref. [183] reformulates the matrix method with Bayesian reasoning.

Chapter 6

Fake Factor Measurement

In the theoretical description of the Fake Factor Method , one short paragraph was devoted to the measurement of fake factors at the end of section 5.5. What looks straightforward in theory and what is expressed concisely in equation (5.37) turns into a miniature analysis by itself, to which this chapter is devoted. The results, namely the fake factors and their uncertainties, are used in chapter 7 to estimate the contribution of fake events in the signal region of the HWW analysis. The measurement of the fake factors needs to be guided by decisions in the main analysis. The tight and loose lepton selections are even strictly dictated by the main analysis. Therefore, this section contains a few forward references to the HWW analysis, but the method is in principle independent of the main analysis.

Similar versions of this fake measurement have been performed before on a smaller dataset. Descriptions can for example be found in Refs. [118, 184]. The focus of this chapter is on the measurement in a Z +fake region, where the Z boson serves as a tagging object. A similar derivation in a jet+fake region is used for a smaller subset of events, but it is of subordinate relevance. For both cases, the event selection and the extraction of fake factors are shown. For the analysis of Z +fake events, also systematic uncertainties are derived.

6.1 Choice of Extraction Region

A basic question when designing a fake estimate is how to treat different origins of fake leptons. In principle, each source of fake lepton background can have different fake efficiencies. One method is to estimate all sources of fake leptons separately by constructing control regions purified for each fake origin. While this is a straightforward approach, it is cumbersome in practice because of the many different regions and estimates.

Instead, the HWW analysis is designed to combine fake leptons from all sources and to estimate their contribution simultaneously. Only one fake factor needs to be estimated, which simplifies the procedure¹. The disadvantage is, however, that the composition of the

¹However, to complicate the situation, this fake factor will be split depending on other variables as explained below.

fake origin can vary. To account for this, systematic uncertainties need to be assigned. This was done similarly in the previous HWW analysis [185], where the composition uncertainty on the fake factor was dominant for low- p_T leptons. For the sake of simplicity and in the light of other uncertainties of comparable impact, this drawback can be tolerated.

The only fake process that is not estimated with this method is from photon conversions. Their impact on the HWW analysis is small, because of the tight object selection. Therefore, they are estimated from MC simulation. Thus, the discussion in the remainder of this chapter does not apply to converted photons.

To take into account the dependence of fake efficiencies on the transverse momentum p_T , pseudo rapidity η and flavour (e, μ) of the fake lepton, the fake factor is measured as a function of these three variables. This means effectively that a separate fake estimate is performed for each combination of fake p_T , η and flavour. Ideally, the kinematic variables should be used of the object that is being misidentified (eg. the jet). However, the corresponding variables of the reconstructed fake lepton take similar values and are used instead to simplify the procedure.

Equation (5.37) prescribes how to calculate the fake factor. Upon inspection it becomes clear that a region enriched in fake leptons is advantageous for the estimate. Such a region has large yields from data in the numerator and denominator. Only few events contain exclusively real leptons and need to be subtracted, which keeps uncertainties small.

Since events are only recorded if they exhibit a distinguishing feature that is recognized by an event trigger, two approaches are conceivable. The first approach is to use the fake lepton itself in the event trigger. In this case, one typically targets events produced by the strong interaction with a signature of two jets in the detector. If one of them is misidentified as a lepton, a single-lepton trigger can collect the event (jet+fake). It is important that the trigger criteria are less strict than the tight and loose lepton criteria defined in the analysis. Otherwise a systematic bias would be included in the fake factors as described in section 5.5.4.

At ATLAS, unprescaled triggers² cannot collect an unbiased single-lepton sample at small p_T that is compatible with the identification criteria of the HWW analysis [186, 187]. While prescaled triggers only collect a subset of the data matching its criteria, the abundance of events with a dijet signature compensates this sufficiently. Furthermore, the prescaling is chosen such that only a small fraction of events are collected at small p_T , but a larger fraction at higher p_T , where fakes occur less frequently. This way, multiple prescaled triggers can be combined to achieve large sample sizes across a wide range of p_T . One intricacy is that the fake factors need to be binned in accordance with the p_T ranges in which the same prescale is applied.

²Unprescaled triggers record all data events satisfying the trigger criteria. A prescaled trigger with a prescale x only records a random subset of events satisfying its criteria, on average every x -th event.

The second possible approach is to trigger on a feature other than the fake lepton. A typical process is Z +jets, where the Z boson decays to two leptons and where one additional jet is misidentified as a lepton (Z +fake³). These events can be collected with a single-lepton or a dilepton trigger. To ensure that the selection of fakes is not biased in any way, only events are considered that would have been recorded even if the fake lepton had not been present. Because the fake lepton is not used by the event trigger, even unrescaled triggers collect an unbiased sample of fake leptons.

The disadvantage of this method, however, is that Z bosons are produced rarely compared to dijet events (cf. Figure 2.5), resulting in a smaller number of relevant events. On the other hand, the p_T spectrum of Z +jets is more similar to the corresponding W +jets spectrum, the main fake process in the HWW signal region. The similarity in the p_T spectrum ensures that the fake factor estimate has the highest sensitivity, where it is needed. Moreover, one would intuitively expect that the source of the fake lepton between Z +jets and W +jets agrees better than between dijets and W +jets⁴, because electroweak processes are involved in both cases. Moreover, the presence of tagging leptons in the Z +jets process makes it easy to measure fake factors at small transverse momenta, because no implicit trigger requirements are applied to the additional lepton.

Taking these pros and cons into consideration, a fake factor estimated in Z +jets events is used in the HWW analysis. The composition of fake origin played a role in this decision and the fact that the HWW analysis is mostly sensitive to low- p_T leptons, which have a small statistical uncertainty in Z +jets events.

6.2 Fake Leptons in Events with a Z Boson

Before the fake factor can be determined, an analysis region has to be defined that is sufficiently pure in Z +fake. The backgrounds are estimated with the MC samples listed in section 4.3. Specifically, the samples are used that have the entry Z +fake in the last column of Table 4.2. The next sections outline the event selection before the fake factors are extracted and sources of systematic uncertainties are discussed.

6.2.1 Event Selection

With the goal to construct a region that is pure enough to determine fake factors precisely, Z +fake events are selected. The influence of all requirements on simulation and data is reflected in Table 6.2.

³This section uses the terms “ Z +fake” and “ Z +jets” somewhat interchangeably. Z +fake describes the detector signature, while Z +jets more accurately describes the physics process.

⁴A more detailed analysis of the fake origin shows that this is not necessarily the case. The occurring flavours show some distinct differences between Z +jets and W +jets as discussed in section 6.2.6.

Figure 6.1: Distributions of the invariant mass of the reconstructed Z -boson candidate after identification of the Z boson (left) and after the cut on the transverse mass of the W boson (right). The stacked histograms are background MC processes not including Z +fake. The measured data is shown in black datapoints and the blue datapoints are the data-driven Z +fake estimate. They are calculated by taking the difference between data and the stacked MC processes. They can be compared to the green Z +jets MC, which is not stacked on top of the other MC processes.

Events with exactly three reconstructed leptons are considered and all three leptons are required to have a transverse momentum of $p_T > 15$ GeV. Any pair of leptons qualifies as a Z -boson candidate if it satisfies the following requirements. The leptons are of same flavour and opposite charge and they each satisfy the Z -candidate requirements in Table 6.1. In addition, an electron pair needs to be in an invariant-mass window of $80 \text{ GeV} < m_{\ell\ell} < 110 \text{ GeV}$, a muon pair in a window of $70 \text{ GeV} < m_{\ell\ell} < 110 \text{ GeV}$ in order to select on-shell Z boson decays. If at least one of the two leptons is matched to the triggered object, the lepton pair is accepted as a Z -boson candidate. This last condition is applied so that events are selected that do not apply any implicit condition on the third lepton. If multiple lepton pairs satisfy the requirements above, the pair with the invariant mass closest to the Z boson mass [7] is chosen. When applied to a Z +jets MC sample with three reconstructed leptons, this algorithm correctly assigns leptons to the Z boson in about 99% of all cases.

The reconstructed Z -boson peak can be seen in Figure 6.1. This figure uses a plotting style highlighting the subtraction that is inherent to the fake estimate. Black datapoints show the measurement in data. The color-filled histograms in the bottom of the panel are stacked and show processes with real leptons estimated by MC simulation. The difference of the two is depicted in blue datapoints and corresponds to the estimated number of fake events. This matches the structure of equation (5.37)

$$F = \frac{N^t - N_r^t}{N^l - N_r^l}, \quad (6.1)$$

where the left terms in the numerator and denominator are determined from data and the right terms from MC simulation. Their difference, the blue datapoints, can be compared to

the prediction for Z +fake from MC, which is shown with a green, non-stacked histogram. The shape of the fake distribution agrees well between data and MC simulation. At the stage of Z -boson identification, the normalization shows a small disagreement that disappears after the cut on the transverse mass of the W boson. The seemingly decent description of fake processes by MC simulation fails once the events are split by the flavour of the fake lepton.

After the Z -boson candidate has been identified, the remaining lepton is the fake candidate if it meets the tight or loose selections in Table 6.1. These selections are chosen in accordance with the HWW analysis. The p_T and η cuts constitute the range in which the fake factor is determined. Since photon fakes are not supposed to be estimated, any objects with ambiguity between electrons and photons according to Ref. [105] are rejected⁵. The cut on $|z_0 \sin \theta|$ reduces the contamination of fake leptons from pile-up and heavy-flavour decays with a displaced vertex. The requirement on the transverse impact parameter d_0 is expressed in terms of the uncertainty of the impact parameter measurement σ_{d_0} . The tight selection is more restrictive for muons than for electrons in order to suppress fakes from heavy-flavour hadrons, which are the main source of muon fakes. The loose muon selection explicitly targets these heavy-flavour decays by relaxing the requirement.

The identification and isolation working points further distinguish the tight and loose selections. The loose selection accepts less clearly identified leptons that only need to satisfy the *LooseLH* likelihood and *Medium* quality working points, which increases the number of jets misidentified as leptons with respect to the tight selection. The looser isolation requirements accept leptons in the vicinity of significant hadronic activity making it more likely that the lepton originated from a close-by jet.

The criteria for Z -candidate leptons do not have a strict equivalent in the HWW analysis. In the previous analysis, these leptons were required to satisfy the tight selection criteria. This condition was loosened in this analysis version, because a study showed that the looser identification and isolation working points allow around 25% more Z +fake events into the region used for the fake-factor extraction. This reduces the statistical uncertainty, while keeping the purity of fake events high.

The main background in the 3-lepton analysis region comes from the WZ process, whose leptonic decay produces three real leptons. Assuming that the leptons from the Z boson are identified correctly, the remaining lepton and neutrino carry information about their origin. In the case of WZ production, the leptons come from an on-shell W boson. The invariant mass of the W boson can be calculated with

$$(m_W)^2 = m^2(p_\ell^\mu, p_\nu^\mu) = (p_\ell^\mu + p_\nu^\mu)^2 = m_\ell^2 + m_\nu^2 + 2(E_\ell E_\nu - \vec{p}_\ell \vec{p}_\nu), \quad (6.2)$$

⁵For reference, this condition is often referred to as the `AUTHOR = 1` requirement.

Electron			Muon		
Z candidate	tight	loose	Z candidate	tight	loose
	$p_T > 15 \text{ GeV}$ $ \eta < 1.37 \text{ or } 1.52 < \eta < 2.47$ No ambiguity with γ $ z_0 \sin \theta < 0.5 \text{ mm}$ $ d_0 /\sigma_{d_0} < 5$			$p_T > 15 \text{ GeV}$ $ \eta < 2.5$ $ z_0 \sin \theta < 0.5 \text{ mm}$ $ d_0 /\sigma_{d_0} < 3$	
<i>LooseLH- with-b-layer</i>	<i>TightLH</i> if $p_T < 25 \text{ GeV}$ <i>MediumLH</i> if $p_T > 25 \text{ GeV}$	<i>LooseLH</i>	<i>Medium Quality</i>	<i>Tight Quality</i>	<i>Medium Quality</i>
FCLoose iso.	FCTight iso.	Veto against tight	FCLoose iso.	FCTight iso.	Veto against tight

Table 6.1: Requirements on electrons and muons in the Z +fake analysis. For each lepton, the left column specifies the requirements for Z -boson candidate leptons. The right two columns for each lepton indicate the selection of tight and loose leptons as needed for the fake estimate. The requirements in the first rows are shared between different columns. The transverse and longitudinal impact parameters d_0 , z_0 and the angle θ are defined in section 3.3.2. More details on the electron likelihood, muon quality and isolation working points can be found in sections 3.3.2ff.

$\sqrt{s} = 13 \text{ TeV}, \mathcal{L} = 139/\text{fb}$	Z+jets Powheg	$V + \gamma$	WW	WZ	ZZ	Top	VVV	Total Bkg	Data	Fakes
Z-tagging	139500 ± 200	18300 ± 300	126 ± 3	32270 ± 50	6000 ± 30	10690 ± 20	86.2 ± 0.4	67500 ± 300	214484	147000 ± 600
$m_{T,W} < 50 \text{ GeV}$	125500 ± 200	15600 ± 300	46 ± 2	10130 ± 20	4270 ± 20	4060 ± 10	22.0 ± 0.2	34100 ± 300	161198	127100 ± 500
fake lepton loose or tight	63300 ± 100	4600 ± 200	21 ± 1	9730 ± 20	4040 ± 20	3520 ± 10	21.1 ± 0.2	21900 ± 200	86206	64300 ± 300
fake lepton flavour: electron	34300 ± 100	3900 ± 100	13 ± 1	4380 ± 20	1850 ± 10	801 ± 5	9.4 ± 0.1	10900 ± 100	41125	30200 ± 200
$ \eta_e < 1.37$ or $1.52 < \eta_e < 2.47$	27150 ± 90	3400 ± 100	9.9 ± 0.9	4130 ± 20	1740 ± 10	742 ± 5	8.9 ± 0.1	10100 ± 100	34003	24000 ± 200
Normalization factor (NF)				NF = 0.99 ± 0.01				NF		NF
signal selection: tight electron	2430 ± 30	790 ± 60	1.2 ± 0.3	3370 ± 10	1272 ± 7	277 ± 3	7.4 ± 0.1	5710 ± 70	7996	2300 ± 100
Normalization factor (NF)				NF = 0.99 ± 0.01				NF		NF
control selection: loose electron	24720 ± 80	2600 ± 100	8.7 ± 0.9	737 ± 7	470 ± 8	464 ± 4	1.53 ± 0.06	4300 ± 100	26007	21700 ± 200
fake lepton flavour: muon	28900 ± 100	740 ± 80	8.0 ± 0.7	5350 ± 20	2190 ± 20	2710 ± 10	11.7 ± 0.2	11010 ± 80	45081	34100 ± 200
$ \eta_\mu < 2.5$	28060 ± 90	690 ± 80	7.7 ± 0.7	5240 ± 20	2140 ± 20	2640 ± 10	11.5 ± 0.2	10730 ± 80	43638	32900 ± 200
Normalization factor (NF)				NF = 0.99 ± 0.01				NF		NF
signal selection: tight muon	1430 ± 20	30 ± 10	1.0 ± 0.2	4350 ± 10	1360 ± 10	388 ± 3	9.5 ± 0.2	6140 ± 20	7464	1330 ± 90
Normalization factor (NF)				NF = 0.99 ± 0.01				NF		NF
control selection: loose muon	26630 ± 90	670 ± 80	6.7 ± 0.6	856 ± 6	780 ± 10	2250 ± 10	1.92 ± 0.07	4560 ± 80	36174	31600 ± 200

Table 6.2: Cutflow of the Z +fake analysis with statistical uncertainties. The columns show the Z +jets and background processes to the Z +fake analysis estimated from MC simulation, the sum of all background processes, the number of events observed in data and finally the estimated number of fake events obtained by subtracting the total background from data.

The first row shows the number of events collected with single-lepton triggers, with three leptons after event reconstruction, overlap removal, a loose requirement for three leptons with $p_T > 15 \text{ GeV}$ and after finding a Z -boson candidate. The following rows list the number of events after the transverse mass of the W boson is restricted and the fake lepton is required to satisfy either the tight or loose identification criteria (not including the cut on $|\eta|$). After this cut, the cutflow splits up into one part for fake electrons, one for fake muons, each separated by a double horizontal line. After the cut on pseudorapidity is applied, the cutflow branches again into the tight and loose fake lepton definitions. Recall that the loose lepton definition excludes tight leptons. A normalization factor (determined in the region shown in Figure 6.2) is applied to the final four entries of the WZ process as indicated in blue. Also the total background column and the fake estimate are indirectly affected by this normalization.

Figure 6.2: Distributions for the WZ CR. The left-hand-side plot shows the transverse mass of the W boson, where the dashed line indicates the cut discriminating between fakes and the WZ background. The phase space with $m_{T,W} < 50$ GeV is used to extract fake factors (details in section 6.2.3) and the orthogonal is used for the WZ CR. The right-hand side plot shows the transverse momentum of the fake lepton candidate (i.e. the lepton not associated with the Z -boson decay) in the WZ CR. A normalization factor of 0.993 is applied in both plots to the WZ process.

where p_ℓ^μ, p_ν^μ are the four-vectors of the charged lepton and neutrino, respectively; $\vec{p}_\ell, \vec{p}_\nu$ are their momenta and E_ℓ, E_ν their energies. The transverse component of the neutrino momentum can be approximated with the missing transverse energy of the event, but the longitudinal component is unknown. Therefore, the transverse mass [188] of the W boson is defined as

$$(m_{T,W})^2 = m_T^2(p_\ell^\mu, p_\nu^\mu) = m_\ell^2 + m_\nu^2 + 2(E_{T,\ell}E_{T,\nu} - \vec{p}_{T,\ell} \vec{p}_{T,\nu}) \quad (6.3)$$

with the transverse energy defined through $E_T^2 = p_T^2 + m^2$. It can be shown that this definition of the transverse mass of two particles constitutes a lower bound on the invariant mass $m_T(p_a^\mu, p_b^\mu) \leq m(p_a^\mu, p_b^\mu)$ [189]. With respect to the W boson, the masses of the leptons are small and can be neglected so that the expression simplifies to

$$(m_{T,W})^2 \approx 2 p_{T,\ell} p_{T,\nu} (1 - \cos \phi). \quad (6.4)$$

In many fake processes, there is only a small transverse momentum imbalance due to a lack of neutrinos. If a fake lepton is produced through heavy-flavour decays, the associated W -boson is highly virtual with an invariant mass much smaller than the nominal W -boson mass. In either case, events with fake leptons typically have small $m_{T,W}$, while WZ processes exhibit larger values. The Z +fake analysis exploits this by requiring $m_{T,W} < 50$ GeV in order to increase the purity of fake events. The resulting region (*extraction region*) is used to extract the fake factors, which is described in detail in section 6.2.3.

The events that are rejected by the cut on $m_{T,W}$ largely contain both a real W and a real Z boson. These events comprise a control region for the WZ process (WZ CR) after

requiring that the third lepton satisfy the tight lepton criteria. Figure 6.2 depicts the distribution of the transverse mass of the W boson. It clearly shows that the variable is a powerful discriminant to separate Z +jets and WZ production. A normalization factor of $\alpha = 0.993 \pm 0.009$, where the uncertainty is purely statistical, was extracted in the WZ CR by comparison with data. This normalization factor is already applied to the WZ process in the plots. The normalization factor is also used in the extraction region to correct the estimated data yield of the WZ process with

$$N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{est}} = \underbrace{\frac{N_{\text{WZ CR}}^{\text{data}}}{N_{\text{WZ CR}}^{\text{MC}}}}_{\alpha} N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{MC}}. \quad (6.5)$$

The superscript indicates if the yield is taken from data or MC simulation and the subscript indicates if it is taken from the extraction region or WZ CR.

The right-hand side of Figure 6.2 shows that the transverse momentum of the fake lepton candidate is modelled well by MC simulation. This is noteworthy, because disagreement has been seen in a previous analysis and was taken into account as a systematic uncertainty on the normalization factor [118, 184]. The prior mismodelling was caused by an issue during MC generation that was not known at the time. Figure 6.2 shows that this issue has been fixed. Because a small mismodelling of the transverse momentum can have a large effect on the normalization, it was decided to apply a mismodelling uncertainty.

6.2.2 Anticipation of HWW Control Selections

Before using the extraction region from above to calculate fake factors, this section takes a brief look at the control selections in the HWW analysis. Technically, this topic would rather belong to chapter 7, but thematically it fits here in the description of the fake estimate. The reason is that the HWW control selections will be multiplied with the fake factor to give the fake estimate in the signal selection. With the limited sample size in the Z +fake estimate, it is helpful to know the fake lepton kinematics in the HWW control selection in order to choose an appropriate binning for the fake factors.

The HWW analysis covers two production processes, ggF and VBF , and has four principal signal regions. Three signal regions target the ggF Higgs signal and their main difference is the number of jets: 0-jet, 1-jet and 2-or-more-jets. The VBF process is mainly measured in one signal region that requires at least two jets. For simplicity, the signal regions with two or more jets are referred to as 2-jet signal regions in the following. The exact definition of these Higgs signal regions is described in section 7.2.

The leading contribution to the fake estimate comes from the control selections with one tight and one loose lepton (cf. equation (5.15)). The transverse momentum of the loose lepton in these control selections is depicted in Figure 6.3. All plots show that the vast majority of fake leptons have small transverse momentum. Comparing plots in different rows reveals that the momentum of fake leptons increases with the number of jets. The reason

Figure 6.3: Transverse momentum of the loose lepton in control selections with one loose electron (left) and one loose muon (right) in the HWW signal regions. The four rows show the 0-jet, 1-jet and 2-jet ggF and the VBF signal regions, respectively.

Figure 6.4: Pseudorapidity of the loose lepton in control selections with one loose electron (left) and one loose muon (right) in the HWW signal regions. The four rows show the 0-jet, 1-jet and 2-jet ggF and the VBF signal regions, respectively.

for this effect is that the otherwise low-momentum fake leptons recoil against the jets. But even in the 2-jet signal regions fakes do not have transverse momentum above 80 GeV and only rarely above 50 GeV. The majority of fake leptons have a p_T below 30 GeV in all signal regions.

Figure 6.4 shows the pseudorapidity for the same four signal regions and two control selections. At first sight, a clear difference is visible between electrons and muons. Electron fakes follow a flatter distribution, while muon fake yields drop towards either side of the distribution⁶. But unlike the p_T distributions, the entire pseudorapidity range is reasonably populated and no regions with a particularly low fake yield are identified.

6.2.3 Extraction of Fake Factors

The extraction region, previously defined using $m_{T,W}$, is used to determine fake factors. In this region, two selections are constructed for each fake lepton type, electron and muon, depending on whether the fake lepton satisfies the tight or loose identification criteria. These selections are called signal and control selection⁷ if they contain a tight or loose lepton, respectively. The events in these two selections are then divided into bins of $|\eta|$ and p_T of the fake lepton candidate Equation (6.1) prescribes how to calculate the fake factor for each of the bins.

The resulting fake factors are shown in Figure 6.5. For muons, the fake factors depend on $|\eta|$ with larger values in the end-cap region of the muon spectrometer. For electrons, the fake factor increases as a function of p_T with a step at 25 GeV caused by the changing likelihood working points. It was checked that the fake factors depend neither on the missing transverse momentum nor on the number of interactions per bunch crossing. The values of the fake factor are listed in Table 6.3 together with their binning and uncertainties.

The binning of the fake factor that was chosen for this estimate is subjective to a certain degree. A finer binning increases statistical uncertainties, but allows for a more finely grained dependence on sensitive variables. The limited sample size in the Z +fake event selection combined with the selective lepton requirements dictate a rather coarse binning. The fake factor dependence on pseudorapidity was investigated at different transverse momenta. It was observed that the electron fake factor does not depend on $|\eta|$, while the muon fake factor shows a dependence. These findings are also reflected in Figure 6.6, where the shape of the fake electron yield is similar between the signal and control selection producing a uniform fake factor. For muons, on the other hand, the signal selection has uniform yields across η , while the control selection has higher yields in the central and lower yields in the forward region. The result is that the fake factor increases as a function of $|\eta|$. The boundary between the barrel and end-cap of the muon spectrometer [190] is located at $|\eta| = 1.05$. In

⁶Incidentally, this qualitative behaviour will also be visible in the control selection of the extraction region for the fake factors in Figure 6.6.

⁷These selection names were conceptually introduced in section 5.2.

Figure 6.5: Fake factors derived in Z +fake events as a function of p_T . The plot in the top shows the electron fake factors, the middle plot the muon fake factors in the low- η region and the bottom plot the muon fake factors in the high- η region. The values are also listed in Table 6.3.

the central barrel region, the yields are roughly uniform and they decrease in the end-cap region. Therefore, a bin boundary of $|\eta| = 1.05$ is chosen according to the detector design. The electron fake factor is not binned in $|\eta|$.

When trying to bin the fake factor in transverse momentum, the lack of high- p_T fake events becomes problematic. Recalling the p_T distributions in the HWW signal regions in Figure 6.3, it seems reasonable to merge all events above 35 GeV into one bin and to determine a single fake factor. This treatment would not be acceptable in other analyses, but the small lepton momenta in the HWW signal region allow such a coarse binning. Below 35 GeV, the fake factor is split into one bin of 10 GeV and two bins of 5 GeV width at the lowest transverse momenta.

For muons, it is even trickier to measure the fake factor at high transverse momenta. Therefore, bin boundaries are set at $\{15, 20, 25, 50, \infty\}$ GeV. An extrapolation factor is derived in Z +jets MC simulation to estimate the fake factor in the highest p_T bin based on the second-highest bin. The extrapolation factor is found to be 1.68 ± 0.43 . The motivation and details of this extrapolation are presented in the next section.

6.2.4 Muon Extrapolation Factor ★

Figure 6.6 shows the input distributions to the fake-factor calculation. It indicates that tight fake leptons are scarce at high p_T , which complicates in particular the muon fake factor estimate. Above 40 GeV, no significant fake contribution is visible anymore in the signal selection rendering the extraction of fake factors unfeasible. To make the situation worse, the split into two pseudorapidity regions reduces the event count even further. Considering the same approach as for electrons would require to set the highest p_T bin boundary as low as 25 GeV and extract a combined fake factor for all events above this threshold. This is not ideal, because the transverse momenta of fake muons in the HWW signal region tend to be higher than for electrons and should therefore be binned more finely. Moreover, the sizeable subtraction of real-lepton events would cause large uncertainties on the fake factor.

Instead, another strategy has been investigated. If the highest bin boundary is set to 50 GeV, the fake factor below 50 GeV can be measured with relatively good precision. This constitutes a significant improvement to the analysis result, because the number of muon fakes between 25 and 50 GeV is substantial (refer again to Figure 6.3). For all of these events, the uncertainties would drop with respect to the previous approach with coarser binning. The drawback is, however, that it is virtually impossible to determine a fake factor above a transverse momentum of 50 GeV.

To solve this problem, this high- p_T phase space can be extrapolated from the neighbouring bin in p_T . The fake factors of the Z +jets process are determined in simulation as depicted in Figure 6.7. The ratios between the fake factor above 50 GeV and in the next-highest bin between 25 and 50 GeV are 1.86 ± 0.27 and 1.34 ± 0.37 for POWHEG and SHERPA, respectively. They are averaged to 1.68 ± 0.22 (stat). To account for a potential mismodelling, a systematic uncertainty is assigned. This modelling uncertainty is based on the discrepancy

Figure 6.6: Kinematic distributions of the fake candidate in the extraction region. The top four plots are electron fake candidates and the bottom four muon fakes. For each set of four plots, the top two show the signal selection with a tight fake candidate and the bottom two the control selection with a loose fake candidate. The transverse momentum is shown on the left and the pseudorapidity on the right-hand side.

Figure 6.7: MC-based muon fake factors in Z +jets events in POWHEG and SHERPA as a function of p_T . Even though the MC generator predictions for fake factors are different by about a factor of two, the qualitative shape of the fake factors agrees. Thus, also the extrapolation factors, which are calculated as the ratio of the rightmost bin content over the adjacent bin, are similar.

of the individual extrapolation factors from the averaged mean. The standard deviation is calculated taking into account the applicable student-t factor. Then, the systematic modelling uncertainty is 0.34 and the combined uncertainty of the extrapolation factor is $0.22 \text{ (stat)} \oplus 0.35 \text{ (modelling)} = 0.41 \text{ (total)}$.

Figure 6.8 shows how the fake-factor extrapolation reduces the uncertainty compared to the scenario without an extrapolation factor. The uncertainty due to the down variation of the real-lepton background in the region between 25 and 50 GeV is reduced by a factor of two. The up variation is hardly affected, because of the constraint that the fake factor be positive. This effect obscures the improvement due to the fake factor extrapolation. Also the statistical uncertainty is slightly reduced in this region. When extrapolating to the region above 50 GeV, the statistical and real-lepton subtraction uncertainty in principle remain unchanged, because they are not affected by the extrapolation.

Due to this extrapolation, the statistical uncertainties in the highest two p_T bins need to be treated as correlated in the statistical HWW analysis. The subtraction uncertainty is correlated between all bins. Hence, no special handling needs to be applied.

One can question how sensible a simulation-based extrapolation is within the Fake Factor Method, given the large effort to design this data-driven estimate. But arguably, it is hardly possible to estimate in data an effect that does not occur in said data. Both the Z +fake estimate and the control selection in the HWW signal regions confirm that muon fakes are very rare, particularly in the signal selection. The fake factor at lower transverse momentum serves as a reliable basis for the extrapolation. For the extrapolation from low to high p_T , it is well possible that any mismodelling in simulation is similar between both regions and therefore cancels out when taking the ratio. This assumption is justified, because heavy-flavour decays are the only considerable source of fake muons and thus the extrapolation does

Figure 6.8: Uncertainties on the muon fake factor in the central $|\eta|$ bin to illustrate the effect of the extrapolation on the uncertainties. In each bin, the configurations with extrapolation factor (darker colours) and without extrapolation factor (lighter colours) are compared. Below 25 GeV, the uncertainties are the same. Above 25 GeV, the subtraction uncertainty is reduced drastically at the expense of increasing the statistical uncertainty and introducing an extrapolation uncertainty. Note that any fake factor should be greater than 0 and therefore its negative, relative uncertainty is naturally bounded at -1. Thus, the extrapolation has a larger effect on the positive uncertainty of the fake factor.

not relate different physical processes. Nevertheless, an additional systematic uncertainty was derived and applied on the extrapolation factor.

Regardless of this discussion, the best argument for the extrapolation approach is that it improves the quality of the data-driven fake estimate in the low- p_T region, where the impact is comparatively large and no extrapolation is applied. The extrapolated fake factor, in contrast, is only applied to few events and does not harm the analysis result even if accompanied by larger uncertainties. Therefore, the extrapolation method is chosen.

6.2.5 Subtraction Uncertainty

When the fake factor is calculated with equation (6.1), processes are subtracted from the data yield that only contain real leptons. Theoretical uncertainties in the normalization of these MC processes cause a systematic uncertainty in the fake factor. This is referred to as *(real-lepton) subtraction uncertainty*.

The cutflow in Table 6.2 shows that the control selections are more than 80% pure in fakes, while the signal selections are mainly populated by real-lepton background processes. Therefore, the ratio in equation (6.1) is sensitive to MC uncertainties in the signal selection, but is barely affected by uncertainties in the control selection. Hence, the latter ones will be neglected in the following discussion.

The largest backgrounds in the signal selection for fake muons come from the production of WZ and ZZ . The same processes, as well as $Z+\gamma$ also contaminate the electron signal

Kinematic Region ($ \eta $ and p_T range)	Value	Statistical	Subtraction	Sample Composition	Total
Electron:					
$0.0 < \eta < 2.5$					
15.0 – 20.0 GeV	0.076	6.2	3.9	7.5	10
20.0 – 25.0 GeV	0.086	11	8.1	31	34
25.0 – 35.0 GeV	0.14	13	14	7.4	20
35.0 – ∞ GeV	0.21	12	25	21	35
Muon:					
$0.0 < \eta < 1.05$					
15.0 – 20.0 GeV	0.042	8.4	7.1	8.1	14
20.0 – 25.0 GeV	0.017	35	34	11	50
25.0 – 50.0 GeV	0.026	39	58	11	71
50.0 – ∞ GeV	0.043	47	58	11	75
$1.05 < \eta < 2.5$					
15.0 – 20.0 GeV	0.060	6.7	5.3	8.1	12
20.0 – 25.0 GeV	0.042	17	14	11	25
25.0 – 50.0 GeV	0.065	19	28	11	36
50.0 – ∞ GeV	0.11	32	28	11	44

Table 6.3: Fake factors from the Z +fake estimate with uncertainties. All uncertainties are quoted in percent on the nominal value. *Value* denotes the nominal fake factor value. *Statistical* denotes the statistical uncertainty on the fake factors including the extrapolation uncertainty for the highest muon p_T bin. *Subtraction* denotes the uncertainty due to the electroweak backgrounds that enter the fake factor estimate. *Sample Composition* denotes the uncertainty that accounts for differences in fake factors between Z +jets and W +jets processes, and includes both statistical and systematic uncertainty on the correction factors. The column *Total* sums all individual contributions in quadrature to give an impression of the total uncertainty of the fake factor. In the HWW analysis, however, all uncertainties are treated independently.

selection. For these three processes, theory uncertainties are derived in the following paragraphs. These uncertainties are then propagated into the fake estimate to give an estimate for the systematic uncertainty on the fake factor. For the other background processes, for which a dedicated theory uncertainty estimate is not worthwhile because of their small contribution, an uncertainty of 10% is assumed. This is a similar uncertainty as derived for the other processes without control region (see Table 6.8).

The general procedure is to change parameters one by one in the production of the MC samples and check how the prediction in the extraction region is affected. The difference between the varied yield and the nominal yield is called *impact*. This impact characterizes the systematic effect that can be expected due to a given variation.

Uncertainties from renormalization and factorization scales, μ_R , μ_F , are estimated by varying the scales by a factor of 2. Using the reweighting mechanism provided by SHERPA [191],

ZZ Uncertainty	Impact high / low [%]			
	tight electron	tight muon	loose electron	loose muon
μ_F, μ_R	10.3 / -7.8	8.3 / -6.8	10.4 / -7.9	11.2 / -8.2
PDF	1.6	1.8	1.6	1.7
α_s	1.3 / -1.3	1.2 / -1.3	1.2 / -1.3	1.2 / -1.3
symmetrized total	8.6		-	-

Table 6.4: Theory uncertainties of the ZZ MC process in the extraction region. The columns correspond to the tight and loose selections in events, where electrons or muons are the fake candidate. Only the tight columns are considered for the systematic uncertainty (see the text for an explanation). The loose columns are only quoted for completeness. The rows show different sources of normalization uncertainty. In the last row, the symmetrized and quadratically summed uncertainty is shown. Also the uncertainties for the two cases of fake electron and fake muon are averaged.

$Z+\gamma$ Uncertainty	Impact high / low [%]			
	tight electron	tight muon	loose electron	loose muon
μ_F, μ_R	6.7 / -7.8	13.3 / -24.8	13.3 / -9.2	40.7 / -7.3
PDF	3.7	10.0	2.5	2.9
α_s	1.5 / -0.6	-1.9 / -3.4	1.1 / -1.3	-0.2 / -0.2
symmetrized total	8.2	22	-	-

Table 6.5: Theory uncertainties of $Z+\gamma$ MC process in the extraction region. The columns correspond to the tight and loose selections in events, where electrons or muons are the fake candidate. Only the tight columns are considered for the systematic uncertainty (see the text for an explanation). The loose columns are only quoted for completeness. The rows show different sources of normalization uncertainty. In the last row, the symmetrized and quadratically summed uncertainty is shown. Note that the region with fake muons has no practical relevance because of the small yields.

seven configurations are considered $\{\mu_R, \mu_F\} = \{0.5, 0.5\}, \{0.5, 1\}, \{1, 0.5\}, \{1, 1\}, \{1, 2\}, \{2, 1\}, \{2, 2\}$ and the largest positive and negative impact is quoted as uncertainty (“envelope method”). Uncertainties on the PDFs are evaluated by considering 100 varied replicas of NNPDF3.0. The variations affect the yields of the analysis and the standard deviation of the impact is taken as an uncertainty. The choice of the QCD scale α_s when evaluating the PDFs is considered as a separate uncertainty and evaluated by varying the value of α_s by ± 0.001 .

Table 6.4 and 6.5 show these theory uncertainties for ZZ and $Z+\gamma$. In both cases, the scale uncertainty dominates. Since up and down variations are of similar size and to simplify the handling, they are symmetrized. The ZZ theory uncertainties should be largely independent of fake type and are therefore averaged for the fake electron and fake muon case. This is not the case for $Z+\gamma$, which behaves differently for both fake flavours. Thus, the uncertainties are handled separately.

To estimate systematic uncertainties related to the parton shower, namely the resummation scale, matching scale and dipole recoil scheme, dedicated MC samples, that are generated for the WZ process with the corresponding variations, need to be compared to the nominal ones. The resummation scale is varied up or down by a factor of ± 2 . The factorization scale, which is nominally set to $Q = 20$ GeV, is varied to 15 GeV and 30 GeV. For the dipole recoil scheme, the two different methods are compared [192, 193]. To reduce the computational effort, these samples are only generated at particle level, i.e. without the detector simulation and reconstruction.

In case of the WZ process, the three leptons required by the selection cuts exist at particle level. Using these leptons directly is a reasonable approximation for the tight identification criteria, that are normally applied to leptons. Thus, the regions for the particle-level analysis are defined like the regular analysis regions with the exception of the tight lepton requirements and trigger matching, which is not available at particle level. The events passing into the truth analysis regions in different samples provide information about the normalization of the WZ process when the resummation or matching scales are varied.

Since the WZ yield in the extraction region is constrained by a normalization factor from the WZ CR, the uncertainties for the WZ process need to be calculated differently than for ZZ and $Z+\gamma$. In the latter case, impacts are computed as the yield difference between the nominal and a systematic variation. For the WZ process, however, the uncertainties of the extrapolation from the WZ CR into the extraction region need to be used. These extrapolation uncertainties estimate how the normalization in the extraction region is affected compared to the WZ CR due to a certain systematic variation. The term

$$\frac{\Delta N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{est}}}{N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{est}}} = \frac{N_{\text{extr}}^{\prime\text{est}} - N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{est}}}{N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{est}}} = \frac{N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{MC}}/N_{\text{WZ CR}}^{\text{MC}}}{N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{MC}}/N_{\text{WZ CR}}^{\text{MC}}} - 1 \quad (6.6)$$

describes the relative uncertainty of the WZ yield estimate in the extraction region. To distinguish the systematically varied yields from the nominal ones, they are primed. The double ratio on the right-hand side is obtained by substituting equation (6.5).

Table 6.6 shows the extrapolation uncertainties of the WZ process. In addition to the previously mentioned uncertainties, the statistical uncertainty in the WZ CR is listed. Moreover, an uncertainty for the fake contamination in the WZ CR is derived. If the normalization of Z +jets is generously varied by $\pm 30\%$, it affects the normalization factor by less than 1%. Because in the 36/fb Couplings analysis the p_T of the fake lepton candidate was mismodelled in the WZ CR, a corresponding uncertainty was derived. Even though no apparent mismodelling is seen in this analysis, the same approach is followed to derive an uncertainty. The normalization factor is extracted in three sub-regions defined by the p_T of the fake candidate with region boundaries at $\{15, 35, 80, \infty\}$ GeV. The standard deviation of the normalization factor weighted by the event yield is used as an uncertainty. Since no differences are seen between cases when the electron or the muon is the fake candidate, these last three uncertainties are evaluated for both cases simultaneously.

WZ Uncertainty	$\Delta N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{nest}} / N_{\text{extr}}^{\text{nest}} [\%]$	
	tight electron	tight muon
μ_F, μ_R	1.3 / -1.3	1.2 / -1.2
PDF	0.6	0.1
α_s	0.1 / -0.2	0.0 / 0.0
matching scale (particle level)	-0.9 / 0.0	-1.8 / 0.6
resummation scale (particle level)	-0.9 / -0.4	-0.8 / -1.5
dipole recoil scheme (particle level)	0.2	0.1
Statistical	0.9	0.9
Fake contamination	1	1
p_T mismodelling	2.0	2.0
symmetrized total	3.0	3.5

Table 6.6: Theory uncertainties on the estimate of the WZ yield due to the extrapolation from the WZ CR into the extraction region. The columns distinguish between events, where electrons or muons are the fake candidate. The rows show different sources of uncertainty. In the last row, the quadratically averaged and conservatively symmetrized uncertainty is shown. Correlations between the systematic uncertainties are ignored.

WZ Uncertainty	Impact high / low [%]	
	tight electron	tight muon
μ_F, μ_R	10.4 / -7.6	11.3 / -9.0
PDF	1.5	1.4
α_s	1.6 / -1.6	1.5 / -1.5
matching scale (particle level)	0.1 / -2.9	-0.8 / -2.3
resummation scale (particle level)	3.6 / -1.9	3.7 / -3.0
dipole recoil scheme (particle level)	0.1	0.0

Table 6.7: Theory uncertainties on WZ yields derived from impacts in the extraction region. These uncertainties are not used directly to derive uncertainties of the WZ process. But the uncertainties in the truth analysis give an idea about the impact of the matching and resummation scale uncertainties in diboson samples.

Process	Normalization uncertainty [%]	
	tight electron	tight muon
ZZ	9.5	
$Z+\gamma$	9.1	22
WZ	3	3.5
other	10	

Table 6.8: Summary of real-lepton subtraction uncertainties. The values for ZZ and $Z+\gamma$ are taken from Tables 6.4 and 6.5 after adding a 4% uncertainty for the matching and resummation scale variations. The WZ uncertainties are taken directly from Table 6.6.

Figure 6.9: Leading-order Feynman diagrams for W +jets and Z +jets production. The quark flavour changes in W +jets, but remains the same in Z +jets.

Table 6.7 shows the impact of theory uncertainties on WZ . These are not relevant for the WZ uncertainty. But since no parton shower uncertainties are derived for the ZZ and $Z+\gamma$ samples, the uncertainties in this table can serve as a basis for a rough estimate. The quadratic sum of all uncertainties from the truth analysis amounts to at most 4%. This value is added in quadrature to the total uncertainties from Tables 6.4 and 6.5. Then, the final normalization uncertainties are summarized in Table 6.8.

To translate Table 6.8 into an uncertainty on the fake factors, the sample normalization is varied up and down simultaneously for all processes and fake factors are rederived in all bins. The resulting uncertainties are displayed on the right-hand side of Figure 6.5 and in Table 6.3.

6.2.6 Flavour Composition

An assumption of the Fake Factor Method is that fake efficiencies do not depend on the type of event. This allows to measure fake factors in Z +jets events and to apply them to W +jets events. As discussed in section 5.5, only the properties of the jet, that fakes the lepton, are relevant. The kinematic variables, η and p_T are already taken into account by binning the fake factor. But the origin of the fake lepton, in this case the flavour of the original parton spawning the jet, cannot be measured and needs to be considered as well. In this analysis, a correction for the *flavour composition*⁸ and a corresponding systematic uncertainty are derived.

The production mechanisms of the two relevant processes, W +jets and Z +jets, are similar. At leading order, they are represented by the Feynman diagrams in Figure 6.9. The W and Z bosons are radiated off a quark that interacts with a gluon. Therefore, the flavour of the incoming quark together with the radiated vector boson determines the flavour of the outgoing quark. The Z boson does not change the quark flavour, whereas the W boson swaps weak isospin partners.

Tables 6.9 and 6.10 show the origin of a fake lepton as predicted by POWHEG. The entries in this table are derived solely from simulation with the help of the MC particle record. This record contains intermediate states at particle level. Particles, that are reconstructed from

⁸Note that flavour composition does not refer to the flavour of the fake lepton, but to the associated parton in the matrix element.

Sample	Fake cand. selection	Muon Flavour Composition (%)				
		Bottom	Charm	Strange	Light	Other
W+jets	tight	7.6 ± 1.2	78 ± 5	6.4 ± 1.1	5 ± 1	3.2 ± 0.8
	loose	4.9 ± 0.2	84.5 ± 1.2	5.1 ± 0.2	4.7 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.1
Z+jets	tight	59 ± 2	27 ± 1	4.3 ± 0.3	4.3 ± 0.3	6.0 ± 0.4
	loose	59.0 ± 0.4	31.3 ± 0.2	5.4 ± 0.1	3.6 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.1

Table 6.9: Flavour of the initiating parton in jets faking muons in POWHEG W+jets and Z+jets samples. The uncertainties are only statistical.

Sample	Fake cand. selection	Electron Flavour Composition (%)				
		Bottom	Charm	Strange	Light	Other
W+jets	tight	1.5 ± 0.4	17 ± 2	8.1 ± 0.9	66 ± 3	6.9 ± 0.9
	loose	1.5 ± 0.2	26.5 ± 0.6	13.4 ± 0.4	57.4 ± 1.0	1.2 ± 0.1
Z+jets	tight	21.1 ± 0.7	7.9 ± 0.4	7.5 ± 0.3	55 ± 1	8.6 ± 0.4
	loose	13.7 ± 0.2	12.2 ± 0.2	16.0 ± 0.2	56.0 ± 0.3	2.0 ± 0.1

Table 6.10: Flavour of the initiating parton in jets faking electrons in POWHEG W+jets and Z+jets samples. The uncertainties are only statistical.

their detector signature, are matched to the intermediate particles to gather information about their origin. This matching happens based on the distance of the two objects in η - ϕ space.

The procedure starts by selecting events with two reconstructed leptons in MC simulation of W+jets. The lepton originating from the W boson is identified by virtue of the particle-level record. The other lepton is called the fake lepton. Then, the fake lepton is matched to close-by transient particles in the particle record. If a b-quark or a hadron containing a b-quark is found at particle level within a window of $\Delta R < 0.4$ around the fake lepton, the fake lepton is considered to have the fake origin bottom. If no bottom-flavour particle is found in the vicinity of the fake lepton, the same matching is performed successively for charm, strange and light quarks. All remaining fake leptons are classified as “other”. To derive the entries for Z+jets, the same procedure is used in three-lepton events, where two leptons are matched to the Z boson using the particle record.

Only statistical uncertainties are derived for this classification method, but the numbers nevertheless allow to make qualitative statements about the origin of fakes⁹. First consider muon fakes. The main production mechanism for fake muons is through heavy hadrons that decay by radiating a W boson, which further decays to a muon. Lighter hadrons, like pions and kaons can also produce muons, but these can be rejected during lepton identification more easily due to the longer hadron lifetime. Thus, only hadrons with charm and bottom

⁹Note that these tables are only shown to illustrate the different parton flavours of the W+jets and Z+jets processes. A flavour composition uncertainty is derived independently.

quarks contribute significantly to muon fakes. The lack of top quarks in the proton PDF explains that bottom quarks are rarely produced in the W +jets process.

When considering fake electrons in Table 6.10, the same heavy-flavour decays play a role as for muons. But in-flight decays of light hadrons into genuine electrons also contribute. An additional source for fake electrons is the misidentification of a jet as an electron in the detector. The latter process is largely independent of the quark flavour. Therefore, the original quark flavour of fake electrons is lighter than for fake muons. Strange quarks have the next-highest PDF values, then charm quarks. This is reflected in Table 6.10 and can be seen qualitatively by comparing the charm and strange columns. In association with a W boson, incoming strange quarks largely produce charm-flavoured jets, which are seen about twice as frequent as strange-flavoured jets. Also in association with a Z boson, strange quarks are produced slightly more frequently than charm quarks, which generally confirms the picture¹⁰. Like in the case of fake muons, W bosons are not accompanied by b quarks at leading order.

This discussion shows that there is a considerable difference in the origin of fakes for the two processes W +jets and Z +jets. The differences for muons are quite large, but the production mechanism is the same in all cases. For fake electrons, the difference between the processes is smaller. The largest difference is 20% in the tight selection for the Bottom origin. For these reasons, a correction is applied to the fake factors to account for the fake origin.

This correction is applied as a *correction factor* to the data-driven fake factor $F_{Z+\text{fake}}^{\text{data-driven}}$ extracted from Z +fake events to estimate a fake factor applicable to W +fake events:

$$F_{W+\text{jets}} = C \cdot F_{Z+\text{fake}}^{\text{data-driven}} \quad (6.7)$$

$$\text{with } C = \frac{F_{W+\text{fake}}^{\text{MC}}}{F_{Z+\text{fake}}^{\text{MC}}}. \quad (6.8)$$

The correction factor C is the ratio of the fake factors extracted from W +jets and Z +jets in MC simulation. To determine these fake factors, first events with a fake candidate are identified. They are split into a tight and loose selection depending on the properties of the fake candidate. Then they are binned in $|\eta|$ and p_{T} like the data-driven fake factor. Analogously to equation (6.1), the MC-based fake factors are calculated by dividing the fake estimate in the tight selection by the fake estimate in the loose selection.

The nominal correction factors C are shown in Figure 6.10. The simulation shows that the correction factor is independent of η for both fake lepton flavours. Therefore, one joint correction factor is derived for the entire pseudorapidity range. The highest two p_{T} bins for the muon fake factor are merged in order to reflect the extrapolation procedure. As a function of p_{T} , the correction factors show the same qualitative behaviour for electron and

¹⁰The difference is less clearly visible in association with Z bosons, which could be caused by a larger fake rate of charm quarks compared to strange quarks.

Figure 6.10: Correction factors derived as the ratio of MC-based fake factors. The fake factors for W +jets and Z +jets are derived with an equivalent POWHEG + PYTHIA 8 generator setup.

muon fakes and are consistent between different generators. As alternative generators for both Z +jets and its W +jets counter part, a MADGRAPH5_AMC@NLO v2.2.2 [194] setup at LO interfaced with PYTHIA 8.186 [195] is available and a SHERPA 2.2.1 [144] setup at NLO. Both alternative generators produce consistent correction factors with the nominal generator POWHEG. This is particularly reassuring for the derivation in SHERPA, because this setup uses a different parton shower algorithm.

The MADGRAPH setup is used to assign systematic uncertainties. The reason to choose MADGRAPH is that it has smaller statistical uncertainty and better agreement with data-driven fake factors compared to SHERPA. The difference between the MADGRAPH and POWHEG correction factors is quoted as a systematic uncertainty. The result is listed in Table 6.3.

Again, one can ask how sensible it is to correct a data-driven estimate based on MC simulation after section 5.1 argued that MC simulation is not suitable to estimate fakes. While this approach is not ideal and therefore associated with sizeable uncertainties, it benefits from using double ratios. The fake factors from simulation are divided and a potential mismodelling that affects both processes similarly cancels out. This hypothesis is supported by comparing different setups of MC simulation. Whether looking at W +jets or Z +jets, the fake factors in MADGRAPH are generally¹¹ greater than the POWHEG fake factors, which are greater than the SHERPA ones. Just like described above, this is a systematic effect that cancels out to a degree when calculating the correction factor. This is the case for both electron and muon fakes.

¹¹Since these fake factors are also binned and each bin is affected by statistical uncertainties, this is a general trend, not a strict relation.

6.2.7 Experimental Uncertainties

The influence of experimental uncertainties on the fake factor was investigated using the same approach as in section 7.5.1. These experimental uncertainties are typically a factor of 5 smaller than the statistical uncertainties, but at least a factor of 2 in all fake factor bins. Because of the small relevance, these uncertainties are ignored.

6.3 Fake Leptons in Events with Two Jets

6.3.1 Anticipation of HWW Trigger Requirements

In section 5.5.4, the scenario was discussed that the Fake Factor Method is affected by a selection bias. This is the case for the HWW analysis, because lepton triggers decide which events are recorded as described in 3.2.4.

Two principal triggers are used, a single-lepton trigger and a dilepton trigger. Both of them have a high selection efficiency for tight leptons. The dilepton trigger is designed to also be sensitive to loose leptons, while the single-lepton trigger only selects a small fraction of loose leptons. Because the dilepton trigger selects tight and loose leptons in the same way, the corresponding events are not biased. Conversely, events, that are only recorded due to the single-lepton trigger, are biased, because they have additional, implicit selection requirements. Therefore, the following discussion and special treatment are only needed for events that are not selected by the dilepton trigger.

The equations suggested for reweighting in section 5.5.4 assume that the trigger efficiency ε for loose leptons is known. Instead of measuring this efficiency explicitly and to simplify the experimental treatment, explicit fake factors are measured that already contain the trigger efficiency correction. Starting at equation (5.44) and using the example of one tight and one loose lepton, one can write

$$F_2 N^{tl} = F_2 (N^{t_1^T l_2^T} + N^{t_1^T l_2'^T}) + \frac{F_2}{\varepsilon^{l_2}} N^{t_1'^T l_2^T} \quad (6.9)$$

$$= F_2 (N^{t_1^T l_2^T} + N^{t_1^T l_2'^T}) + F_2^T N^{t_1'^T l_2^T}. \quad (6.10)$$

The ratio of the fake factor and the trigger efficiency is called the *triggered fake factor* F^T . It can be measured experimentally analogously to the nominal fake factor in equation (6.1). The only additional requirement is that the loose lepton pass the single-lepton trigger requirement

$$F^T = \frac{F}{\varepsilon^l} \quad (6.11)$$

$$= \frac{N'^t - N_r'^t}{\varepsilon^l (N'^l - N_r'^l)} \quad (6.12)$$

$$= \frac{N'^t - N_r'^t}{N'^{l^T} - N_r'^{l^T}}. \quad (6.13)$$

Equivalently to equation (6.10) and using the same triggered fake factor, the number of events with two loose leptons can be estimated with either of the two following equations

$$F_1 F_2 N^{ll} = F_1 F_2 (N^{l_1^T l_2^T} + N^{l_1^T l_2'^T}) + F_1 F_2^T N^{l_1'^T l_2^T} \quad (6.14)$$

$$= F_1 F_2 (N^{l_1^T l_2^T} + N^{l_1'^T l_2^T}) + F_1^T F_2 N^{l_1^T l_2'^T}. \quad (6.15)$$

In spirit, this treatment follows the idea outlined in section 5.5.4. But instead of measuring trigger efficiencies, a second set of fake factors F^T is measured and applied where appropriate. This way, the estimate is corrected for a selection bias introduced by the single-lepton trigger.

Due to the specific trigger setup in the HWW analysis, this treatment has a small inaccuracy that is only apparent when the dilepton and single-lepton triggers are considered explicitly. The single-lepton trigger efficiency ε^l is measured implicitly in the derivation of the fake factor. And it is applied only to events that do not pass the dilepton trigger requirements. If the dilepton and single-lepton triggers were independent, then ε^l would be a valid efficiency. But since both triggers use similar lepton requirements, the trigger efficiency changes when only selecting events failing the dilepton triggers.

This subtle problem is not easy to solve. One approach would be to measure the trigger efficiency contingent on failing the dilepton trigger. But this violates the important assumption that the fake factor only depends on the properties of the fake lepton, which allows to estimate the fake factor in a different process. Another solution would be to consider the criteria that the dilepton trigger applies to each individual lepton separately. This correction would be more complex and also require high statistics, because very specific trigger requirements are measured. A more drastic approach would be to drop either the dilepton trigger or the single-lepton trigger from the HWW analysis. This might be an option once more data are collected and the statistical power of the collected data is sufficient.

While these thoughts are interesting from an academic standpoint, one should bear in mind the small relevance this has on the analysis. The data-driven fake estimate is a small background in the HWW analysis and the selection bias due to the trigger is taken into account as a higher-order effect. Thus, the impact of the assumption that the triggers are independent is small. In addition, it can be argued that the two triggers are only partly correlated, because the single-lepton trigger only considers one lepton. Therefore, the decision was taken to use the equations outlined above with a suboptimal definition of the trigger efficiency.

6.3.2 Jet+fake Event Selection

The only difference between the nominal and the triggered fake factor is the trigger requirement on the loose lepton as prescribed in equation (6.13). With the same reasoning as before, the triggered fake factor can be measured in any process. It was attempted to make a measurement in the Z +fake selection, but the trigger requirement reduces the available data

Figure 6.11: Triggered Fake Factors derived with the requirement that leptons pass the trigger requirements. Since the triggers can vary considerably from year to year, the fake factors in different years are measured separately.

events too much to extract a reliable fake factor estimate. Instead, the jet+fake selection is chosen that was introduced in section 6.1.

The event selection targets dijet production, where one of the jets is misidentified as a lepton. Because there is no neutrino in the final state, these events typically have small missing transverse energy. Due to conservation of momentum, the jet and the fake lepton are reconstructed in opposite sides of the detector. These two requirements are reflected in the event selection.

All events are considered that contain one or more jets with transverse momentum of at least 25 GeV. Additionally, the events are required to have one reconstructed lepton, electron or muon, with $p_T > 15$ GeV. The leading jet and the lepton are required to have a minimum distance in the transverse plane of $\Delta\phi > 2.5$. Additionally, the missing transverse energy of the event needs to be below 30 GeV. To further reject events with a W boson, the transverse mass as defined in equation (6.3) is required to be below 60 GeV. This effectively applies an upper cut on the missing transverse energy depending on the angle $\Delta\phi$ between the lepton and the missing transverse energy.

6.3.3 Extraction of Triggered Fake Factors

After this region definition, the lepton is classified as tight or loose according to the requirements in Table 6.1 and required to pass the single-lepton trigger. This does not strictly follow the derivation in equation (6.13), where only the loose lepton is required to pass the trigger. However, due to the high trigger efficiency for tight leptons and the simplicity of using only single-lepton triggers to select events, this approximation is deemed appropriate.

The derived fake factors are shown in Figure 6.11. The binning in $|\eta|$ is chosen equivalently to the nominal fake factors. As a function of p_T , the bin boundaries follow the trigger thresholds of the corresponding data-taking year. After the data collected in 2015, a different trigger with a higher threshold and different characteristics is used for the following years. Because of this change and because the 2015 data only contribute 2% to the integrated luminosity in Run 2, only the fake factors in the later years are discussed explicitly.

In the case of fake electrons, the trigger algorithm [187] was optimized between all data-taking years. The largest change occurred in the beginning of 2017, when a new algorithm was introduced for electron reconstruction by the HLT. Despite these changes, the number of events in the tight electron selection is very similar in all three years after accounting for the different luminosity. Differences in the fake factor generally come from the loose selection. At low electron p_T , the fake factors are consistent with each other. Towards higher transverse momentum, the suppression of loose fakes improves in later years causing a higher fake factor. Between the 2016 and 2017 years, this improvement is visible above 50 GeV. Similarly, it is visible above 130 GeV when comparing the years 2017 and 2018.

For fake muons, the trigger requirements [186] change substantially at transverse momenta of 50 GeV. Above this threshold, no isolation requirement is applied, which allows a larger number of loose muons into the selection leading to a small fake factor. Below 50 GeV, an upper cut is set on the scalar sum of the p_T of all tracks within a distance of $\Delta z < 6$ mm around the muon vertex. For data-taking in 2018, this distance is reduced to 2 mm to reduce the impact of pile-up. In return, the isolation criteria are loosened, which is reflected in the higher number of loose muons and thus a reduced fake factor. At high transverse momenta, the purity of fake events in the tight selection is quite small, like in the measurement of nominal fake factors. Therefore, the fake factor in the highest p_T bin is most sensitive to the lowest available transverse momenta around 50 GeV.

6.3.4 Contribution of Triggered Fakes in HWW

It is not straightforward to quantify the influence of the triggered fake factors on the final fake estimate. The reason is that a number of effects come into play: the different triggers for events with loose electrons and muons, the subtraction of MC simulation, the different values of triggered fake factors compared to nominal ones and the subtraction of events with two loose leptons. The latter ones tend to have a higher number of events that are corrected with triggered fake factors.

When only the positive contributions are counted from events with one tight and one loose lepton, about 2.5% of the raw events are weighted by the triggered fake factors. Their weight amounts to typically 10% to 15% once fake factors are applied and MC simulation has been subtracted. But the final contribution to the yield tends to be smaller than 10%, because events with two loose leptons still need to be subtracted. In the VBF signal region, for example, the subtraction works out such that the contribution of events with triggered fake factors to the fake estimate is less than 1%. In the ggF 2-jet signal region, the contribution is around 8%.

This relatively small contribution justifies that systematic uncertainties are not estimated as rigorously as for the nominal fake factor. In fact, the variations of the triggered fake factor are so small compared to other systematic uncertainties, that they are generally pruned (see section 7.6.2) before entering the statistical analysis in an effort to reduce statistical noise.

Chapter 7

HWW Analysis

7.1 Analysis Strategy

The previous chapters have paved the way and laid the foundation for the HWW analysis. The goal is to measure the cross section of the ggF and VBF production modes of the Higgs boson with subsequent decay into two W bosons. Additionally, the significance of the VBF signal above the background-only hypothesis is determined. Naturally, this chapter is closely related to Ref. [127]. This overlap is only highlighted explicitly when figures are identical.

In ggF production, the Higgs boson is formed by two fusing gluons and involves a virtual top-quark loop. This mechanism does not produce jets so that any additional jets come from ISR or the underlying event. On the other hand, the VBF production mode comes with at least two jets. Driven by this signature, the dataset is split into three *analysis categories* according to the number of reconstructed jets: 0j, 1j, 2+j. The first two only target the ggF production mode, while the latter one includes events with two or more jets (“2 jets inclusive”) and targets both ggF and VBF .

Out of the possible Higgs boson decay modes mediated by W bosons (cf. Figure 2.6), the final state $e\nu\mu\nu$ provides the cleanest signature, because it suppresses well the Drell-Yan background¹. Some leptonic decays of τ leptons are included in an $e\nu\mu\nu$ selection, provided the different-flavour criterion is satisfied. The larger fraction of $\ell\nu qq$ final states is appealing, but this would introduce background from the W +jets process and increase the $t\bar{t}$ yield with ℓ +jets decays.

In this analysis, only the $e\nu\mu\nu$ final state is considered, where the charged leptons have different electric charge. One major background is then the production of a W -boson pair, that can only be distinguished from the signal by its kinematic properties, especially the invariant mass of the two leptons $m_{\ell\ell}$ and the azimuthal opening angle between them $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$. This angle is small for HWW events as explained in section 2.2.3 and large for WW events [196]. The Drell-Yan process with two τ leptons can also produce the $e\nu\mu\nu$ final state

¹For reference, in the HWW analysis during Run 1, the expected uncertainty on the signal strength in a signal region with two same-flavour leptons was roughly twice that for different-flavour events [41].

in case of leptonically decaying τ leptons. This process is reduced with different strategies (see section 7.2.2) in the different signal regions (SRs). In the 2^+j category, also $t\bar{t}$ constitutes an important background. The bulk of events are rejected with a veto on b -jets.

In the SRs targeting a measurement of the VBF process, a deep neural network (DNN) further discriminates between signal and background. With the two forward jets, the VBF signal is particularly rich in features that the DNN can harness. This approach is superior to a cut-based analysis, because of the small signal yield in the 2^+j phase space. Condensing the 15 input variables into a one-dimensional output, the DNN classifies each event by “signal-likeness”. This variable is used as final discriminant for the statistical analysis. In the ggF SRs, the transverse mass of the Higgs boson is used.

The statistical analysis takes the event distributions and uncertainties in the SRs as input and constructs a likelihood function. The maximum of the likelihood is considered the best-fit value and is used to measure the signal strength, the cross section and their uncertainties. Similarly, the significance of the VBF process is derived with a likelihood fit. The same procedure is also used to extract cross sections for subsets of the signal processes, resulting in a Simplified Template Cross Section (STXS) measurement.

7.2 Signal Regions

Signal regions (SRs) are defined in multiple steps that first establish a preselection, then reject backgrounds and finally focus on the signal topology. All requirements are summarized in Table 7.1.

7.2.1 Preselection

At first, a common preselection is applied to all data events to capture the basic event structure. If any condition is not satisfied, the event is removed. Note that this event preselection is different from the object (pre)selection in section 3.3.8. The preselection here follows the object (pre)selection in logical order.

Each event needs to contain exactly one electron and exactly one muon satisfying the tight identification requirements in Table 6.1. The leptons need to be of opposite electric charge and at least one of them needs to be matched to the event trigger. One of the two leptons² needs to have a transverse momentum of at least 22 GeV, the other one at least 15 GeV. Events are also discarded if the invariant mass of the two leptons $m_{\ell\ell}$ does not exceed 10 GeV, which removes Drell-Yan events with an intermediate τ lepton.

Events are not allowed to contain any additional electrons or muons, even if they are defined with a looser set of criteria. This looser set of criteria is equivalent to the requirements

²The leptons (just like jets) are ordered by their transverse momentum and accordingly called *leading* and *subleading*. This also explains the notation for the transverse momentum of the leading $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{lead}}$ and subleading lepton $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}}$.

Figure 7.1: Jet multiplicity after preselection cuts. The hashed uncertainty bands in each bin show the combined statistical and experimental systematic uncertainty of the MC simulation. They are added to the uncertainty of the data-driven fake estimate (Mis-Id) that is described in chapter 6. The Poissonian errorbars on data are too small to be seen. Also the signal contribution is barely visible at this point.

for Z candidates in Table 6.1 with the exception that electrons need to satisfy the likelihood working point for the tight selection.

After these cuts are applied — at preselection level — the jet multiplicity can be seen in Figure 7.1. Only jets with a transverse momentum of at least 30 GeV are considered. It shows the main backgrounds and their relevance in the different bins. In events without jets, the WW process is the main background, followed by Drell-Yan. With increasing jet activity, the relative contribution of the $t\bar{t}$ background rises drastically and completely dominates in events with two or more jets. Also the background due to fake events is shown and labeled as “Mis-Id”. It will gain importance when further cuts reduce the contribution of other backgrounds.

Apart from the background composition, the signal kinematics also change between bins. Most notably, the ggF -produced Higgs boson has small transverse momentum in events without jets, because the incoming quarks carry no transverse momentum. In contrast, the Higgs boson in one-jet events has transverse momentum that roughly balances the momentum of the jet. These differences in background composition and kinematics motivate the split of events into different analysis categories according to the number of jets. As displayed in Figure 7.1, jets with at least 30 GeV of transverse momentum are used to define

Category	0j: $N_{\text{jet}} = 0$	1j: $N_{\text{jet}} = 1$	2 ⁺ j: $N_{\text{jet}} \geq 2$
Target process	ggF		VBF
Preselection	Two different-flavour leptons ($\ell = e, \mu$) with opposite electric charge $p_{\text{T},\ell}^{\text{lead}} > 22 \text{ GeV}$, $p_{\text{T},\ell}^{\text{sublead}} > 15 \text{ GeV}$ $m_{\ell\ell} > 10 \text{ GeV}$		
Background rejection	$N_{b\text{-jet},(p_{\text{T}} > 20 \text{ GeV})} = 0$		
	$E_{\text{T}}^{\text{miss}} > 20 \text{ GeV}$		
	$\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell, E_{\text{T}}^{\text{miss}}} > \pi/2$ $p_{\text{T},\ell\ell} > 30 \text{ GeV}$	$m_{\tau\tau} < m_Z - 25 \text{ GeV}$ $\max(m_{\text{T}}^{\ell}) > 50 \text{ GeV}$	
$H \rightarrow WW^* \rightarrow e\nu\mu\nu$ topology	$m_{\ell\ell} < 55 \text{ GeV}$ $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell} < 1.8$		CJV OLV $m_{jj} > 120 \text{ GeV}$
		fail CJV or fail OLV $m_{jj} < 70 \text{ GeV}$ or $m_{jj} > 100 \text{ GeV}$ or $\Delta y_{jj} > 1.2$	
Discriminant variable	m_{T}		DNN

Table 7.1: Event cuts that define the SRs for the four analysis categories. The variable N_{jet} refers to the number of jets with $p_{\text{T}} > 30 \text{ GeV}$. Only for b-jets, the preselection jets from section 3.3.8 are used. These only require $p_{\text{T}} > 20 \text{ GeV}$. The abbreviations CJV and OLV stand for central jet veto and outside lepton veto. All variables are defined in the text.

the three categories 0j, 1j, 2⁺j. The latter one is comprised by events with two or more jets and is further divided to purify the ggF and VBF signal separately.

7.2.2 Background Rejection

A well-proven remedy against $t\bar{t}$ events is b -tagging, which was introduced in section 3.3.5. Using a b -tagging configuration that aims to be 85% efficient at identifying b -jets, events containing a b -jet are discarded in all three analysis categories. Because the transverse momentum of b -jets can be as low as 20 GeV, also the 0j analysis category benefits from the b -jet veto.

In the 0j analysis category, the dilepton system and the missing transverse energy are typically oriented back-to-back (see Figure 2.7). This is enforced with the cut on the azimuthal angle between the dilepton system and the missing transverse energy $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell, E_{\text{T}}^{\text{miss}}}$. This requirement has only a small effect and mostly removes fake events or events with a mismeasured missing transverse energy.

A minimum requirement on the missing transverse energy helps discriminate against the Drell-Yan background, particularly in the 0j analysis category. It is not used in the *VBF* analysis, because no significant improvement was seen.

Drell-Yan events with the decay chain $Z \rightarrow \tau\tau \rightarrow e\mu + 4\nu$ resemble the signal because they have charged leptons with different flavour in the final state. These events cannot be fully reconstructed because of the four neutrinos in the final state. However, one can find a good approximation by utilizing the fact that the Z boson is much more massive than the τ lepton. Due to energy conservation, a large fraction of the Z -boson energy is passed on to the τ leptons as kinetic energy. When these boosted τ leptons decay further, their daughter particles move in the same direction as their parent τ lepton in the detector reference frame. This motivates the collinear approximation [197, 198], in which the charged leptons and neutrinos continue on the same trajectory as their respective mother particles. It is further assumed that the entire missing transverse energy originates from the four neutrinos. Then, the \vec{E}_T^{miss} is decomposed into the components along the trajectory of the charged leptons in the transverse plane. For each charged lepton, the sum of the charged lepton momentum \vec{p}_T and the \vec{E}_T^{miss} component in the same direction approximate the momentum of the parent τ lepton. This gives the full four-vectors of the τ leptons and allows to reconstruct their invariant di-tau mass $m_{\tau\tau}$ with the equations [143]

$$m_{\tau\tau} = \frac{m_{\ell\ell}}{\sqrt{x_1 x_2}} \quad (7.1)$$

$$x_1 = \frac{A}{p_y^\mu E_x^{\text{miss}} - p_x^\mu E_y^{\text{miss}} + A} \quad (7.2)$$

$$x_2 = \frac{A}{p_x^e E_y^{\text{miss}} - p_y^e E_x^{\text{miss}} + A} \quad (7.3)$$

$$A = p_x^e p_y^\mu - p_y^e p_x^\mu, \quad (7.4)$$

where the indices x, y specify the components of the vectors.

In the 1j and 2+j analysis categories, a veto is placed on events, in which the di- τ mass falls within a 50 GeV wide window around the Z -boson mass. This cut rejects a large part of the Drell-Yan background. In the 0j analysis category, the approach of reconstructing the $m_{\tau\tau}$ does not work similarly well, because the Z boson does not recoil against jets and has only small transverse momentum. Thus, the two τ leptons move back-to-back and the transverse momenta of the neutrinos cancel out to a large degree. In this case, the relative precision of the \vec{E}_T^{miss} reconstruction is low and the assumption that the \vec{E}_T^{miss} is equal to the neutrino momenta is not satisfied anymore. Additionally, a linear combination of two anti-parallel vectors can in general not be used to decompose an arbitrary missing transverse energy.

Instead, the 0j analysis category uses the transverse momentum of the dilepton system $p_{T,\ell\ell} > 30$ GeV to reject Drell-Yan background. Because the charged leptons tend to be emitted in opposite directions with similar $|p_T|$, their combined transverse momentum is

small. The Higgs signal on the other hand has larger values of $p_{T,\ell\ell}$, because the leptons are emitted in a similar direction due to spin correlations. On top of that, the two additional neutrinos in the Drell-Yan process compared to the Higgs signal increase this discriminating effect by carrying away parts of the transverse momentum thus reducing the $p_{T,\ell\ell}$.

In the 1j category, at least one lepton needs to exceed a transverse mass of 50 GeV when combined with the missing transverse momentum. This variable is called the transverse mass of a lepton $m_{T,\ell}^{\ell}$ and it is defined like in equation (6.3) after replacing the neutrino momentum by E_T^{miss} . The Drell-Yan background has small transverse lepton masses, because the charged leptons and missing transverse energy tend to travel in a similar direction. The signal on the other hand, exhibits larger values, because the angle is larger and the momenta higher. The transverse mass is also small for multijet events containing fake leptons. The momentum of the fake lepton is sometimes reconstructed smaller than the momentum of the original jet. This leads to a missing transverse energy pointing in the same direction as the fake lepton and a small transverse mass.

7.2.3 Signal Topology

The following event requirements reject more than one background and are motivated by the topology and kinematics of the signal process. The proximity of the charged leptons, that is caused by the spin correlation, is reflected in the cut on the azimuthal angle $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ between them. It can also be found in the related criterion that the invariant dilepton mass be smaller than 55 GeV. The invariant mass is bounded above by the Higgs boson mass and reduced significantly by the small opening angle. The effect of these two cuts is shown in Figure 7.2 for the 0j and 1j analysis categories and in Figure 7.4 for the *VBF* SR together with the other DNN input variables. The histograms show the variables $m_{\ell\ell}$ and $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ and where the cut is placed. In all cases, the majority of the signal is retained, while relevant backgrounds are reduced. Note that the $m_{\ell\ell}$ requirement is applied first, which changes the shape of the $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ distribution due to correlations between both variables.

So far, events with two or more jets can fall into both the *ggF* and the *VBF* category. To ensure that every event is only analyzed in one SR, the following cuts provide orthogonality between the regions. They are related to the different Higgs-boson production modes.

In a *VBF*-initiated event, two jets with large momentum in the forward detector regions are typically reconstructed originating from the incoming quarks. Because none of other particles involved in the Higgs-boson production vertex interact via the strong force, no jets are expected at leading order perturbation theory in the region between the two high-energetic jets [199]. This requirement is implemented with the central jet veto (CJV), which rejects all events containing a jet with $p_T > 30$ GeV in the rapidity gap between the two jets with the highest transverse momentum. With the same idea, the outside lepton veto (OLV) ensures that both leptons are inside the rapidity volume spanned by the two leading jets, which is the natural *VBF* signature [200]. Finally, the invariant mass of the two leading jets m_{jj} is required to be larger than 120 GeV. This cut is comparatively loose [200], because

Figure 7.2: Distributions of the variables $m_{\ell\ell}$ (top) and $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ (bottom) in the 0j (left) and 1j (right) analysis category [127]. The bottom panel shows each process normalized to unity, which allows to compare the shapes of the different processes. The black dashed line shows the signal-region selection with the arrow pointing towards the events that are retained. For each depicted variable, all requirements are applied that appear above it in Table 7.1.

the m_{jj} variable is used as input to the DNN. Events with a high-DNN score tend to have considerably larger invariant di-jet masses.

For the ggF -targeting 2^+j analysis category, the CJV and OLV requirements are inverted. If at least one jet is inside or at least one lepton outside the rapidity gap of the two leading jets, the event is accepted into the ggF category. The subsequent requirements on m_{jj} and the absolute rapidity difference of the two leading jets Δy_{jj} remove the VH production mode, where the vector boson decays hadronically.

To make better use of the available data and construct regions with slightly different background composition, all analysis categories targeting the ggF production mode are further subdivided. They are each split into two regions, one with $m_{\ell\ell} \leq 30$ GeV and one with $m_{\ell\ell} > 30$ GeV. The 0j and 1j regions are further split according to the transverse momentum of the subleading lepton into regions with $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}} \leq 20$ GeV and regions with $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}} > 20$ GeV (cf. Figure D.2 for the 0j analysis category). The regions with a small $m_{\ell\ell}$ are purer in the Higgs signal than their large- $m_{\ell\ell}$ counter parts. In the region with small $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}}$, the contamination by the WW background is reduced at the cost of a higher fake contribution [41].

Another variable that is sensitive to the signal process is the transverse mass of the Higgs boson [201, 202]. In the context of this analysis, it is defined as (cf. the definition of transverse mass in equation (6.3))

$$m_{T,H}^2 = m_T^2(p_{\ell\ell}^\mu, p_{E_T^{\text{miss}}}^\mu) = \left(\sqrt{|\vec{p}_{T,\ell\ell}|^2 + m_{\ell\ell}^2} + E_T^{\text{miss}} \right)^2 - |\vec{p}_{T,\ell\ell} + \vec{E}_T^{\text{miss}}|^2. \quad (7.5)$$

It is not intuitive that the two leptons are clustered together, even though they don't originate from the same W boson. However, this definition of the transverse mass is bounded above by the Higgs boson and is better than other definitions [203]. Instead of placing a cut on this variable, it is used to categorize the events in histogram bins. These are given as input to the statistical analysis.

For the VBF analysis, the SR is comparatively loose and is not split into subregions. Instead, the DNN provides a more sophisticated selection, which — together with the smaller data yields — makes subregions obsolete. Later, the binned output variable of the DNN is used as input to the statistical analysis.

7.3 Signal Discrimination with a Neural Network

The purpose of the deep neural network (DNN) is to classify events by how closely they resemble the VBF signal process. The DNN model is trained with supervised machine learning based on event variables in MC simulation. This procedure encodes the topological and kinematic features of the signal and background processes into the neural network. Once the network model is trained, it is used to process and classify data events.

Parameter	Value
Hidden layers	{256, 128, 64, 32, 16, 8}
Activation function	Rectified linear unit between nodes ($f(x) = \max(0, x)$), Sigmoid function at output ($f(x) = 1/(1 + e^{-x})$)
Loss function	Cross entropy
Optimizer	Adagrad
Regularization	Dropout
Batchsize	512

Table 7.2: Hyperparameters for the DNN training. The batchsize is the number of processed events before the backpropagation algorithm is invoked.

In previous analyses, a boosted decision tree (BDT) was used to classify events. This approach was deprecated in favour of the DNN, because neural networks often exploit large training datasets better than BDTs. Studies confirmed that the available simulated dataset is large enough for this effect to occur.

The DNN is an artificial feed-forward network [204]. Nodes are arranged in nine consecutive layers. The layers have {15, 256, 128, 64, 32, 16, 8, 1} nodes and adjacent layers are connected by edges. Each edge has a weight associated with it and each node a bias. When the variables x_i of one event are passed to the DNN, each x_i is entered into one input node i and propagated through the different layers. A node j gets assigned a variable x_j based on all nodes i in the previous layer, the weights between the nodes w_{ij} and the bias b_j

$$x_j = \sum_i w_{ij} f(x_i) + b_j \quad (7.6)$$

with the activation function $f(x) = \max(0, x)$. The very last node uses instead a sigmoid function.

When training the network, the goal is to adjust all weights and biases such that signal events get an output value of 1 and background events an output value of 0. To quantify the agreement of the output values p_k with the true classes y_k (signal or background), where k indexes the events, the binary cross-entropy

$$L = -\frac{1}{N} \sum_{k=1}^N (y_k \log(p_k) + (1 - y_k) \log(1 - p_k)) \quad (7.7)$$

is used as a loss function. After $N = 512$ events have been classified, a backpropagation algorithm calculates partial derivatives $\partial L / \partial w_{ij}$ and $\partial L / \partial b_j$ for the weights and biases in all layers. According to the partial derivatives, the weights and biases are updated with the goal to minimize the cross-entropy following the Adagrad method [205]. The *learning rate* is a hyperparameter that controls the step size towards the negative gradient of the cross-entropy during the updates. It has been optimized to this problem and decreases during the training.

<i>VBF</i> topology	$H \rightarrow WW^* \rightarrow e\nu\mu\nu$ topology	$t\bar{t}$ rejection
m_{ℓ_1, j_1} p_{T, j_1} m_{jj}	$m_{\ell\ell}$	E_T^{miss} significance
m_{ℓ_1, j_2} p_{T, j_2} Δy_{jj}	$\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$	$p_{T, \text{tot}}$
m_{ℓ_2, j_1} p_{T, j_3} $C_{\ell_1} + C_{\ell_2}$	$m_{T, H}$	
m_{ℓ_2, j_1}		

Table 7.3: Input variables to the DNN, most of which are defined in the text. The indices ℓ_i and j_i refer to the p_T -ordered leptons and jets, respectively. Indices are omitted if the two leading leptons or jets are used. The lepton centrality is defined in equation (7.8) and the $p_{T, \text{tot}}$ in equation (7.9). More documentation about the E_T^{miss} significance can be found in Ref. [209].

Figure 7.3: Schematic view of the centrality (cf. Ref. [210]). Centrality of an object is calculated with respect to two reference objects, in this case jets. In the middle between the two reference objects, the centrality is 0. It grows to 1 when reaching the reference objects.

During the training, dropout layers [206] randomly deactivate nodes in order to keep the neural network flexible and resistant to overtraining³. The training data is split in half and each half trains a different model. The performance of each model is evaluated with the training data of the other model to avoid a bias (two-fold cross validation). The training is performed on MC samples of signal and background after the b -jet veto cut in Table 7.1. The VBF and ggF processes are each given a weight of 5%, the remaining 90% are divided between background processes according to their sample composition after the b -jet veto cut. The training proceeds for 80 epochs, i.e. each event is processed 80 times during the training procedure. The DNN is defined and trained with the machine learning library TensorFlow [207] that is accessed through Keras [208]. The technical settings are summarized in Table 7.2.

Variables were considered as potential inputs to the DNN, if they describe the characteristics of the VBF signal and the background processes. They were further required to be well-modelled by my MC simulation in comparison to data. The final input variables to the DNN were selected by comparing the classification performance of different input configurations. The signal significance with statistical uncertainties was the main criterion for the variable selection. Among configurations with similar performance, ones with fewer

³Intuitively, this procedure can be understood as the training of many thinned networks. Once they are trained, their effect is averaged by using the unthinned network.

input variables were favoured, because they reduce the risk of introducing parameters that are mismodelled or affected by large uncertainties.

The final input variables to the DNN are listed in Table 7.3 and categorized into three groups (see also Figure 7.4). The first set of variables identifies the VBF production mode. All four combinations of the invariant mass of the two leptons and the two leading jets are constructed. The VBF signature causes consistently larger values than backgrounds. Especially for the $t\bar{t}$ process, where the two jets supposedly come from the top-quark decays, two of the four combinations have an upper bound at the top quark mass around 173 GeV. The jets tend to have higher transverse momenta in signal events compared to background, motivating the use of the transverse momenta of the three leading jet. If the event does not contain a third jet, 0 is given as input to the network. The invariant mass of the dijet system is the most sensitive variable and the signal shows a long tail towards large values. The rapidity gap between both jets has similar features and adds information to the DNN even though it is highly correlated with the m_{jj} . The lepton centrality C_ℓ is defined as

$$C_\ell = \frac{|2\eta_\ell - (\eta_{j_1} + \eta_{j_2})|}{\Delta\eta_{jj}} \quad (7.8)$$

and quantifies how central the lepton is with respect to the rapidity gap spanned by the jets. This variable is illustrated in Figure 7.3. The signal shows a preference for central values.

The three variables addressing the HWW topology in Table 7.3, $m_{\ell\ell}$, $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ and $m_{T,H}$, are familiar from the ggF SRs in the previous section. They help to identify the Higgs boson decay into two W bosons with the characteristic small opening angle. The variables in the right column of Table 7.3 are mostly helpful to suppress the large $t\bar{t}$ background. To distinguish real missing transverse energy from resolution effects, the E_T^{miss} significance [209] quantifies how compatible the E_T^{miss} measurement is with the hypothesis that the event does not contain real missing transverse energy. The $t\bar{t}$ background tends to have a larger E_T^{miss} significance than the signal. The variable $p_{T,\text{tot}}$ is defined as the modulus of

$$\vec{p}_{T,\text{tot}} = \vec{p}_{T,\ell_1} + \vec{p}_{T,\ell_2} + \vec{E}_T^{\text{miss}} + \sum_j \vec{p}_{T,j}, \quad (7.9)$$

where the sum runs over all jets passing the object selection (i.e. $p_{T,j} > 25$ GeV). This variable is sensitive to soft radiation from QCD processes like $t\bar{t}$ production that does not exceed the energy threshold for the analysis jets. The signal process has comparatively small values of $p_{T,\text{tot}}$.

All input variables for the DNN are shown in Figure 7.4. It can be seen from these figures how well each variable alone is able to discriminate between the VBF signal and backgrounds. The DNN is able to combine these variables and exploit subtle correlations between them in the multi-dimensional input space. To check that the correlations between the input variables are modelled adequately, Figure 7.5 shows profile plots for all pairs of input variables, for both data and MC simulation. A χ^2 test quantifies the agreement between both distributions

Figure 7.4: Distributions of the input variables of the DNN in the VBF signal region: variables with information about the VBF topology in (a) to (j), the HWW topology in (k) to (m) and for $t\bar{t}$ rejection in (n) and (o). In the main panel of each plot, the signal and background estimates are stacked and normalized according to the post-fit yields (see later sections for more information). The hashed uncertainty band includes all sources of uncertainties based on the fit information. It is calculated following the prescription in Appendix C. The data points are superimposed. To visualize shape differences between signal and background that provides discriminatory power, the VBF signal process is multiplied by 50 and overlaid. The bottom panel shows the ratio of the data and the prediction (signal+background). This visualization is helpful to verify that the data fits well to the prediction. The distributions of m_{jj} and Δy_{jj} have been published before in Ref. [127].

Figure 7.5: Profile plots for all pairs of DNN input variables for data and MC simulation. The agreement between data and MC simulation is estimated with a χ^2 test and the corresponding p -value is printed in the bottom of each plot (this might not be legible in the print version). The p -value decides the colour-coding of each plot. Values between $5\% < p < 100\%$ are green, $0.5\% < p < 5\%$ are yellow and $p < 0.5\%$ are red.

Figure 7.6: Signal and background classified according to the DNN output variable (pre-fit). Only values $\text{DNN} > 0.25$ are displayed. The fine binning reveals large statistical MC uncertainties that are unsuitable for the statistical analysis and motivate a binning algorithm. Large uncertainties are also caused by events with a large event weight, most prominently one Z/γ^* event around $\text{DNN} \approx 0.6$.

in terms of a p -value taking into account only statistical uncertainties. The overproportionate occurrence of red plots (16/210) hints at mismodelling that is however acceptable in light of the neglected systematic uncertainties. It is also reassuring that only two pairs of variables show such extreme p -values in both corresponding plots. The number of yellow plots (13/210) is close to the expectation.

The DNN output variable serves as final classifier for the VBF process. It is shown in Figure 7.6 after all SR cuts are applied. Even in comparison to the most discriminant input variables, this distribution shows a much better separation of the VBF signal process from background. How the events are distributed along the DNN output variable depends on the loss function and might not be optimal for the further analysis. A fine binning makes good use of the DNN classification, but might suffer from systematic uncertainties and statistical fluctuations of data and MC simulation. A coarser binning is more robust in the statistical analysis, but might not separate signal from background well enough. A binning algorithm uses the signal and background predictions as inputs to set bin boundaries on the DNN output and find a decent compromise. Data is not used for the binning optimization.

Analysis Category	WW	$t\bar{t}/Wt$	Z/γ^*
$N_{\text{jet}} = 0$ ggF	$1.03^{+0.07}_{-0.07}$	$0.96^{+0.23}_{-0.18}$	$0.96^{+0.07}_{-0.06}$
$N_{\text{jet}} = 1$ ggF	$0.82^{+0.15}_{-0.14}$	$1.07^{+0.19}_{-0.16}$	$0.97^{+0.10}_{-0.09}$
$N_{\text{jet}} \geq 2$ ggF	$0.80^{+0.35}_{-0.34}$	$0.94^{+0.23}_{-0.18}$	$0.97^{+0.18}_{-0.16}$
$N_{\text{jet}} \geq 2$ VBF	—	$1.00^{+0.37}_{-0.22}$	$0.96^{+0.25}_{-0.20}$

Table 7.4: Normalization factors extracted in the combined fit. The values are mostly constrained in the CRs. Their uncertainties are correlated with systematic effects. Because these systematic effects are similar in the SRs, the effective uncertainty on the process normalization is typically smaller than the uncertainty quoted here.

Starting at the upper bin boundary $DNN = 1$, a bin is grown in steps of 0.01 towards $DNN = 0$ until it contains at least 10 signal events, at least 10 background events and the background prediction has a relative statistical uncertainty below 20%. At this point, the lower bin boundary is set and the next bin is grown starting at this position. The following bins are constructed with the same procedure, but they additionally require that the significance in a new bin is at least 1/3 of the highest significance in previously created bins. If the growing bin does not satisfy the requirement, it keeps growing. This prevents that the histogram is binned finely at low DNN values, where the background dominates. The last bin boundary is set at $DNN = 0$. The binned DNN distribution can be found in section 7.7 (Figure 7.9d).

7.4 Control Regions

The MC simulation of background processes typically reproduces differential distributions in data quite well, but the process normalization is often less precise. This problem is commonly addressed by defining control regions (CRs), which are pure enough in a specific background process to measure a normalization factor in data. This normalization factor is applied in the SR and constrains the background yield. In this procedure, the applicable extrapolation uncertainties between the regions need to be taken into account. In the HWW analysis, normalization factors are extracted with the fit model in section 7.6. The results can be found in Table 7.4. Different distributions in the CRs are shown in Figure 7.7.

CRs for three background processes are used in the HWW analysis: top quark, WW and Z/γ^* . The VBF analysis only has top quark and Z/γ^* CRs. Each analysis category has its own set of CRs, but the regions are not split according to $m_{\ell\ell}$ and $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}}$. Because the orthogonality between regions can be difficult to extract from the region definition, Figure 7.8 illustrates the differences between all regions. The following sections define the CRs with respect to the corresponding SRs. The selections for the fake estimate are not recapitulated here, because they were discussed in chapter 6.

Figure 7.7: Distributions in the CRs. The two plots in the top show the WW and top quark CRs in the 0j and 1j analysis category, respectively. The other four plots are in the Z/γ^* (left) and top quark CRs (right) in the VBF phase space (“ VBF -enriched”) and show the modelling of the m_{jj} (top) and DNN variables (bottom). The signal and background estimates are normalized according to the post-fit yields (see later sections for more information). The hashed uncertainty band includes all sources of uncertainties based on the fit information. It is calculated following the prescription in Appendix C. The plots with ATLAS label have been published before in Ref. [127].

Figure 7.8: Visual representation of the cuts separating SRs and CRs. All analysis categories are shown: 0j (previous page, top), 1j (previous page, bottom), *ggF* 2+j (this page, top), *VBF* 2+j (this page, bottom). Arrows pointing from one region are labeled with the cuts that are applied when moving from one region to another. Bold text indicates that a cut provides orthogonality between regions. A cut is crossed out if it is removed when going from one region to another. Units of GeV have been omitted for brevity. Cuts based on the mass of the *Z* boson have been shortened, i.e. $m_Z - 25 \text{ GeV} \approx 66 \text{ GeV} \equiv 66$.

7.4.1 WW Background

The WW CRs are mainly constructed by requiring larger opening angles between the two leptons $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ and/or the related larger invariant dilepton masses $m_{\ell\ell}$ to suppress signal and enhance the WW background. In the 0j analysis category, the range between $55 \text{ GeV} < m_{\ell\ell} < 100 \text{ GeV}$ is selected (see Figure 7.2). The cut on $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ is loosened to 2.6, which still suppresses the Z/γ^* background sufficiently.

In the 1j analysis category, the CR definition suppresses signal more strongly by requiring $m_{\ell\ell} > 80 \text{ GeV}$. In exchange, the phase space is opened to the less-relevant Z/γ^* process by removing the cut on $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ and only requiring $m_{\tau\tau}$ to lie outside of the Z -boson window of 50 GeV.

The top quark background in the 2+j analysis category is so large that after the requirement $m_{\ell\ell} > 80 \text{ GeV}$ too much top quark background remains for a WW CR. The variable m_{T2} helps to reduce the top quark background. The variable is designed for decay chains with two resonances, that both partly decay into invisible particles [189]. It estimates a lower bound for the invariant mass of the heavier resonance. This is helpful in the context of the WW CR, because m_{T2} can operate under the assumption of a $t\bar{t}$ process and estimate the invariant mass of the top quark. If the invariant mass is larger than m_t , then the process does likely not contain a $t\bar{t}$ pair.

The variable is classified in Ref. [202] as a late-projection transverse momentum and defined as

$$M_{2T}^2(p_{\text{vis}1}^\mu, p_{\text{vis}2}^\mu) = \min_{\vec{p}_{T,\nu_1} + \vec{p}_{T,\nu_2} = \vec{E}_T^{\text{miss}}} \left(\max(m_{T1}^2(p_{\text{vis}1}^\mu, p_{\nu_1}^\mu), m_{T2}^2(p_{\text{vis}2}^\mu, p_{\nu_2}^\mu)) \right). \quad (7.10)$$

The transverse mass function that is defined in equation (6.3) takes as inputs the four-vectors of the visible particles “vis” and neutrinos ν from resonance 1 and 2 to calculate a transverse mass. Since both transverse masses are a lower bound for the actual resonance mass, the maximum is taken. A problem with this approach is that it is unclear how the measured \vec{E}_T^{miss} needs to be decomposed into \vec{p}_{T,ν_1} and \vec{p}_{T,ν_2} . To ensure that m_{T2} constitutes a lower bound for the actual mass, the minimum of all configurations is taken that are consistent with the measured \vec{E}_T^{miss} .

The minimum of the four following combinations⁴ is considered in the analysis and called

$$\begin{aligned} m_{T2} = \min & (M_{2T}(\ell^{\text{lead}} + j_1, \ell^{\text{sublead}}), \\ & M_{2T}(\ell^{\text{lead}}, \ell^{\text{sublead}} + j_1), \\ & M_{2T}(\ell^{\text{lead}} + j_2, \ell^{\text{sublead}}), \\ & M_{2T}(\ell^{\text{lead}}, \ell^{\text{sublead}} + j_2)). \end{aligned} \quad (7.11)$$

⁴Further discussion about this definition of the variable m_{T2} can be found in section 9.2.

In the ggF 2^+j analysis category, events in the WW CR are required to have $m_{T2} > 165$ GeV. This way, a WW purity of around 40% can be achieved with a top-quark contamination amounting to around 45%.

For the analysis region targeting the VBF production mode, a similar approach was taken to define a WW CR. After a cut on m_{T2} to reduce the top quark background and a cut on $m_{T,H}$ to reduce the signal and Z/γ^* background, a similar WW purity was achieved as in the ggF 2^+j category, but no benefit was seen the final analysis result. Also different combinations of top quark and WW CRs were tried with no improvement the analysis. Therefore, it was decided to not use a WW CR.

7.4.2 Top Quark Background

Since in all analysis categories b -tagging is used to reject top quark background, inverting this criterion will select events with top quarks. This approach is used to construct most CRs. In addition, looser lepton requirements $m_{\ell\ell}$ and $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ enhance the top quark background.

In the $0j$ analysis category, at least one jet below 30 GeV in transverse momentum is required to be b -tagged. This allows to keep the 0 -jet criterion for jets above 30 GeV active in the top quark CR. Furthermore, the higher invariant lepton masses typical of the $t\bar{t}$ process are allowed and the angular separations of the leptons can extend to $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell} < 2.8$. The analysis category with one jet requires the main jet to be b -tagged and maintains the b -jet veto below for jets below 30 GeV. Additionally, the $m_{\ell\ell}$ and $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ requirements are lifted.

In the 2^+j analysis categories, the background from $t\bar{t}$ events is so overwhelming that the b -tagging requirement does not necessarily need to be inverted to build a CR. This has the advantage that b -tagging uncertainties are correlated between the control and SRs and their impact is reduced. In the region targeting the ggF production mode, the top quark CR requires a dilepton mass of $m_{\ell\ell} > 80$ GeV and $m_{T2} < 165$ GeV to maintain orthogonality to the WW CR.

A similar definition of the CR was tried for the VBF -targeting analysis category, but no reduction of b -tagging uncertainties was observed. Thus, this approach was discarded and the top quark CR requires exactly one b -jet and achieves a purity of 97%. Even higher purities could be achieved by allowing events with two or more b -tags into the CR, but this would change the flavour composition of jets even more.

The top quark CRs are used to extract a normalization factor for the processes involving a top quark: Wt and $t\bar{t}$. The Wt process plays the largest role in events without jets. The corresponding CRs have a ratio of $Wt/t\bar{t}$ that is close to the SR. This ratio deviates in the 2^+j analysis categories, but the Wt contribution there is small so that this suboptimal ratio is acceptable.

7.4.3 Drell-Yan Background

In cases where the SR has a cut on the invariant di-tau mass $m_{\tau\tau}$, Z/γ^* CRs can be constructed by changing or inverting this requirement. The 0j analysis category does not have such a cut. Instead, the requirement on the opening angle between leptons is changed to $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell} > 2.8$. Additionally, the invariant lepton mass is loosened to $m_{\ell\ell} < 80$ GeV and all background rejection cuts are removed with the exception of the b -tagging requirement. For events with one jet, the cut on the collinear approximation of the di-tau mass is inverted and $m_{\ell\ell} < 80$ GeV. On top of that, the region is purified by allowing events to enter with any E_T^{miss} and any $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$.

Also the Z/γ^* CR in the 2+j analysis category inverts the $m_{\tau\tau}$ requirement. A requirement of a large $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ would benefit the purity of the CR, but mismodelling is observed and could affect the extrapolation into the SR. Hence, no cut on $\Delta\phi_{\ell\ell}$ is applied. In the VBF -targeting category, the invariant di-tau mass needs to lie within a window of 50 GeV around the Z -boson mass. A $m_{\ell\ell}$ requirement of $m_{\ell\ell} < 70$ GeV is introduced that purifies the region and brings it kinematically closer to the signal-sensitive part of the SR at high DNN values. Lastly, the m_{jj} requirement is removed.

7.5 Uncertainties

All uncertainties are grouped into three different categories: experimental uncertainties, theoretical uncertainties and statistical uncertainties. The first two groups need some explanation and are discussed in their own section below. Statistical uncertainties in this context refer to the uncertainty of the event yield due to the random nature of the underlying process. They affect both data and MC simulation. With respect to the roughly $2.9 \cdot 10^{11}$ recorded collisions in Run 2, the number of selected events is tiny. Similarly for MC simulation, a much larger number of events is generated than selected in the analysis. This justifies using Poissonian uncertainties, which are valid in the limit of a small probability of occurrence and an infinite number of trials. These uncertainties are applied to data and MC simulation separately and used in the statistical analysis.

7.5.1 Experimental Uncertainties

Experimental uncertainties refer to all effects that originate from the ATLAS detector or its simulation. These detector effects influence the reconstruction and identification of objects and their energy and momentum measurement. Also the trigger efficiencies are considered and the uncertainties of scale factors that assimilate selection efficiencies in data and MC simulation.

The experimental uncertainties are derived centrally by ATLAS for many different analyses. Their impact on the analysis result is calculated by varying parameters and reanalyzing. There are two ways in which the MC simulation can be varied. Events can be

weighted to account for an uncertainty in selection efficiencies. This affects the yields directly that are predicted by the sum of weights. Alternatively, the momenta of reconstructed particles are changed. This affects the event selection and therefore indirectly the yields. In both cases, the difference between a nominal analysis and a systematically varied analysis allows to quantify the impact of a systematic uncertainty.

The uncertainties of muons are derived in $Z \rightarrow \mu\mu$ events with a tag-and-probe method [102]. The reconstruction and identification efficiencies are limited by potential biases in the tag-and-probe method and the isolation uncertainties by the modelling of jets in MC simulation. Also uncertainties related to the variables d_0 and z_0 and the momentum scale and resolution are applied. The efficiency uncertainties of the muon trigger are applied separately for systematic and statistical uncertainties [117].

In a similar way, the uncertainties for electrons are derived in $Z \rightarrow ee$ decays [105]. The uncertainty on the energy scale of electrons is measured and found to be between 5% and 10% below 60 GeV. Furthermore, an uncertainty for the energy resolution, the reconstruction and identification as well as the isolation algorithms are derived. In the latter two, the uncertainties are large for low- p_T electrons and decrease towards higher transverse momenta. While only a few variations are considered for most systematic effects, the reconstruction and identification uncertainty is split into 17 variations to describe the uncertainty of the lengthy reconstruction procedure accurately. Also uncertainties on the trigger efficiency are considered [116].

The energy scale of jets depends on p_T , η , pile-up and the jet flavour and the uncertainty for jets with $p_T \leq 500$ GeV is driven by the different modelling of gluon jets in different MC simulations [109]. Reduction schemes allow to reduce the 125 components of uncertainty to 29 variations, that still capture the necessary correlations and dependences and are applied in this analysis. The energy resolution of jets is taken into account by smearing kinematic properties of jets with 13 variations. Also uncertainties for b -tagging [211], uncertainties related to JVT [113] and for the different pile-up distribution in data and MC simulation are considered.

The reconstruction of missing transverse energy has uncertainties that depend on the type of the considered objects [115]. Variations for the E_T^{miss} scale and resolution are taken into account. The uncertainty on the integrated luminosity of 1.7% is applied to all MC processes that do not have a normalization factor constrained in a CR [73].

For the estimate of fake events, the uncertainties have been derived in chapter 6. They are all counted as experimental uncertainties, even though the subtraction uncertainty — the most relevant uncertainty in the analysis despite the improvements in section 6.2.4 — has purely theoretical uncertainties as source. It is parametrized with one variation for each fake lepton flavour. The same is true for the flavour composition uncertainty. The statistical uncertainty is uncorrelated between different bins of the fake factor. Thus, each bin is considered separately resulting in 12 variations with only a small impact. Even

more variations are considered for the triggered fake factor, because they are split between data-taking years, but they have an even smaller impact on the final result.

7.5.2 Theoretical Uncertainties

Theoretical uncertainties describe systematic effects related to the MC simulation. Generally, uncertainties are assigned to scale parameters, the modelling of PDFs and the value of α_s , the matching procedure and the parton-shower modelling. Also process-specific uncertainties are taken into account. As is the case for experimental uncertainties, MC events can be weighted, for example for scale variations, whose impact changes the probability that an event occurs. In cases, where the uncertainty is difficult to parametrize, eg. the modelling of the parton shower and hadronization, alternative simulations are used and compared to the nominal simulation. The yield comparison in the final regions between variations and nominal simulation determines the impact of a systematic effect.

The dependence of the VBF signal process on the renormalization and factorization scales μ_R, μ_F comes from missing higher-order corrections. It is evaluated by varying them by a factor of two up and down resulting in seven configurations like described in section 6.2.5. In each bin, the largest of the seven variations is taken as the symmetrized uncertainty. To evaluate the uncertainty of α_s and the PDF model, the PDF4LHC15 [12] recommendations are followed. The PDFs are varied with 30 alternative models and the strong coupling constant is varied about its nominal value 0.118 by ± 0.0015 .

The matching uncertainty of the VBF signal sample is evaluated by comparing the two generators POWHEG BOX and MG5_aMC@NLO [212, 213]. Both of them are interfaced with HERWIG 7 [214] for the parton shower. The difference in the yields is taken as a two-sided uncertainty. In a similar way, the uncertainty due to the parton-shower and hadronization algorithm is estimated by comparing PYTHIA 8 with the nominal AZNLO tune against HERWIG 7 with its built-in UE-MMHT tune. The samples are compared after normalizing them to the same cross section, so that only acceptance and shape effects enter the uncertainty.

The ggF signal uncertainty due to the parton shower and hadronization, PDF choice and α_s value is derived equivalently to the VBF process. The typical method of estimating scale uncertainties separately in an exclusive jet selection⁵ can underestimate uncertainties of the Higgs process. The Steward-Tackmann method [215] provides a prescription to estimate uncertainties of an exclusive jet selection by only using inclusive jet selections. This approach is not prone to underestimates as for the default method. In the ggF -targeting analysis categories, variations of the nominal POWHEG BOX sample at NNLO are derived. In the VBF analysis category, the accuracy of the ggF sample is effectively only LO, which is problematic for the uncertainty estimate. Instead, a MG5_aMC@NLO ggF process is generated with

⁵An inclusive jet selection refers to a requirement selecting a minimum number of jets. In an exclusive jet selection, events with a large jet multiplicity are rejected.

two explicit jets in the final state. This sample is used with the Steward-Tackmann method for the 2^+j categories.

For the gg^F uncertainty due to the matching procedure, the nominal POWHEG BOX NNLO sample is compared to an alternative MG5_aMC@NLO version. Both are interfaced with PYTHIA and use different matching algorithms, which provides an adequate comparison for the matching uncertainty. But since the samples are not generated at the same order, the different precision of higher-order corrections increases the uncertainty estimate unintentionally. Hence, the matching uncertainty partially overlaps with the scale uncertainty from above. An alternative derivation method was not feasible and this conservative approach was tolerated.

The quark-induced WW process and the less abundant gluon-loop-induced WW process are treated separately because of their different theoretical uncertainties. The influence of the scale variation on the quark-induced WW process is evaluated like for the VBF signal. The dependence on the PDF is evaluated using 100 NNPDF3.0 replicas and the dependence on α_s by varying the nominal value by ± 0.001 as for all SHERPA samples (and already before in section 6.2.5). The MEPS@NLO method has a free merging scale parameter that is varied from 20 GeV to the alternative values 15 GeV and 30 GeV. The systematic uncertainty of the parton shower is evaluated by varying the resummation scale by a factor of two up and down and by changing the treatment of momentum recoil in SHERPA. The uncertainties of all variations related to matching and the parton shower are evaluated on MC simulation at parton level. To replicate the signal and CRs, the analysis cuts are redefined for particle properties at parton level. Also another DNN is trained with the same hyperparameters as the nominal version to mimic the SR definition despite the different inputs.

The $gg \rightarrow WW$ process is simulated at LO with up to one additional parton emission. Thus, this sample only populates the two-jet phase space if at least one jet is generated in the parton shower. Because of the large dependence on the parton shower algorithm, the process yield is varied up and down by a factor of two to obtain its uncertainty. In the zero and one-jet phase space, the dominant source of uncertainties come from higher-order corrections. The corresponding scale uncertainties are estimated with the MATRIX framework based theory predictions in Ref. [216]. The scale corrections from LO to NLO are used as an uncertainty. It was found that these uncertainties only affect the result marginally due to the small contribution of the $gg \rightarrow WW$ process.

For the $t\bar{t}$ and single-top quark background, additional radiation is affected by the typical renormalization and factorization scales as well as the h_{damp} variable. All three variables are varied in two distinct configurations while using a variation of the A14 tune. This procedure is explained in more detail in Ref. [154] under “improved generator setups”. The uncertainty due to the PDF is estimated with the 100 alternative NNPDF3.0NLO sets. The uncertainty due to the choice of MC generator and matching procedure is estimated by comparing the nominal generator POWHEG BOX to MG5_aMC@NLO and using PYTHIA for the parton shower in both cases. Similarly, the parton shower uncertainty is derived by swapping out the nominal PYTHIA algorithm for the alternative HERWIG program. For both the matching

and parton shower uncertainties, the fast calorimeter simulation Atfast-II [217] is used. An additional uncertainty is applied for the diagram removal method applied to avoid double-counting of Feynman diagrams.

The uncertainties of the Z/γ^* background related to the scale choice, PDF and α_s are estimated as described before for SHERPA samples. The matching and parton shower uncertainties are derived by comparing the nominal sample against a sample generated with MG5_aMC@NLO interfaced with PYTHIA using the A14 tune and symmetrizing the combined effect. For technical reasons, the alternative generator and shower algorithms are used to derive the uncertainties rather than the typical SHERPA variations.

The $W+\gamma$ process, that is not constrained in a dedicated CR, is assigned an uncertainty determined by varying the yields up and down by a factor of two. The factor of two was chosen as a conservative estimate of the disagreement between data and MC simulation in a validation region enriched in $W+\gamma$. This disagreement is caused by the large uncertainty associated with the conversion of photons.

7.6 Statistical Analysis

First, the statistical framework that is used to quantify the analysis result is reviewed. The description mostly follows Refs. [108, 218] with some notation based on Ref. [219]. Then, an overview is given of how the uncertainties from the previous section are included.

7.6.1 Statistical Framework

To describe the agreement between data and prediction while considering uncertainties, a likelihood function is defined. The likelihood is mathematically identical to the probability to observe n data events given the model parameters μ, θ :

$$L(\mu, \theta | n) = P(n | \mu, \theta). \quad (7.12)$$

But the interpretation is different, because the likelihood assesses how well the model parameters match the data, not vice versa. In the maximum likelihood method, the best model parameters for the observed data are the ones that maximize the likelihood. The idea behind this procedure is intuitive when considering two competing models μ_1, θ_1 and μ_2, θ_2 . If the probability to observe the data under model μ_1, θ_1 is greater than under model μ_2, θ_2 , then it is more plausible to conclude μ_1, θ_1 from the data than μ_2, θ_2 .

In practice, the variable θ in the previous notation is multi-dimensional and describes many model parameters — one for each uncertainty listed in the previous section⁶. They are referred to as nuisance parameters (NPs). The parameter μ has been singled out, because

⁶To keep the notation readable, the variable θ refers to the entire set of nuisance parameters. When an index is used, only one specific nuisance parameter is considered. This also applies to the subset of nuisance parameters β .

it is the parameter of interest indicating the amount of signal. It multiplies the predicted signal yield and is therefore expected to be $\mu = 1$ in the Standard Model. This can be seen in the first term of the likelihood

$$L_1(\mu, \theta | n_j) = f_P(n_j | \mu s_j + \beta b_j) \quad (7.13)$$

$$= \frac{(\mu s_j + \beta b_j)^{n_j}}{n_j} e^{-\mu s_j - \beta b_j}, \quad (7.14)$$

that describes the Poisson probability f_P to observe n_j events in a bin j , when expecting s_j signal events and b_j background events. Implicitly, the parameters s_j and b_j depend on the model parameters θ , because the uncertainties affect the predicted yields. The signal and background expectations are scaled by normalization factors μ and β , respectively⁷.

An additional complication is that the signal and background expectations s_j , b_j are not exactly known, because also the MC simulation is subject to statistical fluctuations. The general treatment is to distinguish the true yields s_j , b_j from the simulated ones \tilde{s}_j , \tilde{b}_j and treat them as nuisance parameters [220]. This results in one nuisance parameter per process and bin with a Poissonian constraint. To reduce the complexity to one nuisance parameter γ_j per bin, one assumes that the combined statistical uncertainty in a bin is Gaussian [221] and replaces $\mu s_j + \beta b_j = \gamma_j(\mu \tilde{s}_j + \beta \tilde{b}_j)$. The corresponding term for bin j in the likelihood is

$$L_2(\mu, \theta | n_j) = f_P(\mu \tilde{s}_j | \mu s_j) f_P(\beta \tilde{b}_j | \beta b_j) \quad (7.15)$$

$$\approx f_G(\mu \tilde{s}_j + \beta \tilde{b}_j | \mu s_j + \beta b_j) \quad (7.16)$$

$$= f_G(\mu \tilde{s}_j + \beta \tilde{b}_j | \gamma_j(\mu \tilde{s}_j + \beta \tilde{b}_j)) \quad (7.17)$$

with the Gaussian constraint f_G , whose uncertainty is given by the quadrature sum of individual uncertainties.

Prior information about the nuisance parameters θ comes from the uncertainty estimates in section 7.5. They can be viewed as auxiliary measurements. The information is included in the likelihood with a term constraining the nuisance parameters $L_3(\theta_j) = C(\theta_j)$. The constraint $C(\theta_j)$ is typically a Gaussian function with the mean and width given by the uncertainty estimate. The normalization parameters μ and β do not have an explicit constraint, because they are strongly constrained by equation (7.14) in the corresponding CR.

⁷Technically, backgrounds b_i from different processes i are included separately in the likelihood term L_1 . They have their own normalization factors β_i and are summed over (just like signal and background are added). To keep the notation light, this detail is omitted in the equations.

The final likelihood includes information about the prediction and the data in the SRs and the CRs

$$L(\mu, \theta) \equiv L(\mu, \theta | n) = \prod_j^{\text{bins}} L_1(\mu, \theta | n_j) L_2(\mu, \theta | n_j) \prod_j^{\text{NPs}} L_3(\theta_j). \quad (7.18)$$

It contains all the statistical information needed for the signal extraction. Let $\hat{\mu}$, $\hat{\theta}$ be the parameters that maximize the likelihood and $\hat{\hat{\theta}}$ the parameters that maximize the profile likelihood $L(\mu, \hat{\theta})$ for a given μ . Then the profile likelihood ratio is defined as

$$\lambda(\mu) = \frac{L(\mu, \hat{\theta})}{L(\hat{\mu}, \hat{\hat{\theta}})}. \quad (7.19)$$

It is used in the test statistic $t_\mu = -2 \ln(\lambda(\mu))$ to evaluate the plausibility of a null hypothesis, where μ is fixed to a specific value, with respect to the best-fit hypothesis with $\hat{\mu}$. If the probability distribution $p(t_\mu)$ of t_μ is known under the assumption that the null hypothesis is true⁸, then the p-value can be calculated as

$$p = \int_{t_{\text{obs}}}^{\infty} p(t_\mu) dt. \quad (7.20)$$

It specifies how likely it is to observe a fluctuation from the null hypothesis as great as or greater than the observed value t_{obs} . A p-value of less than $2.89 \cdot 10^{-7}$ corresponds to a fluctuation in a Gaussian distribution of more than 5σ assuming a one-sided Gaussian limit. This is customarily considered the threshold for a signal discovery under the null hypothesis $\mu = 0$.

The uncertainties of any model parameter in the best-fit scenario can be estimated by constructing the likelihood ratio as in equation (7.19), but fixing the corresponding model parameter instead of μ . With the same reasoning as above, confidence level intervals can be estimated. Using the same test statistic t_θ for the parameter θ as above and assuming that it is χ^2 -distributed, then the borders θ' of the confidence interval with confidence level α interval are determined from the condition

$$t_{\theta'} = F_{\chi^2}^{-1}(1 - \alpha, n_{\text{DOF}}). \quad (7.21)$$

The distribution $F_{\chi^2}^{-1}$ is the inverse of the cumulative distribution function of the χ^2 distribution and n_{DOF} counts parameters that are varied in θ' with respect to θ . This number is often 1, but can vary when a multi-dimensional parameter scan is performed like in Figure 7.10.

⁸The probability distribution $p(t_\mu)$ approaches in the asymptotic limit of infinite data the χ^2 distribution [222]. Alternatively, the distribution can be obtained with pseudo experiments.

7.6.2 Treatment of Uncertainties

For each source of uncertainty, a nuisance parameter is introduced and its influence is evaluated for every process and in every region by considering the up- and down variations. The effect of an uncertainty is decomposed into a normalization component that only changes the yield and a shape component that leaves the yield unchanged. These two components are parametrized with the same nuisance parameter, but exceptions exist.

When a single source of uncertainty affects multiple processes or regions, it is reasonable to treat these effects as 100 % correlated. This is important when the same model parameters describe multiple processes or regions. As an example for correlated uncertainties across different regions, consider background normalization factors that are mostly constrained in CRs. These regions are typically quite similar to their corresponding SRs and therefore systematic uncertainties have a similar effect. If a systematic uncertainty affects the background prediction in the SR and CR in the same way, the freely floating normalization factor absorbs this effect completely. Thus, the normalization effect of the uncertainty does not affect the SR anymore, because it is effectively measured in the CR.

Contrary to the prescription above, the nuisance parameters related to theoretical background uncertainties are decorrelated between analysis categories. In the same way the normalization factors are decorrelated. The reason is that a single source of uncertainty can have a different effect in different analysis categories, often caused by the jet multiplicity. This is particularly clear, when an uncertainty is estimated differently between analysis categories. Thus, the approach focuses on providing an accurate and flexible background prediction. For signal processes, however, it is important to provide a consistent description of the signal model throughout the entire analysis in order to extract a common signal strength. Hence, theory nuisance parameters of the signal are 100 % correlated between analysis categories.

Where variations seem to have a physical origin, but cannot be estimated reliably due to statistical uncertainties of a MC sample, uncertainties can be estimated in combined regions: Different regions are merged into larger regions during the extraction of uncertainties. In the analysis, the uncertainties from the combined region are applied in each individual region separately. This is particularly helpful in the analysis categories targeting the ggF process, where the SRs are split in subregions depending on $m_{\ell\ell}$ and $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}}$. Merging these subregions enhances the statistics and allows to estimate systematic uncertainties more reliably.

Uncertainties of the matching procedure or the generator are often taken by comparing a nominal sample against an alternative one. This procedure results in a one-sided uncertainty that is symmetrized to obtain a two-sided model. If an uncertainty is inherently two-sided, like scale uncertainties, and it has normalization components that differ by more than a factor of two, the larger of the two variations is taken and symmetrized to avoid numerical problems during the likelihood maximization and underconstraints.

The uncertainties on the fake factor were derived in section 6.2 and the results are listed in Table 6.3. The three sources of uncertainty are considered separately. The statistical uncertainties are independent in each fake factor bin and are therefore not correlated. The MC subtraction uncertainties have the same origin in different bins and are therefore correlated. The same applies to the uncertainties due to the sample composition.

The procedure of propagating uncertainties can lead to cases where nuisance parameters have a small impact on the likelihood model or affect the model in an unphysical way. It is desirable to remove these cases to improve the fit complexity and stability, while confirming that the change has a negligible impact. General rules are:

- Normalization uncertainties are neglected if their relative impact is $< 0.1\%$.
- Normalization uncertainties are neglected if their relative impact is $> 80\%$. This is only applied in regions and for processes with small yields, where the unreasonable variations are likely caused by statistical uncertainties of the MC simulation. In all cases, the impact on the final result is negligible.
- Normalization uncertainties are neglected if their relative impact is $< 0.2\sigma_{\text{stat}}$, where σ_{stat} is the statistical fluctuation of the MC simulation. This is only applied to uncertainties estimated with four-vector variations, where migrations between neighbouring bins and regions can cause statistical fluctuations.
- Shape uncertainties are neglected if they agree with the nominal distribution well within statistical uncertainties and their p -value is $p > 0.95$.
- Experimental shape uncertainties are neglected for the processes Z/γ^* , single top, other diboson, other Higgs, because the statistical uncertainty dominates.

Despite all these general rules, in practice every uncertainty needs to be considered separately and a reasonable treatment needs to be found. There are a few special cases that are not listed here explicitly, for example decorrelated parameters or neglected shape uncertainties.

7.6.3 Fit Procedure

One goal of the statistical analysis is to measure from data the signal strength parameters for ggF and VBF , that are defined by

$$\mu = \frac{\sigma_{\text{measured}}}{\sigma_{\text{Standard Model}}}. \quad (7.22)$$

To find the best model simultaneously in all SRs and CRs, the parameter μ is split into two, μ_{ggF} and μ_{VBF} . Both of these are treated as unconstrained parameters of interest in a profile likelihood fit. In the ggF -targeting analysis categories, data in the SRs are binned in $m_{T,H}$ with bin boundaries at $\{0, 90, 100, 110, 120, 130, \infty\}$ GeV and used as input to the likelihood function. The DNN discriminant provides the input for the VBF analysis category

and is binned with the binning algorithm in section 7.3. The final bin boundaries have no physical meaning, but are listed here for comparison with the later STXS analyses: $\{0, 0.25, 0.59, 0.73, 0.83, 0.89, 0.93, 1\}$. The bin below 0.25 is enriched in background and effectively acts like a CR with a mix of processes.

The corresponding cross sections are measured by letting the cross sections of the two production modes float in the fit. Using the definition in equation (7.22), the cross section can also be determined from the signal strength. However, the uncertainties are different, because the uncertainties of $\sigma_{\text{Standard Model}}$ do not affect the measurement of σ_{measured} . To take this into account, the signal theory uncertainties are rederived. The effect of all uncertainties is split into two components: a cross-section and an acceptance component. The former category includes normalization effects of the MC sample at particle level. Acceptance components refer to all normalization and shape effects emerging from the detector acceptance or analysis cuts. Cross-section components of the signal theory uncertainties are not considered in cross-section measurements.

A second fit is performed to determine how compatible the data are with the null-hypothesis that the VBF process does not exist in the Standard Model. For this test, the signal strength μ_{VBF} is forced to 0. The signal strength μ_{ggF} is left unchanged and effectively acts as a background normalization factor constrained by the other analysis categories. The procedure of equation (7.20) is followed to extract a significance.

7.7 Results

After the likelihood maximization is performed, the best-fit values for all parameters in the likelihood are used to build the post-fit model. The corresponding yields are listed in Table 7.5 for all SRs. Splits of SRs in $m_{\ell\ell}$ and $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}}$ are not reflected in this table and the individual subregions are merged. The sum of all process yields in a region is compared to the observed data and shows very good agreement. Because the likelihood procedure uses data to constrain the total yield, the yields of the individual processes become anti-correlated. Hence, the uncertainties cannot be added in quadrature to obtain the total uncertainty.

The fit variables in the SRs are shown in Figure 7.9. For visualization purposes, a finer binning is shown in the $m_{T,H}$ distribution than is used in the fit, which affects the regions below 90 GeV and above 130 GeV. Larger discrepancies can therefore be seen here, because of the missing flexibility in the fit model. Furthermore, shape uncertainties are not included in the hashed uncertainty band. Nevertheless, the good agreement that is seen in Table 7.5 is confirmed in these distributions. The only noteworthy exception is the bin between 70 GeV and 80 GeV in the 0j SR. The DNN output variable is shown for the VBF SR and also shows good modelling.

Figure 7.9: Distributions of the post-fit fit variables in the four unsplit SRs [127]. The regions targeting the ggF production mode are shown in (a) for the 0j category, (b) for the 1j category and (c) for the 2+j category. In (d) the VBF SR is displayed. Post-fit uncertainties on the total prediction are shown as a hatched band. The middle panel shows the ratio of data over the prediction, and the bottom one highlights the signal by subtracting the background estimate from the total yield. In (d) the bottom panel is additionally divided by the background yield. In the $m_{T,H}$ distributions, under- and overflow are included in the first and last bins.

Process	0j ggF	1j ggF	2+j ggF	2+j VBF	
				Inclusive	DNN > 0.93
H_{ggF}	2150 ± 220	1100 ± 150	470 ± 100	180 ± 70	2.0 ± 1.0
H_{VBF}	24 ± 6	107 ± 24	50 ± 12	200 ± 40	40 ± 7
Other Higgs	34 ± 1	49 ± 1	47 ± 2	27 ± 2	0.1 ± 0.0
WW	9800 ± 400	3400 ± 500	1500 ± 500	2100 ± 400	5.3 ± 2.1
$t\bar{t}/Wt$	2130 ± 210	5400 ± 400	6100 ± 500	7600 ± 400	3.1 ± 1.0
Z/γ^*	140 ± 50	280 ± 40	930 ± 70	1410 ± 340	1.2 ± 0.6
Other VV	1380 ± 130	850 ± 100	440 ± 90	360 ± 80	0.5 ± 0.1
Mis-Id	1170 ± 130	740 ± 90	480 ± 50	340 ± 40	2.3 ± 0.3
Total	$16\,770 \pm 130$	$11\,940 \pm 110$	$10\,040 \pm 100$	$12\,200 \pm 120$	54 ± 6
Observed	16 726	11 917	9 982	12 189	60

Table 7.5: Post-fit MC yields in the SRs compared to observed data [127]. For the VBF SR, the purest DNN bin is shown in addition to the inclusive SR. The presented yields and uncertainties are rounded, which can give the appearance of incorrect summation. The uncertainties include all statistical and systematic effects described in earlier sections.

Figure 7.10: Likelihood contours of the ggF and VBF cross-section measurements [127]. The brown contour corresponds to the 68% and the green line to the 95% confidence level. The Standard Model prediction is shown in red for comparison.

After the fit, the values of the signal strength parameters are found to be

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_{\text{ggF}} &= 1.20^{+0.16}_{-0.15} \\ &= 1.20 \pm 0.05 \text{ (stat)}^{+0.09}_{-0.08} \text{ (exp)}^{+0.10}_{-0.08} \text{ (sig theo)}^{+0.12}_{-0.11} \text{ (bkg theo)},\end{aligned}\quad (7.23)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_{\text{VBF}} &= 0.99^{+0.24}_{-0.20} \\ &= 0.99^{+0.13}_{-0.12} \text{ (stat)}^{+0.07}_{-0.06} \text{ (exp)}^{+0.17}_{-0.12} \text{ (sig theo)}^{+0.10}_{-0.08} \text{ (bkg theo)}.\end{aligned}\quad (7.24)$$

The breakdown into groups of uncertainties is calculated by comparing the nominal, unconditional fit with a conditional fit. In the latter one, the group of nuisance parameters, whose impact on the uncertainty is to be estimated, is fixed to their best-fit values. Then, the uncertainty of this group of nuisance parameters is estimated by the quadrature difference between the uncertainty of the unconditional and conditional fit. This procedure is applied in parallel for all groups of uncertainty. Due to the correlation effect explained above, the resulting group uncertainties do not add in quadrature to the total uncertainty⁹.

In the ggF analysis, the statistical uncertainty is small, while the three other groups all have a similar impact. The experimental uncertainties (exp) include also the statistical uncertainty of the MC simulation and the uncertainty of the normalization factors. The signal theory (sig theo) uncertainties include both the ggF and VBF processes and the background theory uncertainties (bkg theo) all others. After being statistically limited in analyses with less than 139/fb, the statistical uncertainty in this VBF analysis is smaller than the systematic ones for the first time. The signal theory uncertainties mostly originate from the VBF process, but also have a large contribution from ggF .

The cross section for Higgs-boson production combined with the branching ratio for $H \rightarrow WW^*$ is measured to be

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{\text{ggF}} \mathcal{B}_{H \rightarrow WW^*} &= 12.4 \pm 1.5 \text{ pb} \\ &= 12.4 \pm 0.6 \text{ (stat)} \pm 0.9 \text{ (exp)}^{+0.7}_{-0.6} \text{ (sig theo)} \pm 1.0 \text{ (bkg theo)} \text{ pb},\end{aligned}\quad (7.25)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{\text{VBF}} \mathcal{B}_{H \rightarrow WW^*} &= 0.79^{+0.19}_{-0.16} \text{ pb} \\ &= 0.79^{+0.11}_{-0.10} \text{ (stat)}^{+0.06}_{-0.05} \text{ (exp)}^{+0.13}_{-0.09} \text{ (sig theo)}^{+0.08}_{-0.06} \text{ (bkg theo)} \text{ pb}.\end{aligned}\quad (7.26)$$

These measured cross sections compare to their theory values $10.4 \text{ pb} \pm 0.6 \text{ pb}$ and $0.81 \text{ pb} \pm 0.02 \text{ pb}$ [20] like the signal strengths compare to 1. Also the uncertainties are similar to the uncertainties on the signal strength parameters. A more detailed breakdown can be found in Table 7.6. It emphasizes that the systematic uncertainties are dominated by the theoretical uncertainties with the largest contribution from the respective signal process. The next-largest group of uncertainty contains experimental effects, followed by background normalization and limited MC statistics.

⁹An alternative decomposition procedure can be found in Ref [51]. It has the advantage that group uncertainties add in quadrature to the total uncertainty. On the downside, the breakdown depends on the order in which groups of uncertainties are processed.

Source	$\frac{\Delta\sigma_{\text{ggF}}\cdot\mathcal{B}_{H\rightarrow WW^*}}{\sigma_{\text{ggF}}\cdot\mathcal{B}_{H\rightarrow WW^*}}$ [%]	$\frac{\Delta\sigma_{\text{VBF}}\cdot\mathcal{B}_{H\rightarrow WW^*}}{\sigma_{\text{VBF}}\cdot\mathcal{B}_{H\rightarrow WW^*}}$ [%]
Data statistical uncertainties	5	13
Total systematic uncertainties	11	18
MC statistical uncertainties	4	3.2
Experimental uncertainties	6	7
Flavour Tagging	2.4	0.9
Jet energy scale	1.4	3.3
Jet energy resolution	2.3	1.9
Missing transverse energy	1.9	5
Muons	2.1	0.7
Electrons	1.5	0.3
Fake factors	2.4	1.0
Pile-up	2.4	1.3
Luminosity	2.0	2.1
Theoretical uncertainties	8	16
ggF	5	4
VBF	0.7	13
Top	4	5
Z/γ^*	2.0	2.1
WW	4	5
Other VV	3	1.2
Background normalisations	5	5
WW	3.1	0.5
Top	2.4	2.2
$Z\tau\tau$	3.1	4
TOTAL	12	22

Table 7.6: Breakdown of uncertainties for the cross-section measurement [127]. For easier readability, the uncertainties have been symmetrized.

In the context of this thesis, it is worth highlighting that the uncertainties from the fake estimate are small — not only compared to the theory uncertainties, but also compared to the previous publication [55], where the fake estimate constituted the single largest experimental uncertainty. This is in part caused by the increased size of the dataset, but also by the various improvements: the muon extrapolation factor, the loosening of working points reducing data and MC statistical uncertainties and a bugfix in the MC generation that reduces the normalization uncertainty on WZ .

Figure 7.10 shows the contours of the 1σ and 2σ confidence level for the ggF and VBF cross section measurement. The theory value is on the edge of the 1σ confidence region confirming that the measurement agrees well with the theory prediction. The plotted contours indicate that there is very little correlation in the cross-section measurements of the two processes. The reason is that the contamination of the ggF SR with the VBF process is negligible.

Figure 7.11: Event display of a VBF candidate event with two jets. The two forward jets are shown as green and red cones in the $r\phi$ view in the top left and the rz view in the bottom. The muon in turquoise and electron in yellow are close in ϕ . The transverse energy of the objects can be seen on the right-hand side ranging from 22 GeV for the electron to 77 GeV for the leading jet. The invariant dijet mass is 1.48 TeV, and the event has a DNN score of 0.91.

The compatibility of the data with the background-only hypothesis is estimated. For this test, the VBF signal strength is set to 0 and the p -value is calculated. It corresponds to an observed significance of 6.6σ with an expected significance of 6.1σ . This constitutes the first observation of the VBF -induced $H \rightarrow WW^*$ process. Figure 7.11 shows a typical event with a VBF signature. The event has a DNN score of 0.91 and exhibits the characteristic signatures with close-by leptons and a large invariant dijet mass.

Chapter 8

HWW STXS Analysis

The goal of an STXS analysis is to measure cross sections of fiducial volumes of the Higgs boson process in a standardized way to facilitate combinations of different decay channels. To this end, the signal process is split into fiducial categories using conditions on kinematic and topological variables related to the production mechanism. All of these Simplified Template Cross Sections (STXS) are measured individually. Since the cross-section definitions are standardized and since the measurements are not interpreted at this stage, the measurements can be combined between different analyses and experiments¹.

The STXS analysis is very similar to the HWW analysis in the previous chapter. The differences are listed in section 8.1 and the results are shown in section 8.2.

8.1 Adjustments for STXS

The signal processes are divided according to the production mechanism [56]. In higher order diagrams, ambiguities between production modes occur. To resolve these, the VBF production mode and the VH production mode with a hadronically decaying vector boson are combined to EW qqH . Similarly, the ggF process is combined with the gluon-induced ZH process, where the Z boson decays hadronically. They are called ggH . Other Higgs processes are considered as background, namely VH with a leptonic vector-boson decay, $t\bar{t}H$, $b\bar{b}H$, tH .

Each production mode is split into STXS categories² that are defined using variables sensitive to the production mechanism. The STXS scheme distinguishes between events with 0 jets, 1 jet and 2 or more jets, because most experimental analyses divide the events according to the number of jets. Furthermore, the transverse momentum of the Higgs boson $p_{T,H}$ is used to measure the amount of recoil. Events with high $p_{T,H}$ are particularly sensitive to effects beyond the Standard Model and are combined into one category independently of

¹Recall also the motivation for STXS measurements at the end of section 2.2.3.

²The relevant categorization scheme (stage 1.2) has not been published. Refer to the figures in Appendix D.1 for an overview.

Figure 8.1: Reduced STXS categories used in the HWW analysis (left) and SRs defined to measure the cross section of these processes (right) [127]. For the ggH and $EW qqH$ processes, arrows lead to the category names and show the applied fiducial cuts. On the right-hand side, all events are first classified by the number of jets, which implicitly applies all corresponding signal-region cuts (the OLV and CJV are listed explicitly to highlight orthogonality). Further cuts lead to the STXS SRs that are coloured according to the targeted STXS category. The variables on the left-hand side are defined at particle level and on the right-hand side at reconstruction level.

the number of jets. The variable $p_{T,Hjj}$ measures the transverse momentum of the combined system of the Higgs boson and the two leading jets. It is sensitive to the amount of additional radiation beyond the second jet. Finally, the invariant dijet mass m_{jj} is relevant for the $EW qqH$ production mode, because of the two forward jets in VBF .

This analysis takes the STXS stage 1.2 scheme as a basis and merges categories as needed for experimental sensitivity. The resulting categorization is called “reduced stage 1.2” and is shown on the left-hand side of Figure 8.1. The right-hand side of this figure summarizes the SRs that are optimized to measure the STXS categories on the left-hand side. All SRs are based on the region definitions in the sections 7.2 and 7.4. They are constructed with variables at reconstruction level that resemble the particle-level variables used for the STXS categories. The m_{jj} is defined at reconstruction level as the invariant mass of the two highest- p_T jets like previously, the transverse Higgs-boson momentum as $p_{T,H} = |\vec{p}_{T,\ell}^{\text{lead}} + \vec{p}_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}} + \vec{E}_T^{\text{miss}}|$.

In deviation from the suggestions in the STXS 1.2 definitions, the ggH 0-jet process is not split at $p_{T,H} = 10$ GeV. The reason is that the 10 GeV window is difficult to resolve, because of the two neutrinos in the final state and the uncertainties in the \vec{E}_T^{miss} reconstruction. Higgs bosons in the ggH 0-jet process experience a small amount of recoil and therefore have a much smaller transverse momentum than 200 GeV. Thus, the STXS 0-jet categorization is effectively the same as in the total cross-section measurement. Hence, the SRs and CRs remain unchanged.

In the 1-jet phase space, the ggH events with $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV are split into three categories depending on $p_{T,H}$. This division is equivalently reproduced in the SRs. In order to maintain an acceptable number of events in these SRs, the events are not split by $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}}$ and $m_{\ell\ell}$.

For the ggH process with two or more jets, the STXS 1.2 scheme defines a fine splitting using $p_{T,H}$, $p_{T,Hjj}$ and m_{jj} , which is difficult to realize experimentally. The division into m_{jj} categories is particularly challenging, because these events are very similar to the equivalent EW qqH events so that the cross-section measurements are highly correlated. To provide a robust cross-section measurement without large correlations, all ggH components with more than one jet and $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV are merged into one single category. The corresponding SRs are identical to the total cross-section measurement with the exception that events with large $p_{T,H}$ are split off.

All ggH events with $p_{T,H} > 200$ GeV have been excluded in the previous categorization. They are combined into their own STXS category. This category is targeted by multiple SRs, one in the 1j and two in the 2⁺j phase space. These SRs are split by the number of jets due to the design of the total cross-section measurement.

To provide a dedicated background estimate in the various ggF SRs, also CRs need to be redefined. Since the 0j reconstruction is unchanged, also the CRs remain the same. In the 1j and 2⁺j phase space, the division of SRs is exactly replicated by the CRs. Whenever a SR applies a cut on $p_{T,H}$, the same requirement is set in the three corresponding CRs.

For the EW qqH process, only events with $m_{jj} > 350$ GeV are considered in the reduced STXS 1.2 scheme due to the challenging distinction between VBF and ggF at smaller invariant masses. After splitting off events with $p_{T,H} > 200$ GeV, the remaining events are grouped into four categories according to m_{jj} . The same split is also used in the SRs with the reconstruction-level m_{jj} variable. Due to the limited background statistics in the phase space with two forward jets, the CRs are not split as finely as the SRs. The low- $p_{T,H}$ SR with $350 \text{ GeV} < m_{jj} < 700 \text{ GeV}$ and the high- $p_{T,H}$ SR have dedicated CRs with corresponding selection requirements. The other three SRs share one set of CRs defined by $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV and $m_{jj} > 700$ GeV. The normalization factors in all control regions are listed in Appendix D.2.

Figure 8.2 gives an overview of the expected signal composition in the SRs. It shows that most SRs resolve the corresponding STXS process very well. One exception is the 1j SR at very low $p_{T,H}$, that observes large migration from 0-jet ggH events. At low invariant

Figure 8.2: Signal composition in the STXS SRs [127]. All SRs are listed on the y -axis. For each of them, the horizontally-stacked histogram shows the contribution of each STXS signal process as a fraction of the total amount of signal. SRs that only differ by a $m_{\ell\ell}$ and $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}}$ requirement are merged.

dijet masses, the VBF SRs are contaminated by ggH events. However, the DNN is able to disentangle well the events of different origin, which simplifies the signal extraction.

It was considered to optimize the DNN for each SR separately, but different studies indicated that this approach would only give a marginal improvement. Thus, the same DNN definition as in the total cross-section measurement is used in all VBF SRs. In the SR with $350 \text{ GeV} < m_{jj} < 700 \text{ GeV}$, the binning algorithm finds bin boundaries at $\{0, 0.27, 0.5, 0.84, 1\}$. When processing the other four SRs, the suggested binning by the algorithm is very similar. It is therefore harmonized³ between the four regions to $\{0, 0.5, 0.74, 0.87, 1\}$. The SRs aiming to constrain the ggH process use the $m_{T,H}$ variable in the fit with the same binning as before: $\{0, 90, 100, 110, 120, 130, \infty\} \text{ GeV}$.

In all SRs and CRs, the systematic uncertainties are estimated following the same procedure as in section 7.6.2. The signal uncertainties are calculated separately for all STXS categories and only acceptance uncertainties are considered. All signal processes that do not fall into any STXS category are treated together. Because the cross section of these signal processes is not measured in the fit, both cross-section and acceptance uncertainties are considered. Since the processes are split into smaller categories and distributed across more regions, the statistical precision is more problematic than in the total cross-section measurement. Hence, more uncertainties are estimated in combined STXS regions and

³Choosing the same binning simplifies the estimation of uncertainties in combined regions. This procedure was introduced in section 7.6.2.

applied to exclusive regions. In some cases, also smoothing procedures are used to reduce statistical fluctuations in shape uncertainties.

The fit procedure from the total cross-section measurement is adjusted to accommodate the eleven STXS signal categories as well as the 17 SRs and 27 CRs. One unconstrained parameter of interest is introduced per STXS category and used to extract the corresponding cross section. Similarly, the number of unconstrained nuisance parameters is increased with the number of CRs to normalize the backgrounds. All STXS categories that are not explicitly considered in the reduced STXS scheme are fixed to the Standard Model prediction. They are given appropriate uncertainties and the corresponding nuisance parameters are combined across analysis categories.

8.2 Results

The post-fit distributions of the VBF^4 SRs are shown in Figure 8.3. The DNN output is most sensitive to the signal at high values close to 1. In each signal region, three signal components are shown. The specific target category that the SR is designed to purify, the remaining EW qqH categories and the ggH categories. The data agrees very well with the fit model. A comparison of the different SRs highlights clearly how important the m_{jj} variable is in the identification of VBF processes. In contrast to the signal composition overview in Figure 8.2, these distributions show that the high DNN bins have a high proportion of VBF events⁵.

The cross section of the low- m_{jj} VBF category is measured to be negative. While negative cross sections are not physical, they are allowed in the likelihood maximization. This treatment avoids a bias in later combinations. Such a bias would originate if fluctuations causing negative cross sections are cut off, but fluctuations causing large positive cross sections are allowed. It is worth mentioning that even with the negative cross section of one category, the post-fit contribution of the total HWW process remains positive in all SRs.

The extracted cross section values are listed in Appendix D.4 for completeness. The comparison of all extracted cross sections with the prediction is illustrated in Figure 8.4. Most measurements agree well with the Standard Model expectation. With eleven parameters of interest, a few outliers are expected. The consistency with the Standard Model is confirmed by the p -value of 0.52, which indicates that the measurement is consistent with the Standard Model assumption.

The measured ggF signal strength in equation (7.23) can be compared to the cross-section ratios of the STXS categories and show very good agreement. In fact, the near-perfect agreement of the uncertainties in the ggH 0j STXS cross section with equation (7.23) is a

⁴For the corresponding ggF SRs, see Appendix D.3.

⁵For direct comparison with the pre-fit composition in Figure 8.2, one should revert the scaling of the target cross section. In this case, the highest DNN bins would all be dominated by the target process.

coincidence and not necessarily expected. When comparing the VBF signal strength close to unity in equation (7.24) with the STXS cross sections, the agreement seems less obvious. The small cross sections in the SRs with $350 \text{ GeV} < m_{jj} < 1000 \text{ GeV}$ have a smaller impact on the total cross-section measurement than the high- m_{jj} events, because they are given different importance by the DNN discriminant.

For the ggH cross sections, systematic uncertainties tend to dominate over statistical ones. The 1j category with $120 \text{ GeV} < p_{T,H} < 200 \text{ GeV}$ and the high- $p_{T,H}$ category are exceptions. For the EW qqH cross sections, statistical uncertainties dominate the measurement except in the $350 \text{ GeV} < m_{jj} < 700 \text{ GeV}$ category. More details about each of these can be extracted from breakdowns of uncertainties (cf. Ref. [127]). A visual and less detailed breakdown is also shown in Figure 8.5.

Given that the zero-jet STXS category is the dominant process in the total cross-section measurement, it has similar uncertainties as shown in Table 7.6. For the one-jet STXS categories, the theoretical uncertainties of the background processes limit the measurement more than the experimental ones. Mainly the top quark and WW processes are responsible with the WW contribution shrinking as a function of $p_{T,H}$. Also the background normalization of the WW process plays a leading role. In the ggH 2⁺j category, the top quark process is ubiquitous, which is reflected in the large impact of its theoretical and normalization uncertainty. The ggH cross section with $p_{T,H} > 200 \text{ GeV}$ has fairly balanced systematic uncertainties. An improvement of the data statistics in the future will also reduce large uncertainties related to the Z/γ^* normalization.

For the VBF components in the EW qqH process, a distinction between low- m_{jj} and high- m_{jj} needs to be made. With a lower dijet mass, the theoretical uncertainties related to ggF gain relevance. This needs to be considered for a future extension of the measurement into the $120 \text{ GeV} < m_{jj} < 350 \text{ GeV}$ phase space. An even better discrimination between the ggF and VBF production modes would help to reduce these uncertainties. In the phase space of $m_{jj} > 1000 \text{ GeV}$, the statistical uncertainty is currently the limiting factor and no systematic uncertainty stands out in particular.

Figure 8.4: Cross sections for each STXS category divided by the Standard Model prediction [127]. Statistical and systematic uncertainties are shown separately as coloured bars and their combination is given by the length of the uncertainty bar. The theory uncertainty on the Standard Model cross-section prediction is shown as shaded, grey band.

Figure 8.5: Breakdown of the total uncertainty on each STXS measurement into components related to statistical, background theoretical, signal theoretical, experimental and Standard Model uncertainties [127]. The breakdown components are quoted as uncertainty relative to the Standard Model prediction.

Chapter 9

Conclusion and Outlook

The ATLAS Run 2 dataset is a valuable resource to study the Higgs boson. The dataset is analyzed in this thesis to measure the cross section of Higgs-boson production and the subsequent decay into two W bosons. The two production modes ggF and VBF are considered with a focus on the VBF analysis. The measured values

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{ggF} \mathcal{B}_{H \rightarrow WW^*} &= 12.4 \pm 1.5 \text{ pb}, \\ \sigma_{VBF} \mathcal{B}_{H \rightarrow WW^*} &= 0.79^{+0.19}_{-0.16} \text{ pb}\end{aligned}$$

agree with the prediction by the Standard Model. The uncertainties in both measurements are reduced with respect to the previous result [55] with integrated luminosity of 36/fb. The observed signal in the VBF analysis category has a significance of 6.6σ . Also an STXS analysis is performed by splitting the signal into eleven categories and measuring each of the cross sections. Also in this analysis, the data agrees with the Standard Model.

In the meanwhile, an interpretation in combination with other Higgs-boson measurements has been performed in Ref. [59]. With respect to a previous combination [51] that does not include the results presented in this thesis, the uncertainties of the κ -measurement were improved. Also the EFT constraints could be improved due to the included HWW result in comparison with the previous interpretation in Ref. [223].

An estimate of the fake lepton background is used as input to the HWW analysis. Various aspects of this estimate are optimized. The statistically limited region with high- p_T muons is considered now with an extrapolation to reduce statistical uncertainties. Lepton working points in the Z +fake estimate are decoupled from the working points in the HWW analysis, which recovers 20% of data. Also the uncertainties related to the WZ CR are reduced. In combination with the larger available dataset, these optimizations result in largely reduced uncertainties when applied to the HWW analysis compared to the previous analysis [55] with 36/fb. The breakdown of uncertainties estimates the uncertainties as 2.4% and 1.0% for the ggF and VBF analysis. This is in comparison to the 6% and 9% in the previous analysis.

The fake estimate in the analysis also sparked the effort to put the Fake Factor Method on a solid mathematical foundation. For the first time, the Fake Factor Method is derived consistently from the Matrix Method for a final state with an arbitrary number of leptons. No approximations are needed. The relevant result for most analyses is equation (5.35). With this equation, the Fake Factor Method is able to provide a background estimate in a blinded analysis, which is impossible with the Matrix Method. The behaviour of the Fake Factor Method is studied with pseudo experiments. Due to the inherent multiplication in the fake estimate, the convenient approximation of Gaussian error propagation only works well when the relative uncertainties of the multiplied event yields are different. Further development including the Fake Factor Method into a maximum-likelihood estimate could be beneficial. To reduce the number of nuisance parameters, a procedure similar to the procedure in the `faketoys` framework [173] could be used to estimate constraints of the fake factors rather than the underlying yields.

The current measurements of the Higgs boson continue the long success story written by big collaborations at CERN. All results indicate that the properties and interactions of the Higgs boson agree with the predictions of the Standard Model. More precise measurements in the future will allow to strengthen these statements or find evidence for new physics. Elaborate interpretations will be crucial in finding subtle hints of new physics in nature. The Run 3 and the high-luminosity LHC will collect the necessary data with increased luminosity and higher centre-of-mass energy. In the meanwhile, analyses strategies need to be improved to extract the most information from the available data. Some suggestions for the analyses discussed in this thesis are outlined here.

9.1 Potential Improvements of the Fake Estimate

One of the important decisions when designing a fake estimate is the choice of working points that define loose and tight leptons. In the Z +fake estimate, every baseline lepton is either loose or tight. One could imagine introducing a third category, intermediate lepton, that separates the tight and loose definitions. Events with these leptons are not used in the final estimate, but purely serve as a validation sample. For the validation, a separate fake factor would be derived in analogy to equation (5.37) with

$$F = \frac{N^i - N_r^i}{N^l - N_r^l}, \quad (9.1)$$

where the superscript i refers to the intermediate selection. This fake factor would be applied to the control selection in the signal region. The resulting estimate could be compared to data to validate the procedure and the general estimate.

The other advantage of defining an intermediate lepton requirement is that the tight and loose selections are separated further. The loose selection would be contaminated less by processes with real leptons. This would increase the purity of fake processes in Figures 6.3

and 6.4 and make the fake estimate more robust against theoretical uncertainties. These benefits, however, would have to be balanced against the disadvantages that the statistical precision decreases and that the selections, between which the extrapolation takes place, become more dissimilar.

9.2 Potential Improvements of the VBF Measurement

With the inclusion of 139/fb of data, the HWW measurement in the VBF production mode is for the first time not limited by data statistical uncertainties anymore. While an increase of the dataset will still benefit the measurement, future analyses will need to focus on reducing systematic uncertainties. Two general areas of improvement are the separation of signal and background and the targeted reduction of the largest uncertainties.

With respect to the boosted decision tree that was used in previous versions of this analysis [55], the DNN constitutes a considerable improvement, because the separation of signal and background is a key ingredient to a counting experiment. A further improvement of the classification algorithm could also allow to explore new phase space in the STXS measurement, for example the EW qqH category between 120 GeV and 350 GeV.

One could imagine using a DNN to define a boundary in the 2^+j phase space between the ggF and VBF SRs. Such a requirement could enhance the ggF and VBF purity in their respective signal regions. A concrete example would be to use a DNN with two output nodes to quantify the ggF -likeness and VBF -likeness of an event. The boundary between the two SRs would be drawn in the two-dimensional space spanned by the two output variables. Alternatively, a two-dimensional histogram created from the two DNN output variables could be used directly to extract the two processes simultaneously. Then, no formal separation between the ggF and VBF SRs is needed. Instead of the one-dimensional binning algorithm, procedures from image processing could be used to cluster regions with a similar process composition (see eg. Ref. [224]). To match the signal kinematics in CRs, the same DNN discriminant could in principle be used.

A potential risk with multi-variate analyses is that the classification is not flexible enough to model data accurately. To improve the flexibility and to attenuate features that are highly dependent on systematic uncertainties, one could try using MC simulation with systematic variations as input to the DNN training. This could lead to a reduction of the systematic shape uncertainties in the DNN discriminant.

Four of the DNN input variables are the combinations m_{ℓ_1,j_1} , m_{ℓ_1,j_2} , m_{ℓ_2,j_1} and m_{ℓ_2,j_2} . These variables tend to be large for VBF events, because of the high-energetic forward jets, and smaller for backgrounds. For the $t\bar{t}$ process specifically, two of the four combinations calculate the invariant mass of daughter particles of the top quark and are therefore bounded by the top mass. To make more specific use of these variables, it could be beneficial to construct the two possible pairings $m_1 = m_{\ell_1,j_1} + m_{\ell_2,j_2}$ and $m_2 = m_{\ell_1,j_2} + m_{\ell_2,j_1}$. Using these

two variables would reduce the number of input parameters and could help to consolidate the DNN.

The variable m_{T2} is defined by the minimum of the four combinations in equation (7.11). Each of these combinations only considers one of the two jets and pairs it with the leptons. This definition implicitly assumes a Wt final state and estimates the lower bound of the invariant mass of the top quark. With the overwhelming amount of $t\bar{t}$ background, however, a more sensible definition might be

$$m'_{T2} = \min(M_{2T}(\ell^{\text{lead}} + j_1, \ell^{\text{sublead}} + j_2), M_{2T}(\ell^{\text{lead}} + j_2, \ell^{\text{sublead}} + j_1)), \quad (9.2)$$

which considers the two possible pairings of jets and leptons in the $t\bar{t}$ decay (cf. Ref. [225]). This way, m'_{T2} should have values below the top-quark mass for the $t\bar{t}$ process, while the random pairings of the jets and leptons in the WW process produce larger values. Even though the variables m_{T2} and m'_{T2} are very similar, the advantage of m'_{T2} is that the distribution of neutrino momenta between the two decay arms is more realistic. If the physically-motivated variable m'_{T2} separates $t\bar{t}$ and WW well, it could also be used to define a WW CR in the VBF analysis. In addition, it could be considered as an input to the DNN with the goal to reject $t\bar{t}$ events.

The breakdown of uncertainties in Table 7.6 shows that the theory uncertainty of the signal process contributes significantly to the cross-section uncertainties. The shower variations have a particularly high impact. Since they affect the amount of additional radiation, they enter the analysis through the CJV. This cut is physically motivated, because the two initial quarks do not exchange colour at leading order and therefore the rapidity gap between them is void of hadronic radiation. However, higher-order corrections can cause hadronic radiation in the vicinity of the jets. To reduce acceptance uncertainties, it could prove beneficial to allow additional jets close to the leading jets. The CJV currently vetoes events with jets above $p_T > 30$ GeV and a centrality of $C_j < 1$. This requirement could be loosened to $C_j < c$, for instance with $c = 0.8$, with the hope to reduce the dependence on the shower uncertainties.

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Appendix A

Electrical Isolation of ITk Strip Sensors

Abstract: The Inner Tracker (ITk) is going to replace the current Inner Detector of the ATLAS experiment before the start of the High-Luminosity LHC in 2026. The outer part of ITk has silicon strip sensors as sensitive material. It is important that currents between these sensors, which are isolated by approximately 350 μm of nitrogen, remain smaller than 70 nA, the lowest expected leakage current through a sensor. Additionally, the threshold voltage, a property of gas discharges, needs to be larger than the maximum bias voltage of 700 V. We have measured the current between silicon sensors. The measurements show that inter-sensor currents are in the order of 0.1 nA and that the threshold voltage is above 1200 V. This shows that the ITk design has sufficient isolation between adjacent sensors without addition of extra insulation.

A.1 Introduction

The inner detector of the ATLAS experiment will be replaced by the ITk during the Long Shutdown 3 (LS3) between 2024 and 2026 to prepare the ATLAS detector for the High-Luminosity LHC phase. ITk is a silicon tracking detector. Its inner layers have a pixel detector while the outer layers are segmented into strips. This report focuses on the strip subsystem, whose technical design report can be found in ref. [226].

The ITk strip detector is subdivided into a barrel and an end-caps region. In the barrel, sensors will be mounted on staves which each hold two rows of 14 sensors. In the end-caps, 9 sensors with different layouts will be mounted on each side of a petal. 32 petals comprise one disk.

Figure A.1: Schematic view of a petal (top) and a stave (bottom) [226]. The blue areas are silicon sensors. Each sensor is read out with one or two hybrids (dark green for petal and light green for stave). One sensor and its hybrid(s) are called module. The red (yellow) lines between sensors indicate regions in which a HV drop can (not) occur.

Figure A.2: Schematic view of two adjacent sensors with a high voltage drop between them. The sensor backplane on the right-hand side is disconnected from the HV. The potential of the backplane extends along the silicon edge up to the guard ring. Red arrows indicate an electric field. Figure not to scale.

Individual sensors are operated at a reverse bias voltage¹ of up to $V_b = 700$ V. If a sensor or a module fails during operation, the high voltage (HV) supply can be interrupted by a HV switch. As a consequence, two adjacent sensors will have a potential difference of V_b . The purpose of this report is to assess whether dedicated insulation between two adjacent sensors is needed to ensure reliable operation. These studies were done in the scope of an ATLAS authorship project.

Section A.2 gives an overview and illustrates which requirements need to be satisfied in the inter-sensor gap. Detailed studies of gas discharges and contamination are summarized in sections A.3 and A.4.3, respectively. Section A.5 lists other effects, that have not been investigated in detail, before section A.6 concludes.

¹A reverse bias voltage would usually be indicated by a negative voltage. Since the sign of the voltage does not matter for the studies in this report, a positive voltage will be used for simplicity.

A.2 Overview

An overview of the critical regions in the detector is given in Fig. A.1, which shows a single stave and petal. On a stave, all modules have individual HV switches. On a petal, all modules, which are placed at the same radius, share the same switch. Therefore, some gaps (marked in red) can potentially experience a HV drop and the involved sensors need to be sufficiently isolated. This is less critical for gaps between modules at the same radius (yellow), because the sensors will be on the same potential. The voltage is applied on the aluminized backplane of the sensor, while the readout side is kept at ground (see Fig. A.2).

In the entire strip detector, the total length of sensor edges that would need to be insulated is approximately 3 km; 2 km in the barrel and 1 km in the end-caps². Because every gap has two sensor edges, this corresponds to a total gap length of 1.5 km.

A.2.1 Origin of Crossover Current

Adjacent sensors are not touching and there is no obvious electrical connection between them. This raises the question where crossover currents³ can flow between the sensors. There are two major concerns:

- **Gas discharge:** In the high electric field between two adjacent sensors, free electrons in the surrounding nitrogen gas are accelerated towards the sensors. On their way they ionize nitrogen molecules. As a result, further electrons are released, cause a chain reaction and consequently a high current. Above a threshold voltage V_t , a breakdown behaviour is expected. Gas discharges are addressed in section A.3.
- **Contamination of gap:** The glue (SE4445⁴) or possibly dust settles between the sensors and facilitates charge flow. Section A.4.3 summarizes tries to estimate the impact of contamination.

The crossover current between two sensors depends on the gap width between these sensors. Smaller gaps typically support larger currents⁵. The nominal distance between sensors in the barrel and end-cap are listed in Tab. A.1. It also shows engineering tolerances, placement

²Numbers calculated according to CAD file 2017-11-08-PETAL-RH.stp.

³The current between two adjacent sensors will be called crossover current I_c in the following to distinguish it from leakage current I_l through the p-n-junction of a single sensor.

⁴Dow Corning⁶, SE4445 CV Kit.

⁵While this statement seems intuitive, section A.3 shows that there might be exceptions to this in gas discharges.

	Barrel [μm]	End-cap [μm]
Nominal gap width	346	500
Cut edge position	20	20
Sensor placement precision	50	50
Worst-case gap	206	360

Table A.1: Estimate of the worst-case gap width. The nominal gap width [227] is listed as well as the engineering tolerance [228] and the placement precision for each sensor. The worst-case is calculated by deducting each tolerance twice from the nominal gap width, since a gap has two adjacent modules. The official requirement for the placement precision will be specified in a document [229], which is not finalized at this time. As a reference, the gantry, which will place the sensors, is designed to have an intrinsic precision of 25 μm or less.

errors and the resulting “worst-case” gap at which the detector must still operate reliably. The rest of this report will focus on the inter-sensor gap in the barrel, because of the narrower gap width.

A.2.2 Requirements for Detector Operation

If a HV drop between adjacent sensors causes high crossover currents, various effects could lead to a detector failure.

- **Localized release of heat:** If a gas discharge between two sensors develops a spark, the localized heating could physically damage the sensor. Sparks do not form below a threshold voltage V_t that will be defined in section A.3. We will require that the bias voltage be smaller than the threshold voltage $V_b < V_t$.
- **Release of heat:** Usually, the main source of heating is the leakage current through the sensor. The heat released scales with the power $P = VI$ and can cause thermal runaway because leakage currents grow exponentially with temperature. Additional heat released due to crossover currents could contribute to thermal runaway. To avoid this, the crossover current should be significantly smaller than the leakage current $I_c \ll I_l$. Other reasons to keep the crossover current small are high power consumption and the ability to track radiation damage using I_l .
- **Drop of bias voltage:** A low-pass filter is built in series with the sensor. At the end of lifetime, the total provided voltage of 750 V will drop across the low-pass filter (50 V) and the sensor (700 V). A significant crossover current would increase the voltage drop across the low-pass filter and decrease the bias voltage. This could lead to an incomplete depletion of the sensor material and compromise its performance. This is another reason for the requirement $I_c \ll I_l$.

- **Inducing a signal:** Even though crossover currents are DC, they will have an AC component. A high-frequency contribution could cause a local charge distribution on the aluminum backplane, which would couple capacitively to the strip implant and induce a fake signal. The origin of the AC component is white noise on the one hand and fluctuations in the gas discharge on the other hand. Requiring that $V_b < V_t$ should keep the gas discharge process rather continuous and minimize this effect.

A.2.3 Previous Studies

In a previous authorship project [230], Sam Ng investigated suitable ways of applying an insulating Polyurethane solution on the sensor edges. He tested applying Polyurethane manually with a brush, marker pen, glue dispenser, spraying and dipping the sensor in the solution. Of these methods, the best results were achieved with the marker pen. To obtain a minimum thickness at the edges and corners, multiple layers of coating had to be applied. This, however, lead to large variations in Polyurethane thickness with values up to 500 μm . The maximum allowed thickness is approximately 100 μm if the material is applied on both of the facing sensor edges.

A.3 Breakdown of Gases

The conceptual understanding of gas discharges was developed in the early 20th century and largely driven by Townsend, who first linked gas discharges to the process of ionization. This section summarizes the behaviour of a gas between two conducting plates at different electric potential following ref. [231]. The theoretical understanding will be used to characterize the gas discharge between two silicon sensors.

The transition from a non-conducting to a conducting gas is called breakdown. It is seeded by free electrons released from gas atoms due to radiation. These free electrons are accelerated in the electric field between the conducting plates, ionize other atoms and cause a chain reaction. The positive ions move towards the cathode. If they reach sufficiently high energies, they can knock out electrons from the cathode material which start a new avalanche.

While electrons gain energy in the electric field, they lose energy due to scattering with gas molecules. They can also be removed from the gap by diffusing out of the relevant region or recombining with ions. Therefore, the breakdown process is not only sensitive to the voltage V_g and distance d between the plates, but also to the number of gas atoms, which will be parametrized with pressure p ⁶.

⁶Note that molecule density and pressure are related through temperature. ITk will be operated at negative temperatures with a coolant temperature of approximately -35°C [226]. In the approximation of an

Figure A.3: Voltage across the gap as a function of current (modified after [231]). The gas discharge at small currents (BC) is called Townsend Dark discharge, followed by the normal glow discharge (DE). In the transition between these two regions, the homogeneous electric field of the Townsend Dark discharge field starts to get distorted by free charges in the gap. The plateau BC can be used to determine the threshold voltage. The abnormal gas discharge (EF) and the arc discharge (GH) are not of importance to this report.

To define the threshold voltage at which the gap exhibits critical behaviour, let us look at the effect of a single seed electron at the cathode. This electron gets accelerated in the electric field and causes ionization. The positive ions move towards the cathode and produce secondary electrons on impact. The threshold voltage V_t is defined as the voltage at which one seed electron generates on average exactly one secondary electron at the cathode. Below the threshold voltage, the current caused by a single electron dies out (non self-sustained current), while above the threshold voltage a single electron can cause a gas breakdown (self-sustained current).

In the experimental setup, the gas gap is in series with a resistor R . With an external voltage V , the voltage drop across the gap is $V_g = V - RI$. Fig. A.3 schematically shows the variable V_g as a function of current I , which itself depends on V . The y-value of the first plateau region corresponds to the threshold voltage. The origin of this plateau can be understood by looking at the effect of a small increase in V : It causes V_g to grow and exceed the threshold voltage. The gap is in the self-sustained regime and the number of free charge carriers increases. This, however, also increases the conductivity of the gap corresponding to a smaller resistance. Therefore, the voltage drop across the gap decreases and the equilibrium is reached again at $V_g = V_t$. Above a certain voltage V , this explanation fails because charge accumulation in the gap causes inhomogeneous behaviour.

ideal gas, the equation $N/V = p/k_B T$ suggests that the number density is greater at small temperatures. Neglecting this effect will result in an additional distance safety factor of $\Delta T/T \approx 15\%$ for all processes related to gas discharges.

Figure A.4: Paschen curves in different gases (modified after [231]). The threshold voltage V_t depends on the pressure p and the distance d between two conductors. At distances of $200\ \mu\text{m}$, air and nitrogen have a similar threshold voltage.

The theoretical description motivates the experimental procedure of finding the threshold voltage. The current I as a function of the external voltage V is recorded and converted into the form $V_g = V - RI$. The first maximum of $V_g(I)$ is the threshold voltage V_t .

As established before, the threshold voltage depends on the distance between the capacitor plates and the gas pressure. According to Paschen's law, the threshold voltage depends only on the product pd . It follows the form

$$V_t = \frac{B(pd)}{C + \ln(pd)} \quad (\text{A.1})$$

with pressure p , distance d and the constants B , C . Paschen curves for different gases are shown in Fig. A.4.

The qualitative behaviour of the curves can be understood by looking at the limits. At large distances, a certain electric field $E = V/d$ is needed to accelerate electrons and ions sufficiently, which requires a high voltage. The same reasoning holds for large pressures, where the electric field has to be large enough to overcome energy loss in scattering. At small distances or pressures, the electric field causes a large acceleration, but there are only a few gas atoms in the gap that can be ionized. With insufficient ionization there is no avalanche and currents are non self-sustained. Hence, the threshold voltage is large. Between these extreme cases, there is a combination of pressure and distance with a minimum threshold voltage.

Paschen's law was established when small values of pd could only be obtained by reducing pressure. In more recent publications the gas discharge behaviour has been investigated in

Figure A.5: Setup to measure gas discharges between silicon sensors. In a probe station, two SCT sensors are placed on different sheets of non-conducting acrylic glass. The sensors are weighted down (not shown in picture) to prevent them from moving under the influence of the electric field. The relative position of the two sensors can be changed. HV tabs [233, 234] are welded to the backplane of the sensors. They are used to contact the sensors with needles and apply a HV between them. The circuit also has a $20\text{ M}\Omega$ resistor in series as indicated in red.

micro gaps. With small gap sizes it has been found that the threshold voltage has lower values than the Paschen curves at small pd . An example can be found in Fig. 4 of ref. [232]. This figure suggests that Paschen’s law holds down to distances of approximately $30\text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in nitrogen at atmospheric pressure.

A.4 Experiment

A.4.1 Experimental Setup

To get an estimate of the possible crossover currents mediated by a gas discharge, the setup shown in Fig. A.5 is used. The edges of two silicon sensors form a thin gap which resembles the inter-sensor gap in ITk. Since ITk sensors were unavailable for testing, two W32 sensors of the SCT detector were used instead. These sensors have p-in-n strip implants as opposed to the ITk n-in-p implants. However, the p-n-junction is not investigated here and should not influence the results. The SCT sensors are “blade diced”, while the ITk sensors are “stealth diced”. In principle, SCT sensors are expected to have more spiky features along the edge with high associated electric fields [235], so that they should give a conservative estimate of the breakdown voltage for ITk sensors.

The SCT sensors are aligned along the top edge so that the gap has a length of approximately 72 mm. The distance between the sensors is determined with a digital micrometer⁷ that measures the displacement of the movable stage. The micrometer is zeroed when the two sensors touch. After that, relative displacements of the stage are recorded. Even when the sensors touch, there is a gap of approximately 25 μm visible in the microscope. To use the more conservative estimate, 25 μm are added to all micrometer readings.

The described setup is referred to as setup 1. For a later measurement, an air suspension was added to minimize the effect of vibrations on the measurement, which is then referred to as setup 2.

Current-voltage curves in setup 1 and 2 are taken in an air-filled gap. During ITk operation, however, the detector will be flooded with nitrogen. At the examined distances, the threshold voltage is expected to be similar in air and nitrogen (see Fig. A.4). To take experimental data in a nitrogen atmosphere, the sensors were glued to a Kapton-covered surface using SE4445. A thin line of glue was applied far away from the inter-sensor gap so that it would not affect the electrical properties. Between the sensors and the Kapton tape were spacers of approximately 140 μm thickness. The width of the gap was controlled with fishing line with approximately 165 μm in diameter. The fishing line was removed after the SE4445 had cured. This assembly was put in a metal test box, which could be flushed with nitrogen (setup 3).

The pressure during the measurements⁸ $p_{\text{meas.}}$ is different from the pressure on ATLAS level p_{ATLAS} . Because the gas discharge properties depend on pressure p and gap width d , the measured gap widths are scaled by the ratio of pressures

$$d_{\text{ATLAS}} = \frac{p_{\text{meas.}}}{p_{\text{ATLAS}}} d_{\text{meas.}}$$

to get the distance equivalent on ATLAS altitude using $p_{\text{ATLAS}} = 95.813 \text{ Pa}$. All distances quoted in this report are scaled this way.

The measurements in all three setups are taken in the same way. High voltage is applied between the backplanes of the two SCT sensors using a Keithley source meter 2657A. For different sensor spacings, current-voltage curves are taken in the voltage range of [0 V, 1500 V] with a step size of 20 V. The measurement is automated and the current is recorded with a delay of one second after the voltage is changed.

Figure A.6: Five current-voltage curves are shown for each gap width measured with setup 1 (top) and setup 2 (bottom). Within a set of same gap width, dark curves are taken first. The gap widths are scaled by the ratio of pressures $p_{\text{meas.}}/p_{\text{ATLAS}}$. The threshold voltage is clearly visible as the current jumps by one to two orders of magnitude.

In the lower plot, the red curve indicates Ohm's law with a resistance of $20\text{ M}\Omega$ (resistance of the series resistor) for comparison with the purple curves.

Figure A.7: Current-voltage curves with a gap with of $184\ \mu\text{m}$ in air and nitrogen. The numbers in the legend indicate in which order the curves are recorded. Within a set, dark curves are taken first. Between measurement 7 and 8, dust was removed in the gap.

A.4.2 Gas Discharge Results

Fig. A.6 shows five sets of current-voltage curves for each gap width. Short sensor spacings were measured first. All measurement series have qualitatively the same shape with the exception of three curves at small gap widths. This extraordinary response will be discussed below. At low voltages, the curves show a mild saturation behaviour towards voltages of $500\ \text{V}$ as free charges in the gap are collected at the sensors. In the case of small gaps, the current grows relatively soon at voltages higher than $500\ \text{V}$, while at large distances a significant increase only occurs beyond $700\ \text{V}$. This increase can be explained by gas amplification⁹. The currents exhibit a large jump as they pass the threshold voltage.

Fig. A.7 shows the different response in current-voltage curves between air and nitrogen measured with setup 3. The first four measurements qualitatively show the same behaviour. In the following three measurements, a complete breakdown of the gap is observed, similar to the one in Fig. A.6. After measurement 7, the test box was opened and the gap was

⁷Mitutoyo Corp. ID-C112E

⁸Measurements were taken at the research institute TRIUMF in Vancouver, close to sea level.

⁹It is unclear to what extent humidity in the air contributes to the growing current. This region looks qualitatively different in a nitrogen atmosphere (compare Fig. A.7).

Figure A.8: Threshold voltage as a function of gap width summarizing the curves in Fig. A.6 and A.7. Values for the threshold voltage are averaged over datasets with the same gap excluding outliers that are affected by contamination. The voltage error has a statistical component and a contribution from the voltage sampling. The distance uncertainty is dominated by the sensor roughness. The distance errors in setup 3 are correlated. A Paschen Curve as defined in eq. (A.1) is fitted to the measurements in air using the free parameters B and C .

cleaned with dry air in an attempt to remove contamination. The next two measurements suggest that this was successful, as data points line up with the first four measurements again. It seems likely that contamination is also responsible for the similar behaviour in Fig. A.6. After flushing the box with nitrogen for a few hours, the next five current-voltage curves were taken back to back.

Although the gap width is the same, the current in air increases at lower voltages than in nitrogen. It is possible that the different gas mixture is responsible, which is reasonable because nitrogen has a slightly higher ionization energy than oxygen. It is, however, also possible that humidity in the air is responsible for the different behaviour. In any case, currents $I_c \ll 1$ nA are observed in pure nitrogen. These currents only increase significantly close to the threshold voltage.

All measured threshold voltages are summarized in Fig. A.8. No significant difference is observed between the threshold voltage in air and nitrogen. Within the uncertainties, the data agrees well with the functional form of eq. (A.1), which is essentially a linear function in this regime. The yellow shaded area shows the operating range of the detector. The plot

suggests that even in the worst case, i.e. at an inter-sensor gap of 200 μm and the highest bias voltage of $V_b = 700\text{ V}$, the gas-filled gap will not experience electrical breakdown.

A.4.3 Contamination

The ideal case of a non-contaminated gap was summarized in the previous chapter. If there are other materials in the gap, they could affect the electrical behaviour and support higher crossover currents. In particular, contamination due to dust is imaginable even though the sensors will be assembled in a clean-room environment. Also the SE4445, which fixes the sensor backplane to the bus tape, could penetrate the gap and facilitate charge flow. The impact of contamination is examined in two different tests.

Lint

The previously described setup 3 is used, in which SCT sensors are glued to Kapton tape at a fixed distance. Lint is rubbed off a lab wipe and is allowed to settle on the sensors. Some of the fibers cover the inter-sensor gap. Current-voltage curves in air are recorded in the same way as before and compared to the non-contaminated gap as seen in Fig. A.9. The curves look qualitatively similar and the threshold voltage is unchanged around 1300 V. The currents in the lint-contaminated case, however, are significantly larger. At 700 V, currents up to 100 nA are observed whereas the clean gap allows currents of less than 0.1 nA. Also conditioning is clearly visible. A complete breakdown as observed in Fig. A.7 could not be reproduced.

Glue

In setup 3, the glue is far away from the sensor gap and not expected to influence the electrical properties. To test how the electrical response changes with SE4445 in the gap, the sensors are removed from setup 3 and reglued to the Kapton surface. In this new arrangement (setup 4), SE4445 is applied closely to the sensor edges and leaks into the gap when the sensors are placed. It becomes clear under the microscope that the gap is free of glue in the vicinity of the sensor corners, while glue penetrates the entire gap width in the central region. The glue height does not exceed the sensor height significantly.

The results of the electrical tests are depicted in Fig. A.10. The glue-filled gap exhibits the same general behaviour as the non-contaminated gap. In both the air and nitrogen atmosphere, the current increases with external voltage and jumps by orders of magnitude at a certain voltage.

The effect of glue contamination can be estimated by comparing the nitrogen curve to the corresponding data points in setup 3. The differences at low voltage are insignificant and

Figure A.9: Current-voltage curves for the contaminated inter-sensor gap compared to the clean gap in setup 3. The measurement without contamination was taken first, afterwards the three successive measurements with lint (dark to light) were taken.

Figure A.10: Current-voltage characteristics of a glue-filled gap in an air and nitrogen environment. The green and purple curves are taken in setup 4, while the reference data points in grey are taken in the non-contaminated setup 3 and are identical to Fig. A.7.

probably due to imprecise zeroing of the Ammeter. Above 700 V, the glue allows currents to grow faster with voltage and causes current fluctuations below the threshold voltage. The critical behaviour is less pronounced since there is an intermediate step at about 100 nA. Compared to the clean gap, the threshold voltage varies more and the average is shifted to smaller values despite the slightly larger gap width.

While gas discharges are well-understood, the effects caused by glue are less obvious. Charges could travel along the glue surface, possibly affected by the amount of moisture. The fluctuations in current could be related to this process. The origin of the additional current plateau at 100 nA is unclear.

It should be mentioned that the first electrical tests of the glue-filled gap in air showed strong conditioning. Currents in the order of 1 μ A were measured at 700 V. Over the next 10 iterations, currents dropped to values around 1 nA, which matches the data in Fig. A.10. No reversal of this conditioning has been observed after a few days.

A.5 Other Considerations

ITk needs to withstand a large amount of radiation and temperature cycling and needs to be operational for many years. These conditions could potentially change the electrical properties of the sensor and impact the crossover current. The following effects have been considered, but are believed to be irrelevant. In case of doubt, further studies might be needed.

- **Whiskers:** This phenomenon has first been observed in soldering with lead-free solder. The solder material grows thin hairs of conducting material that can grow up to millimeters in length. This is mainly supported by mechanical stress, high temperatures and electrical fields.

In a survey of related literature, no documentation for whiskers growth in pure aluminium or silicon was found as long as neither mechanical stress nor high temperatures are involved. Therefore, it seems unlikely that whiskers will grow in the inter-sensor gap. This, however, has not been investigated in this report and might need further study.

- **Radiation damage:** In silicon sensors, the most fatal kind of radiation damage are lattice defects increasing the leakage current. These are irrelevant for gas discharge studies. But it might be possible that radiation changes the work function of the oxidized silicon surface. A smaller work function could support a lower threshold voltage, because electrons are knocked out of the silicon dioxide surface more easily. The result is a lower threshold voltage.

Even though radiation changes the silicon lattice and introduces defects, it does not change the element composition. Different elements could change the work function, but intuitively the work function should not depend on the number of lattice defects.

- **Thermal expansion:** When silicon sensors undergo thermal cycling, they expand and shrink. Since the thin layer of silicon dioxide on the surface has a smaller thermal expansion coefficient than silicon, thermal cycling could cause cracks on the surface. These would uncover pure silicon whose different electric behaviour could change the crossover current.

It seems unlikely that this scenario will occur. First of all, cooling a sensor lets the bulk material shrink faster than the surface. Cracks would therefore only occur when heating the sensors. Secondly, the surface layer of silicon dioxide is very thin (in the order of nanometers) and it is questionable if it can be described by the macroscopic thermal expansion coefficient. On these small scales, sheers on the material boundary might compensate the mechanical stress.

A.6 Conclusion

SCT sensors have been used to assess whether crossover currents between non-insulated silicon sensors could compromise ITk performance. It was argued in section A.2.2 that the bias voltage must be smaller than the threshold voltage $V_b < V_t$ and that the crossover current must be much smaller than the leakage current $I_c \ll I_l$ to ensure reliable detector operation.

The requirement $V_b < V_t$ is satisfied as shown in Fig. A.8. The data points agree well with theory expectation and show that the threshold voltage exceeds 1200 V for gap widths above 200 μm . The threshold voltage is lower when glue contaminates the gap. Crossover currents in nitrogen are small over a large range of voltages (Fig. A.7) and only grow close to the threshold voltage. Currents smaller than 0.1 nA have been measured below 700 V. After estimating the leakage current¹⁰ at -30°C , the crossover current $I_c \lesssim 0.2 \text{ nA}$ is much smaller than the leakage current of 70 nA to 1.1 mA (depending on radiation damage).

These two results suggest that the ITk strip detector can be operated without risking HV discharges, even if there is no dedicated insulation between adjacent sensors. Glue spills in the inter-sensor gap should be avoided unless further studies unveil the electrical impact of SE4445. The sensor gap must not be contaminated with dust, because this can cause a complete breakdown of the gap (Fig. A.7).

¹⁰The leakage current at -30°C is estimated using equation 2.16 from ref. [236] and values from ref. [226]

Before the final detector assembly, modules on staves and petals will undergo electrical tests in air. During these tests higher crossover currents are expected than in a nitrogen atmosphere (Fig. A.7 below 700 V), but the currents will still be much smaller than 70 nA. The threshold voltage in both cases is comparable. Hence, electrical tests in air will show similar behaviour as in nitrogen.

Appendix B

Equations for Data-Driven Methods

B.1 Inverted Two-lepton Matrix

The inverted matrices in the Matrix Method become increasingly complicated at high lepton multiplicities. It is still feasible in the two-lepton selection to write down the terms fairly concisely. For reference, the inverted matrix of equation (5.4) is displayed here. For an explanation about the notation refer to section 5.2.

$$\hat{M} = \begin{pmatrix} ((-1 + f_1)(-1 + f_2)) & ((-1 + f_1)f_2) & (f_1(-1 + f_2)) & (f_1f_2) \\ (-1 + f_1 + r_2 - f_1r_2) & (r_2 - f_1r_2) & (f_1 - f_1r_2) & (-f_1r_2) \\ (-1 + f_2 + r_1 - f_2r_1) & (f_2 - f_2r_1) & (r_1 - f_2r_1) & (-f_2r_1) \\ ((-1 + r_1)(-1 + r_2)) & ((-1 + r_1)r_2) & (r_1(-1 + r_2)) & (r_1r_2) \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$\frac{\hat{M}}{((f_1 - r_1)(f_2 - r_2))} \begin{pmatrix} N^{tt} \\ N^{tl} \\ N^{lt} \\ N^{ll} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} N_{rr} \\ N_{rf} \\ N_{fr} \\ N_{ff} \end{pmatrix} \quad (\text{B.2})$$

B.2 Equation Relating Relative Uncertainties

In certain configurations, the uncertainties of the Fake Factor estimate are driven by the multiplication of the near-Gaussian distributions a and b , that are defined through equation (5.58). Starting from the requirement that the relative uncertainties of the terms a and b be equal, equation (5.61) can be derived. The explicit derivation is shown here.

$$\sigma_a^{\text{rel}} = \sigma_b^{\text{rel}} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow \frac{\sqrt{N^{tt} + \sigma_{N_r^{tt}}^2}}{N^{tt} - N_r^{tt}} = \frac{\sqrt{N^l + \sigma_{N_r^l}^2}}{N^l - N_r^l} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

$$\Rightarrow (N^{l^2} - 2N^l N_r^l + N_r^{l^2})(N^{tt} + \sigma_{N_r^{tt}}^2) = (N^{tt} - N_r^{tt})^2 (N^l + \sigma_{N_r^l}^2) \quad (\text{B.5})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow N^{l^2} - 2N^l N_r^l + N_r^{l^2} = \frac{(N^{tt} - N_r^{tt})^2}{N^{tt} + \sigma_{N_r^{tt}}^2} N^l + \frac{(N^{tt} - N_r^{tt})^2}{N^{tt} + \sigma_{N_r^{tt}}^2} \sigma_{N_r^l}^2 \quad (\text{B.6})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow N^{l^2} - 2N^l N_r^l + N_r^{l^2} = 2AN^l + 2A\sigma_{N_r^l}^2 \quad \text{with} \quad A = \frac{(N^{tt} - N_r^{tt})^2}{2(N^{tt} + \sigma_{N_r^{tt}}^2)} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow N^{l^2} - 2(N_r^l + A)N^l + N_r^{l^2} - 2A\sigma_{N_r^l}^2 = 0 \quad (\text{B.8})$$

$$\Leftrightarrow N^l = N_r^l + A \pm \sqrt{(N_r^l + A)^2 - N_r^{l^2} + 2A\sigma_{N_r^l}^2} \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Appendix C

Uncertainties in Post-Fit Plots

In the DNN distribution in the SR, the yield and uncertainty in every bin is explicitly encoded in the likelihood. Therefore, the post-fit yields and uncertainties of the model can be depicted in plots, like in Figures 7.9 and 8.3. For other distributions, it is less clear how the fit result influences the distributions. In Figures 7.4 and 7.7, the following method is used.

For each process, the post-fit yield in the SR is extracted from the DNN distribution and divided by the pre-fit prediction. This term is an “effective normalization factor” N parametrizing how much a process yield changes due to the likelihood minimization. This includes effects caused by nuisance parameters and is therefore different from the normalization factor in the fit. Every process in the pre-fit histogram h^{pre} of the considered variable is multiplied with its effective normalization factor to get the post-fit yield

$$h^{\text{post}} = N h^{\text{pre}}. \quad (\text{C.1})$$

The relative post-fit uncertainties of a process are estimated by considering the effect of each nuisance parameter variation on the process yield. A nuisance parameter k is varied by $\pm 1\sigma$ and the difference between the varied yield $h(\theta_k)$ and the nominal yield $h(\theta)$ is called $\Delta(\theta_k) = h(\theta) - h(\theta_k)$. This variation is performed for all pairs of nuisance parameters in order to account for correlations as expressed in the correlation matrix ρ_{kl} . Then, the relative post-fit uncertainty of a process is given by

$$\frac{\sigma^{\text{post}}}{h^{\text{post}}} = \frac{\sqrt{\sum_{kl} \Delta(\theta_k) \rho_{kl} \Delta(\theta_l)}}{h^{\text{pre}}}. \quad (\text{C.2})$$

In the special case of uncorrelated nuisance parameters, the numerator on the right-hand side simplifies to taking the quadrature sum of all uncertainties.

Appendix D

Additional STXS Material

D.1 STXS Stage 1.2 Categorization

Figure D.1: STXS stage 1.2 categorization that is taken as a basis for the reduced categorization scheme in section 8.1. The figures are replicated from [237–239].

D.2 Normalization Factors

Analysis Category and Phase Space		WW	$t\bar{t}/Wt$	Z/γ^*
$N_{\text{jet}}=0$	ggF $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	$1.00^{+0.07}_{-0.07}$	$0.94^{+0.23}_{-0.18}$	$0.95^{+0.07}_{-0.06}$
$N_{\text{jet}}=1$	ggF $p_{T,H} < 60$ GeV	$0.98^{+0.19}_{-0.18}$	$1.07^{+0.21}_{-0.17}$	$0.99^{+0.10}_{-0.09}$
$N_{\text{jet}}=1$	ggF $60 \leq p_{T,H} < 120$ GeV	$1.03^{+0.24}_{-0.22}$	$1.07^{+0.22}_{-0.17}$	$1.04^{+0.11}_{-0.10}$
$N_{\text{jet}}=1$	ggF $120 \leq p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	$1.04^{+0.21}_{-0.20}$	$1.04^{+0.20}_{-0.16}$	$1.14^{+0.16}_{-0.15}$
$N_{\text{jet}} < 2$	ggF $p_{T,H} \geq 200$ GeV	$1.08^{+0.23}_{-0.21}$	$0.92^{+0.14}_{-0.11}$	$1.06^{+0.26}_{-0.24}$
$N_{\text{jet}} \geq 2$	ggF $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	$0.87^{+0.41}_{-0.37}$	$0.97^{+0.24}_{-0.20}$	$1.07^{+0.20}_{-0.16}$
$N_{\text{jet}} \geq 2$	ggF $p_{T,H} \geq 200$ GeV	$0.68^{+0.39}_{-0.30}$	$1.00^{+0.29}_{-0.25}$	$1.09^{+0.32}_{-0.27}$
$N_{\text{jet}} \geq 2$	VBF $350 \leq m_{jj} < 700$ GeV, $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	–	$0.97^{+0.29}_{-0.21}$	$1.36^{+0.51}_{-0.38}$
$N_{\text{jet}} \geq 2$	VBF $m_{jj} \geq 700$ GeV, $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	–	$1.00^{+0.37}_{-0.24}$	$1.13^{+0.47}_{-0.34}$
$N_{\text{jet}} \geq 2$	VBF $m_{jj} \geq 350$ GeV, $p_{T,H} \geq 200$ GeV	–	$0.94^{+0.22}_{-0.18}$	$1.12^{+0.46}_{-0.34}$

Table D.1: Normalization factors extracted in the combined STXS fit. The values are mostly constrained in the CRs. Their uncertainties are correlated with systematic effects. Because these systematic effects are similar in the SRs, the effective uncertainty on the process normalization is typically smaller than the uncertainty quoted here.

D.3 ggF Signal Regions

Figure D.2: Post-fit distributions of $m_{T,H}$ in the ggF 0j SRs in the binning used for the fit [127]. The depicted regions differ by the selected range of $m_{\ell\ell}$ and $p_{T,\ell}^{\text{sublead}}$. These distributions are nearly identical to the 0j SRs in the total cross-section measurement as indicated in the plot. Post-fit uncertainties on the total background yield are shown as a hatched band. The middle panel shows the ratio of data over the prediction and the bottom panel highlights the signal by subtracting the background estimate from the total yield.

Figure D.3: Post-fit distributions of $m_{T,H}$ in the ggF 1j SRs in the binning used for the fit [127]. The depicted regions differ by the selected range of $p_{T,H}$ as indicated in the plot. Post-fit uncertainties on the total background yield are shown as a hatched band. The middle panel shows the ratio of data over the prediction and the bottom panel highlights the signal by subtracting the background estimate from the total yield.

Figure D.4: Post-fit distributions of $m_{T,H}$ in the ggF 2^+j SRs in the binning used for the fit [127]. The depicted regions differ by the selected range of $p_{T,H}$ and $m_{\ell\ell}$ as indicated in the plot. Post-fit uncertainties on the total background yield are shown as a hatched band. The middle panel shows the ratio of data over the prediction and the bottom panel highlights the signal by subtracting the background estimate from the total yield.

D.4 Measured Cross Sections

STXS category ($\sigma_i \times \mathcal{B}_{H \rightarrow WW^*}$)	Value		Uncertainty [fb]				SM prediction [fb]
	[fb]	Total	Stat	Exp	Sig Theo	Bkg Theo	
<i>ggH-0j</i> , low $p_{T,H}$ $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	7000	+900 -900	+400 -400	+600 -500	+300 -300	+600 -500	5900 ± 400
<i>ggH-1j</i> , very low $p_{T,H}$ $p_{T,H} < 60$ GeV	1190	+820 -840	+390 -390	+380 -380	+70 -60	+550 -580	1400 ± 200
<i>ggH-1j</i> , low $p_{T,H}$ $60 \leq p_{T,H} < 120$ GeV	710	+510 -510	+290 -290	+270 -260	+30 -30	+340 -340	970 ± 150
<i>ggH-1j</i> , med $p_{T,H}$ $120 \leq p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	230	+130 -120	+90 -90	+60 -60	+10 -10	+60 -50	160 ± 30
<i>ggH-2j</i> , low $p_{T,H}$ $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	1560	+800 -800	+350 -350	+400 -400	+90 -80	+550 -540	1010 ± 210
<i>ggH</i> , high $p_{T,H}$ $p_{T,H} \geq 200$ GeV	270	+100 -100	+70 -70	+40 -40	+30 -10	+50 -40	122 ± 34
EW <i>qqH-2j</i> , low m_{jj} -low $p_{T,H}$ $350 \leq m_{jj} < 700$ GeV, $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	-20	+60 -60	+40 -40	+30 -40	+10 -20	+20 -30	109 ± 14
EW <i>qqH-2j</i> , med m_{jj} -low $p_{T,H}$ $700 \leq m_{jj} < 1000$ GeV, $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	28	+33 -30	+27 -24	+12 -13	+10 -8	+11 -11	56 ± 6
EW <i>qqH-2j</i> , high m_{jj} -low $p_{T,H}$ $1000 \leq m_{jj} < 1500$ GeV, $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	54	+26 -24	+23 -20	+8 -8	+7 -5	+7 -7	51 ± 5
EW <i>qqH-2j</i> , very high m_{jj} -low $p_{T,H}$ $m_{jj} \geq 1500$ GeV, $p_{T,H} < 200$ GeV	48	+19 -17	+17 -15	+5 -5	+5 -3	+4 -4	50 ± 4
EW <i>qqH-2j</i> , high $p_{T,H}$ $m_{jj} \geq 350$ GeV, $p_{T,H} \geq 200$ GeV	36	+15 -13	+13 -12	+3 -3	+4 -3	+3 -3	32 ± 3

Figure D.5: Measured cross sections in the STXS SRs [127] (cf. Figure 8.4).